

**NEURO - EXPERIMENT
IN
ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING**

Thesis submitted

By

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Registration Number: 21SUDLIT01

Dated: 01 Mar 2021

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment for the

**Award of the
Degree of**

DOCTOR OF LETTERS (D. Litt.)

In

PSYCHOLOGY

**Department of Psychology
College of Social Science and Humanities**

**Srinivas University
Mangaluru, Karnataka State
India**

October 2021

CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

I, **COL DR JYOTIRMAYA SATPATHY** declare that this thesis, entitled **NEURO - EXPERIMENT IN ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING** submitted for the award of the Degree of **DOCTOR OF LETTERS in PSYCHOLOGY** of this University, has not been submitted earlier for the award of any Degree or Diploma of this or any other University.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that this thesis entitled **NEURO - EXPERIMENT IN ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING** has been submitted by **COL DR JYOTIRMAYA SATPATHY** for the award of the Degree of **DOCTOR OF LETTERS in PSYCHOLOGY** of Srinivas University.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

**"Once you make a decision, the universe
conspires to make it happen."**

..... Ralph Waldo Emerson

Psychological change has come a long way fast. In recent years' researchers have developed a fine - grained understanding of different behaviours in different contexts and neuromanagement processes behind them. My pathway to management and behavioral decision research has been the by - product of an academic maneuver. I have read each paper, article, text that I have cited in this thesis. To ensure that I describe facts, figures, statistical data findings accurately I have been in contact with all authors whose research I cited as evidence. I take an oath that I did my best to provide objective findings and full disclosure.

Humble genuflection and I acknowledge with a deep sense of obligation to Shri CA A Raghavendra Rao, Hon'ble Chancellor, for his kind blessings to pursue this programme. I am truly inspired to learn of his aim to transform Society through education by setting up academic institutions in dynamic equilibrium with its social, ecological and economic environment striving continuously for excellence in education, research and technological service to the nation.

Humble obeisance to Prof. P S Aithal Hon'ble Vice - Chancellor for his perennial blessings during the entire journey. This thesis is a by – product of his constant blessings and who travelled along my research journey by withstanding the vagaries of neuro - research 'monsoon'.

Big thank you to Prof. Praveen B M, Director - Research and Innovation Council, the ever responding academic champion of our University. His constant help and counsel did really help my time and make my academic journey free of any turbulence.

'Gurus';Sheena Iyengar, V. S. Ramachandran, Vasily Klucharev, George Lowenstein, Paul Camerer, Antonio Damasio, Antonio Bechara, Antonio Rangel, Agnieszka Tymula, Brian Knutson, Drazen Prelec, Christian Ruff, Willem Verbeke,

Bernd Weber, Ming Hsu, Valerie Reyna, Uma Karmarkar, Kerstin Preuschoff, Hilke Plassmann, Ivana Bulog, Scott Heuttel, Moran Cerf, John Baron, Fang Ying Yang, Eileen Kowler, Jacob L Orquin, Daniel Kahneman, Colin Camerer, Nina Mazar, Richard Thaler, Dan Ariely, Greg Berns, Jonathan Cohen, Paul Zak, Aldo Rustichini, Natalia Karelaia, Angelika Dimoka, Quing Ma, Tania Singer, Isabelle Brocas, Saras Sarasvathy, Sendhil Mullainathan, Linda Babcock, Matthew Rabin, John P. O'Doherty and Aldo Rustichini occupy the opening leaf of my acknowledgement roll. Their help happens to be the bedrock of this thesis.

I acknowledge from the core of my heart to Ahalya. You accurately represent the idiom 'beck and call'. A bosom friend and a confidante - friend, you were a constant companion in my present journey and hope to treasure it till the last moment of my breathing period. Thank you Tanusree of IIM Ranchi, Sayalee of D Y Patil University, Pune, Swetalina of Sri Sri University, Cuttack, Malavika of Central University, Puducherry and Banitamani of CUTM University, Bhubaneswar for lending me their expertise and intuition to my scientific and technical problems in my quest with joint explorations hand - in - hand that stemmed in some joint authorship. To my survey respondents, I thank you all for being the 'pedestal' of my research excursion.

To my parents, Dr Baikunthanath and Smt Sarabala, who withstood all hardships of life to ensure that their children gain the best of education and life, I dedicate this piece of work under their 'Lotus Feet'. To my Parents - in law, Professor Ram Shankar Rath and Smt Suprava, acknowledgement is a small word. All their blessings acted as renewable sources of 'academic energy'.

To my wife, Mrs Praveena, who ensured that the 'jyoti' from the oil lamp glows without disruption and for her inestimable cups of 'green tea', I owe her an uncalculated amount. My daughter, Mahima ('Divine Grandeur') and son, Mudit ('Eternal Happiness') certainly stood up to their name in ensuring a peaceful academic environment and ambience.

To all the anonymous referees who will undertake the pains to evaluate this thesis, I bow in reverence for their erudite scholarship and their blessings.

To academic officials of Srinivas University, Mangaluru, India, who were instrumental in sharing much assuring information when required through prompt response - mails and telephonic tête - à - têtes.

Above all, my head, heart, mind, body and soul bow down at the feet of Great Almighty. His mercy was with me throughout my life and ever more in this study. I thank Him for enlightening my soul with the respected love and compassion for other humans and allowing me to enter a field where I could practice this desire. Without whose blessings this day would have not been possible in submitting this thesis to the global academic community through the thresholds of Srinivas University, India.

DEDICATION

To my Late Wife

Praveena

Whose departing words were

**“Continue With Your Writings, Research And Studies, As They Are Your
Favourite Engagements”**

thus

**Ensuring That The ‘Jyoti’ From The Oil Lamp Glows Without Disruption and For
Her Inestimable Cups Of ‘Green Tea’**

NEURO - EXPERIMENT IN
ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING

(SYNOPSIS)

Prologue

The era of neuromanagement has arrived carrying along with it the world of neuro - entrepreneurship. Researchers in Psychology, primarily neuro - psychology, engaged in neuro - entrepreneurship choice issues need to get linked with this new scholarship as to notice multi - disciplinary and inter - disciplinary off - shoots. Research efforts carried out, that form the bedrock of this thesis, by Colonel Dr J Satpathy (hereafter, Candidate) was in area of neuromanagement with thrust on neuro - choice behaviourism in entrepreneurship and business.

In 2021, Candidate published papers (and, posters) under the titles, 'Behavioural Transmitters', 'Cerebral Guesstimates', 'Disruptive Blood Guesstimates', 'Face Recognition', 'Hematological Signatures', 'Hemato - Psychological Designs, 'Disruptive Neuro - Heretical in Heterodox Choice', 'Avant-Garde Stratagems', 'Neuro - Hematological Strategy', 'HR Curvatures', 'Hemato - Cerebral Choice', 'Hemachocivation', and 'Hematological Signatures', to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2020, published papers (and, posters) in, Neuro - Calibrations, 'Behaviour Department', 'Neuro - Milieus', 'Entrepreneurship and Technology: Future Trends', Neuro - Reflections in Work - Family Enrichment', 'Traversing Work - Life Equilibrium with Mindfulness', 'Tabula Rasa' Personnel Entrepreneur', 'Perceptive Entrepreneurial Choice Comportment', Noetic Alleyways: Choosing to Choose or Deciding to Decide, 'Behavioural Neuromanagement', 'Neuro - Couplings', 'Neuro - Cursors', 'Choice Mosaic', 'Neuroentrepreneurial Preference', 'Skin Conductance', 'Neuro - Smidgeons' (Poster), 'Ophthalmological Catalysts' (Poster), 'Neuro - Curvatures' (Poster), 'Neuro - Heterodoxies', 'Choice Topography', 'Neuro - Trajectories', 'Computational Neuro -

Trajectories' 'Neuro - Genetic Underpinnings' and 'Cognitive Reconnaissance', to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2019, published papers (and, posters) included, 'Skin Conductance in 'Smart' Entrepreneurial Judgement', 'Visual Monikers', 'Competency Plotting', 'Neuro - Evidence', 'Digitalised Neuro - Choice Making', 'Personality, Neuro - Trust and LMX' , 'Ophthalmic Signatures', 'Neuro - Diagonals', 'Neuro - Geometry', 'Oculo - Empirical Signatures', 'Neuro - Economic 'Agent', 'Neuro - Monikers', 'Oculo - Tactical Monikers', 'Neuro - Preference Connectionism', 'Neuro - Capability', 'Neurophysiological Drivers (Poster)', 'Choice Uncertainties', 'Neuro - Optometric Estimates', 'Electrodermal Traces' and 'Cardio - Peep' (Poster), to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2018, published papers (and, posters) included, 'Socio - Genetic Matrices' (Case Study), 'Human Capital: Neuro - Based Analysis', 'Neuro - Choice Undercurrents', 'Neuroreductionist Approaches', 'Entrepreneurial Skills', 'Choice Signatures' (Poster), 'Choice Monikers', 'Cognitive 'Agent', 'Hematological Insight', 'Hematological Judgement', and 'Mathematical Exposition in Choice Dynamics, to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2017, published papers (and, posters) included, 'Neuro - Organisational Choice Comportment, 'Romancing Neurodecision Making', 'Review on Neuroentrepreneurial Choice Crescendo's, 'No Food, No Water: What Choice Making', 'Neuro - Hybrid Architecture' and 'Brain - Eye Coadjuvancy', to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2016, published papers (and, posters) included, 'Cognitive Underpinning' (Poster), '*Unmapped Territory*', 'Crafting Neuro Economic - Choices', 'Neuro - Operables', 'Neuro - Contemplation' and Neuro - Geometry. A list of papers (and, posters) is appended to this thesis. Candidate published SSRN - ELSEVIER papers, between 2016 and 2021 under the titles, 'Voyage into Neuro', 'Proclaiming Neurosocioconomics', 'Introducing Neuroentrepreneurial Models, 'Postulates in Neuro - Choice Making' and 'Behavioural Transmitters, to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

Introduction

Life is full of choices and selections as human beings are ‘Thinking Agents’. Human behaviour is not the product of a single process, but rather reflects interaction of different specialized subsystems. As old as Civilization and fruition of Earth, choice making is rudimentary humanoid action. 21st Century is baptized to be ‘Century of Human Brain, Blood and Eyes’; a complex playfield in business choice perspectives. With birth of a new scientific field, experts have taxed to comprehend how we make choices by using different approaches. Important question is how individuals make choices. Researchers are interested in assumptions, beliefs, habits and tactics used to make choices. Research suggests that brain considers various sources of information before making a choice. However, how does it do this? In addition, why does the process sometimes go awry, causing impulsive, indecisive and confused choices; that lead to risky and potentially dangerous behaviours? Result is that brain sometimes argues with itself, as these distinct systems come to different conclusions about what we should do. Human behaviour is not under constant and detailed control of careful and accurate hedonic calculations. It is product of an unstable and irrational complex of reflex actions, impulses, instincts and habits.

This is a world of choices, alternatives, options, utility and optimization; VUCA (Vulnerability, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity). Appreciable reflections have been directed toward choice making process that confront an entrepreneur (case in query in this thesis). How do entrepreneurs make an optimal choice? How do entrepreneurs bargain ‘hot buttons’ and influence entrepreneurial brain, blood and eye(s) in business choices? Questions that need to be answered include; how to choose in tough situations where stakes are high and there are multiple conflicting objectives? How should entrepreneurs’ plan? How can we deal with risks and uncertainties involved in a choice? How can we create options that are better than the ones originally available? How can we become better choice makers? What resources will be invested in choice - making? What are the potential responses to a particular problem or opportunity? Who will make this choice? Every prospective action has strengths and weaknesses; how should they be evaluated? These are the questions neuroentrepreneurial researchers suspect are most crucial for understanding complex human behaviours. This affords conceptual geometry for conducting neuro (entrepreneurial) choice research through measurement of neural activity at management levels of analysis. Research investigates neural bases of choice predictability and value as central parameters in expected utility to choice making. Integration of these offers exciting

potential for construction of near - accurate models of choice - making. In such a mosaic of conditions, it becomes vivacious to fruitage powerful, astute businesses that generate enthusiastic doppelgänger of entrepreneurship.

Neuromanagement exhibits that brain behaves differently when facing nature or human actors. Few management investigators are passionate to study character of neuromanagement in entrepreneurial choice making dynamics. Neuromanagement translational research arrange for new way of computing entrepreneurial choice. 'Inferential' information and neuroscientific representations stimulate to start a fresh inquiry with tests choice observables and computational (neural) mechanisms. Motivation prompted to explore links between entrepreneurial choice making and neuroscience. It was significant to arrive at a conclusion that neuroscience and neuromanagement follow '*Biological Plausibility*' (causal connection between presumed origin and outcome that is unswerving with prevailing biotic understanding).

Research Statement

All entrepreneurs face complex circumstances of hard events to take paramount choice, weighing optimistic / unenthusiastic aspects and obliged to accept risk. Some selected inquiries adopted for inquiries are; How to account information about value, risk, ambiguity and timing? How does this criterion behave with orientation to the chosen approach? What distinguishes criteria adopted is dissimilar? Are there direct correlations that exist between approaches? How identifiable variables affect selection of choice making criteria? Is there a relationship between external variables and choice criterion used? What kinds of algorithms and computations underpin choice process?

Emerging neuroentrepreneurial science evidence suggests that sound and rational neuroentrepreneurial choice making depends on prior accurate emotional processing. Somatic marker hypothesis provides a systems-level neuroentrepreneurial anatomical and cognitive framework for neuroentrepreneurial choice making and its influence. These occur at multiple levels of operation. Some occur consciously and some non-consciously. Issues that crop up are; what happens when entrepreneurs change minds? What algorithms allow sensorimotor behaviours to be learned? What computational mechanisms allow brain to adapt changing circumstances? How (and where) are value and probability combined in brain and what is the dynamics of this? What neural systems track defined forms of utility? To what extent do utility computations generalize to choice, which are tasks that are more complex? How do systems that focus on immediate choices interact?

Research statement adopted for this inquiry is despite advances, question of how entrepreneur make business choices continues to pose challenges. Research statement encases; what is the character of entrepreneurial choice dynamics and how do they come around? How do entrepreneurial practices change over time? What agents influence (re) configuration of entrepreneurial practices? How do entrepreneurial practices transmit to entrepreneurial behaviour and abilities? How and why do practices relay implementation probability? How and why do entrepreneurs endorse choice making approaches?

Objective(s) and Scope

Principal gap observed is that there is no rock solid evidence as regards any study centring on role of blood monikers and eye movements in entrepreneurial choice making, barring a negligible few. This research is perhaps step forward research by using tools from neuro - management. This attempt does generate indications for manifold arrangements involved in entrepreneurs' choice making. Principal attempt was to cast eye on tumultuous issues engulfing world of business and primarily that of choice processing. Care has been allotted for 'disruptive mental' approximations'. This is from a principle - based outlook to report research problem based on empirical study. Principal aim is to model entrepreneurs' choice making by using tools from neuro - management. This translational thesis presents neuro-entrepreneurial science of management modelling approach. This was to create evidences for multiple systems involved in entrepreneurs' choice-making. Besides principal objective, following objectives have been taken into consideration for present translational research work; criteria (physiognomies that each alternative own) adopted for choice making, methodology of assessing cases for choice making, variables that emphasizes choice making, choice perspectives as regards (UVCA) and conduct neuro - based interpretation on entrepreneurs' choice making.

Objective of this inquiry is to identify neural processes involved in entrepreneurial choice making. It aims to transport diversity of disciplinary backgrounds to probe into how business choices are made. Attempt contributes to offer inter - disciplinary perceptions of brain and eye(s) activity at time of entrepreneurial choice making to include exploring anatomy of neuro - discourses to functions of 'neuro - biologism'.

Backbone of this thesis embodies translational research depicting link between management and entrepreneurial neuromanagement to explicate how choice makers interdisciplinary field translational research makes choice by integrating psychology, neuroscience and management science. Attempt encompasses irregularities that are gainsay

with traditional entrepreneurial hypotheses, appraise choice making by combining methods such as behavioural, neurophysiological, experimental economics and develop choice models based on neural and psychological mechanism. Through computational approaches, attempt have been to clarify how neural circuits realize ‘mental simulation’ in entrepreneurial choice-making. This plan ventures to offer a model about relationship between eye movements and blood monikers and underlying neuroentrepreneurial underpinnings involved in choice - making.

By characterizing effect of these influences, this study expects to gain insight into how eye movements and blood monikers compute choice-making. this work would attempt to explore phenomena through individual action, choice-making, and reasoning processes on concept of cognitive models of choice - making. Principal aim of proposed study has been to model neuroentrepreneurial basis of choice making by using tools from blood monikers and eye movements. Purpose has been to elucidate principles and choice - making mechanism in brain interaction between variables of blood monikers and eye movements processes. Focal point is to understand neural processes underlying how entrepreneurs craft choices and choices, understand mechanisms of choice - making and integrating interdisciplinary research towards contributing to neuroentrepreneurial choice.

Originality and Relevance

Goal of studying human choice behaviour is prediction. This research seeks to develop theoretical models, based on axiomatic foundation of eye movements and blood monikers, which can predict entrepreneurial choices. These models would take as inputs state of external world and generate as outputs actual choices made by human choosers. For this reason, research aims towards achieving compact and abstract models of choice. To date, management model of choice has not been informed by the way blood monikers and eye movements functions. Analysis of observations include not only choices between options, per se, but additional eye movements and blood monikers data, including length of time taken to make choices, number of error in choices and psychophysical model(s).

Including more than just observed choices allows data to have an additional disciplining effect on theory. This thesis extends this assumption of optimal behaviour to analysis of blood monikers and eye movements process producing a choice. To do this, thesis assumes that there is an unobservable choice that an agent makes, consequences of which are reflected in all observable data that can be measured in the choice process. That choice is strength of effort devoted to processing blood monikers and eye movements information in reaching a choice between options. As a conclusion, attempt has been to propose a model

that links predictions of traditional psychological observations and predictions of relative blood monikers and eye movements activation dependent on exogenous characteristics of choice environment. Neuroentrepreneurial management model will play a crucial role in building of new reliable theories capable of explaining and predicting individual behaviour and strategic choices. Main message is that individual is not one coherent body. Blood monikers and eye movements are a multi-system entity and therefore choice-maker must be modelled as an organisation. Systematic study of interactions between agents and choice processes lead to novel insights. Applying similar methodology to study entrepreneurial choice - making is the way to understand bounds of rationality.

Until now, research has not systematically integrated influence of sub - systems of blood monikers and eye movements in choice-making. Evidence suggests that choice - making depends on methodical methods to analyse relevant blood monikers and eye movements processes. Due to its multidisciplinary nature, this investigation is subject to several kinds of misconceptions. While there are several benefits of using neuroentrepreneurial techniques in understanding choice making, there are questions that neuroentrepreneurial science cannot answer by itself and needs help of experimental methodology and theories to understand how Entrepreneurs decide. The key limitation is identifying different regions of blood monikers and eye movements in certain situations (VUCA). These techniques are not able to provide an explanation or a reason (neuroentrepreneurial) as to why we respond in the manner that we do. What happens in blood monikers and eye movements or what is activated when entrepreneurs make choices or are in process of making choices or responding to outcomes? It does not give insight into why we make choices and why we respond in the manner that we do. This is where experimental methodology would help bolster understanding. A synergy between neuroentrepreneurial techniques and experiments provide insight into understanding Entrepreneurial choice making.

Thesis revolves around 'human beings' and entrepreneurs as principal agents who attempt to 'push' towards constancy in choice dynamics. Thesis presents 'biology - inspired entrepreneurial science' revolutions that originate from management (science of 'choice behaviour') and psychology (discipline of 'thought') with reference to blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s). Attempt has been made to reveal as to how rational events are concomitant to neurophysiological chronicles. There are efforts to reveal blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s) interrelations to appreciate how and why entrepreneurs make choices. Orientations have been made to compendium of subjects that

challenge research. Entrepreneurial issues have been underlined that rear few central issues and offer solution through 'rationalism' scrutiny. Inspiration for undertaking this investigation has been accessible with *potential to propose central change in how entrepreneurs think, perceive and model choice*. Role of neuromanagement, blood monikers and eye movements and eye (s), opinions and sentiments, neurons, psychology, behavioural controlling, cognitive and sentimental neuroscience, entrepreneurial sciences, that possibly deliver answer to issues in entrepreneurial choice dynamics has been anticipated with orientation to '*Biological ('mental effort') Plausibility*'. *Entrepreneurial neuro - linkages have been initiated that develop around hematological, blood monikers and eye movements imaging and ocular (eye movements) considerations. Some empirical processes have been recommended that address core problem in conceptual choice exploration and advance fresh questions? Challenging observations, including some unexplained difficulties and objectives of proposed inquiry have been acknowledged.*

Thesis rationales to present inter - disciplinary review of some neuro - based theories and methods used in entrepreneurial choice making. Challenge is to promote knowledge that apply outside lab and address complex challenges. Thesis relates assimilated entrepreneurial -psychological viewpoint. To conduct a comprehensive review of literature pertaining to a dynamic and interdisciplinary subject of scholarship viz. neuro-preference architecture, review defied its scope with published journal thesis and books plus research literatures linked to bases, philosophies, methods and principles of neuro-preference architecture. Some key words punched for purpose of reviews was neuro - preference, neuro - architecture, types, methods, classification of neuro-preference-architecture, neuro - preference reinforcement, neuro - facilitation, neuro-preference reduction, neuro - preference deficiencies, neuro-preference optimization, neuro-preference assessment and neuro - preference evaluation. Secondary sources were primarily from published literatures and web search engines, along with personal communication via. Mail with resource persons. Thesis describes rudimentary strengths and weaknesses of each neuro - behavioural characteristic with key references. Reviews include theories, investigational facts, figures, statistics, deductions, axioms, corollaries, inferences, conjectures and results of earlier studies well established in chosen area of inquiry; blood monikers, blood monikers and eye movements and eye(s). Focal point revolves around; neural routes underlying how entrepreneurs design preferences, understand methodologies of preference

architecture by using imaging methodologies and integrating transdisciplinary research to preference management.

Research Methodology

Aim of this thesis is to comprehend subjects' relevance judgment based on blood monikers eye tracking method. Fundamental inquiry has two components; First, how subjects' blood monikers and eye tracking 'inferential' data are concomitant with fortitude of bearing of portions of content displayed. Next, connections crop up between blood monikers and eye tracking 'inferential' data with cognitive loads ('mental effort') during exploration tasks? Besides analysing questionnaire responses, principal methodologies adopted for this inquiry are Hematological tests and Eye Movement tests.

Thesis presents gist of experiments, results obtained, inferences drawn and general discussion on 'Cause' and 'Effect' relationship in gamut of entrepreneurial choice making. Thesis emphasizes principally on abstract concerns involved in selecting inquiry method and estimating results by means of diverse practices. Principal aim was to conduct experiments by likening its message / outcome implications with experimental observations, explore causes, establish empirical regularities as basis for new theory, comparing environments by protuberance of neural activity. Research methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary review approach.

Thesis attempts to employ multi - method approach and triangulation. In light of discussing theories and applications of neuroentrepreneurial science in choice making, sophisticated techniques have emerged to understand neural activity and how brains respond to stimuli in brain. Blood monikers and eye movements could precisely localize areas activated when subjects perform various human processes with concentration on formulating research question, designing protocol, analyzing data and interpreting / reporting results. The proposed methodology helped develop theoretical foundations, models and algorithms to support near-optimal choice making in highly complex, dynamic systems, operating in uncertain, resource-constrained situation.

As regards population and sample size, it is estimated that a population of 150 respondents was deemed a fair population and subjecting respondents to clinical test led to fair results. As regards research design, research was based on questionnaires and

interviews with a view to soliciting primary data. Secondary data was extracted from available secondary sources. The usual statistical tools line SPSS, ANOVA, MANOVA and Data Analysis software was considered as deemed fit. As regards clinical primary data, study undertook lab - based neuro - experiments via. Blood monikers and eye movements. For purpose of blood monikers identification, complete blood count analyser equipment was applied. For purpose of eye movements, Tobii eye tracker was applied. Results obtained from statistical tools were compared and contrasted with clinical tools for real - time picture of how an entrepreneur arrives at a choice threshold.

Research Methodology and Results

To provide central basis for understanding entrepreneurial choice making and rational centric choice poise, research analyzed blood samples of willing and volunteer respondents. It is perceived that almost all 'Hematological Monikers' in respondents reflect disquieting trends. Based on clinical tests, it is inferred that; rational centric choice making potential is bad when;

- Blood glucose fasting indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Blood glucose post - prandial indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Blood glucose random indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Urea indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Creatine indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Sodium indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Potassium indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- S bilirubin direct indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- S bilirubin indirect indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Aspartate trans amines AST indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Alanine trans amines alt indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Lipid T - cholesterol indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Lipid tri - glyceride indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Low-density lipo protein indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Very low-density lipo protein indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- High density lipo protein indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- S bilirubin total indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Creatine Phosphate K indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- CPK - muscular / brain indices are seeming as 'atypical'.

- GGT indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- T - Protein indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Albumin indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Globulin indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- A: G ratio indices are seeming as 'atypical'.

Results exhibit signals for spontaneous counterfactual simulation in domain of high - level cognitive. Major finding is that entrepreneur endeavours to address choices using hematological arrangements 'neuro - drivers'. Research discusses inferences and prospective ways to guide hematological neuroscience in choice curve. Research offers 'First - Rate Anchorage' of hematological arrangements 'neuro - drivers' and 'entrepreneur centric choice corridor arrangements' to appreciate how entrepreneurs make choices. Allowing for other methodologies to nature of insolent choice contours, this attempt is considered as psycho - behavioural, in that it routines wide assortment of conceptions used in behavioural scholarships, in which anthropological behaviour is reconnoitred from capacious ways.

Principal findings in this research are; entrepreneurs tend to act rationally and in their own finest interests when deciding, management researchers need to study neuromanagement in realm of entrepreneurial choice dynamics, neuromanagement provides ways of measuring entrepreneurial well-being, neuromanagement aid as a catalyst for entrepreneurial choice dynamics model development, neuromanagement offers way to test entrepreneurial centric choice models, neuromanagement improve capability to predict entrepreneurial choice dynamics behaviour, hematological provisions instrumental evidence in entrepreneurial choice, hematological 'tracking' is appreciated in technopreneur choice process, hematological arrangements scrutinize choice - task approaches and cognitive capability, strong variations in hematological arrangements comportment represent choice certainty, observing hematological variables helps identify transitory situations of ambiguity and hematological arrangements serve as calculation technique beyond customary scrutiny.

Based on the analysis above it is observed that; gender of a person has statistically significant impact on Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid t - Cholesterol, 'Age' level groups have no statistical significance on any one of these

characteristics, 'stress' has statistical significance on potassium, interaction effect of gender and stress is not statistically significant, interaction effect of age and gender is statistically significant, interaction effect of age and stress has no statistical significant, effect of 'gender' and interaction effect of 'age and gender' has influence on blood glucose random.

Results lend credence to aim of experiments undertaken in that, eye tracking methodology does help in investigating and corroborating dynamics of entrepreneurial choice making. Results exhibit substantial connection between 'subjective', 'physiological' and 'fixations' from real-world point of view. When entrepreneurs make choices, there's heavy disparity in comportment. 'Vacillating' entrepreneurs employ additional evidence when attempting a choice compared to 'definite' entrepreneurs. There were differences in the manner entrepreneurs scanned available information. While 'definite' entrepreneurs spot on choice based on particular trait, 'vacillating' entrepreneurs take in all of the 'material'. 'Definite' entrepreneurs perhaps opine that all options have 'good' and 'bad' characteristics. But they prefer a feature that is presumably important. 'Vacillating' entrepreneurs observed and opined that all 'material's had some quota of 'good' and 'bad' points. Secondly, 'vacillating' individuals distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during their course of experimental observation. The 'definite' participants 'focused' on fewer attributes in order to make their choice. Interestingly, 'vacillating' entrepreneurs spent more time overall looking at nothing. The subjects looked at 'blank cells' in 'grid' while (apparently) attempting to make a choice. This series of experiments theorises that undertaking entrepreneurs to 'cogitate' or 'reframe' selections before arriving at 'a choice'.

Prefrontal neurons display saccade - oriented action. Appreciating how entrepreneurial brain works is significant in footings of meaningful impact on cognitive functions. Pre-saccadic activity encrypts guidelines of eye movements. Brain filters out unwanted information when entrepreneurs shift vision from one target to another focal target. Complexity of (entrepreneurial) 'intended' choice problems increases with options and features of each available option. Neuro - 'intended' choice from eye tracking processes (images and responses) to complex results, makes assumptions about how (entrepreneurs) make intended choices, defines link between (entrepreneurial) choices and (entrepreneurial) preferences. This postulates that entrepreneurs have full understanding of 'intended' choice problem and adopt optimising behaviour to create 'intended' choices. Neuro - ocular action, towards entrepreneurial - oriented behaviour, capable of explaining entrepreneurial choice

making, on cognitive models of choice, recommends; escape from clichés and arrangements, challenge conventions, generate options and alternatives, strategize new designs and observe what happens and find new access opinions from which to change forward.

Eye tracking measures provide non - invasive indices of brain dynamics. Apparently, gaze examination divulges attentional and cognitive approaches. Ocular measures deliver perceptions concerning cognitive expanses. Thesis advocates auxiliary inquiries to scan physiognomies of saccade - related dynamics in prefrontal cortex and conceivable influences to eye movement mechanism and related - prefrontal functions. Eye tracking offers novel peep into choice management. It is observed that observations was correct (85%) of the time, there was effect of presence of target item and memory set size on response accuracy, real time ‘inferential’ data follow same pattern of effects for both factors: target presence and substantial interaction, slope was significantly influenced by target presence behavioural results, fixations could be interpreted in different ways depending on context and objective of the study, during processing of neuro - ocular scene, individuals moved eyes to relevant features in that scene, ‘inferential’ data from each subject was analysed independently and observed that error rates was quite low, ‘entrepreneurial choice making is unswervingly inter - oriented to instantaneous accessibility, experiments reveal neurons display saccade - oriented activity, saccade - oriented activity show steering discernment and setting dependence, substantial connection between ‘subjective’, ‘physiological’ and ‘fixations’ from real-world point of view, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs employ additional evidence when attempting a choice, ‘definite’ entrepreneurs spot on to a choice based on a particular trait, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs take in all of the ‘material’, ‘definite’ entrepreneurs, perhaps, opine that all options have ‘good’ and ‘bad’ characteristics. ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs observe and opine that all ‘material’s had some quota of ‘good’ and ‘bad’ points, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during experimental observation, ‘definite’ participants ‘focused’ on fewer attributes in order to make their choice, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs spent more time overall looking at nothing, complexity of ‘intended’ choice problems increases with options and features of each available option, entrepreneurs have full understanding of ‘intended’ choice problem and adopt optimizing behaviour to create ‘intended’ choices.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study of entrepreneurial choice making and problem solving has attracted attention. Expanded research requires (model - based empirical) study of behavior and provide setting for basic research on how ill-structured problems are, and can be, solved. Entrepreneurial neuro - choice making, which is much less well understood than individual choice - making and problem solving, can be studied with great profit using already established methods of inquiry, especially through intensive studies.

Neuroentrepreneurial management offers solution through series of measurements of blood monikers and eye movements activity at the time of choices. It provides conceptual and philosophical framework for understanding and conducting research at intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science, management and psychology. *Neuroentrepreneurial management theory* proposes to build blood monikers and eye movements - based models capable of predicting observed behaviour. Neuroentrepreneurial management sheds light on causes of behaviour (and neuroentrepreneurial anomalies) and help build theories capable of explaining and predicting choices. Measurement of blood monikers and eye movements activity provides information about underlying mechanisms blood monikers and eye movements during choice processes. Neuro - entrepreneurial choice modelling would help when new information is inconsistent with goals. Combining above disciplines stretches inter - disciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - entrepreneurial choice making that has eluded researchers.

Entrepreneurial neuro - management offers insights into nature of planned rationality. Entrepreneurial neuro - management provisions data in totting to those accessible from conjectural, experimental and investigational research on human comportment. Entrepreneurial neuro - management offers blood monikers and eye movements, eyes and blood dynamics - based solution to choice making. Outcome of study is beneficial to various stakeholders directly or indirectly associate with entrepreneurial choice actions. Study provides conceptual architectural framework for appreciation intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science and entrepreneurial choice. Study sheds light on reasons of entrepreneurial behaviour (and incongruities) that help build theories capable of amplification and forecasting business choice. This has been the principal bed - rock of theoretical practicalities in this thesis. Dynamics of blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s) activity affords information about underlying mechanisms blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s) during business choice processes. Combining above disciplines gives interdisciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - entrepreneurial choice making that has eluded translational researchers. This has been a primary pedestal of

experimental realities in this thesis. Research findings are important as foundation for future translational research and academic plus business civilization at a large would get benefit from this study. Being a maiden study, present attempt contributes (at intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science, management and psychology) towards existing scholarship in the following mode;

- Provide conceptual framework for conducting neuroentrepreneurial management research,
- Offer solution through neuro - based measurements at time of choice making, and
- Describe standard inter - disciplinary prototypes for choice making.

**NEURO - EXPERIMENT
IN
ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING**

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CHAPTER - I

INTRODUCTION

Introduction

1.1 Human beings are 'Thinking Agents'. Choice making is as old as Civilization and fruition of earth. Choice making is a rudimentary human action. Choices craft human lives. 21st Century is baptised to be 'Century of Human Brain and Blood. With birth of a new scientific field, social experts and natural technologists have taxed to comprehend how we make choices. Best aspect is that they have proceeded by using completely different approaches to certain, extent. Civilisation is cruising through a tempest with a roller - coaster curve path. Business world, being a part of civilisation is facing challenging time from all angles. Last three to four decades have witnessed wide ranging explorations that lend credence to dynamics and mechanisms that kindle choice (Hirst, Knippenberg and Zhou; 2009), influence emotions (Amabile, Barsade, Mueller, Staw; 2005 and Fong; 2006) motivation (Grant and Berry; 2011 and Shalley; 1991), entrepreneurship (Mainemelis, Kark, and Epitropaki; 2015), inter - organisational grids (Ahuja; 2000) and institutional forces (Hargadon and Douglas; 2001. Shalley, Zhou, and Oldham; 2004, Tadmor, Galinsky and Maddux; 2012).

1.2 The classic dissertation, titled 'Wealth of Nations' (Smith; 1776), styled a number of singularities (psychological insights) for appreciative choice behaviour and accumulation of choices. Anthropologically, backed by heredity, genetics, molecular biology and cellular biology, mankind has always been a prizefighter and combatant with vagaries of nature; efficacious at times and bungled many times. Business entrepreneurial sensitivities have arisen in human mind with regiment of inevitabilities. All these experiences made human beings, as an entrepreneur, endowed with trait of being an administrator, contractor, executive, entrepreneur, producer, backer, founder and undertaker. Of focal reference is concept of being a 'speculator' by architectural creation of conjectures or models without any firm or stable signal. This all led choice maker to be 'Adaptive and Affective Adaptive and

Affective Agent' / design parameters of Darwin's Survival of the Fittest. This maxim or Argument Theory postulates that transgenerational sustenance has consummately housed itself, not doughtiest or ablest, in swipec of things to situation most efficacious in enduring and replicating.

1.3 Darwinism model in business management is a discernment (struggle for actuality used to validate several business) plagiaristic from Darwinian philosophy of biological progression (Satpathy and Gankar; 2020). Does 'Survival of Fittest' apply to human beings? Does 'survival of the fittest' apply to business dynamics? Does it mean that best 'fitted,' or best 'adapted,' to its environment is most likely to exist, and likely to embroidery. It means that establishments or makes not well 'fitted' to their colonnades will not endure or withstand in innumerable contradictory circumstances, at least in in the long - term. Hypothetically, do any of these 'tinned' conjectural explanations categorically work? Why do entrepreneurs some succeed, while others succumb? Why do some make squandering proceeds, while others face predicament on unembellished nourishment? In perspective of these, it is sensed that is there domineering call for giving a retouch to current theoretic archetypes? In this scenario, is there an unavoidable prerequisite towards a prismatic surgery of business management 'poetry' by garnishing an interdisciplinary flavour to explain choice identification better (Satpathy and Gankar; 2020)?

1.4 Translational research has acknowledged edifices and progressions that nurture novelty (Hülshager, et al.; 2009. Miron-Spektor, Erez, and Naveh; 2011, Somech and Drach-Zahavy; 2013 and West; 1996). Nevertheless, more choice architects acquire, more probes appear, that require entrepreneurs to fabricate and develop multi - structured vibrant prototypes that proposition fine-grained appreciation of mechanisms and wider insinuations for management (Amabile and Pratt; 2016). As world of business acquires form of multifaceted, wide - encompassing and vigorous, ingenuity and novelty become significant for business performance and long - term effectiveness (Amabile; 1996 and Padgett; 2012). Advance of business dynamics occurs in a state of problematic settings. In such a matrix, it becomes vital to harvest powerful, judicious businesses that generate optimistic doppelgänger of entrepreneurship. These are multi - level embryonic individualities that oblige nimble - fingered entrepreneurship, reassuring business

circumstances and expedient operational siting (Anderson, Potonik and Zhou; 2014, Cattani and Ferriani; 2008, Gupta, Tesluk and Taylor; 2007 and Sgourev; 2013).

1.5 Humans take to choices by conforming to Laws of Rationality in spite of journeying with ‘Strange Attractors’ in an environment of unstable aperiodic behaviour leading to emergence of varying (choice) phenomena. Paradoxes are valuable in management because they hint at inaccuracies or discrepancies in models of the management. Reality of initiating a process for choice is one major problems in Economics and Commerce or purely ‘Business’. Contemporary scholarship exhibits that in order to act inexhaustibly in multifaceted business surroundings, entrepreneur needs to look forward and appreciate varying changes in vivacious working of brain, eyes and blood. It studies how management behaviour shapes appreciation of brain, eyes, blood and guide coherent geometry towards choice (Satpathy and Gankar; 2016). In earlier attempts during last decades, extensive ranging advances have been made in sophistication towards accepting undercurrents of choice making from a (neuro) scientific point of view. This is a ‘continuum of indentures’. It is a composite platform with contributions coming in from Management (Science of ‘Choice Behaviour’) and Psychology (concept of ‘Thought’). In a way, this scholarship is experiencing a spate of bio (management) - revolution.

1.6 It is perceived that some (cognitive) bias does seep in when entrepreneur is involved in choice ‘plays process’. This is because some element of bias, gut feeling, tastes, preferences and belief / faith coupled up with intuition (reference is drawn to the concept of ‘Quasirationality’; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception) does make way into choice processes. Whether moral based or value based, choice making is prone to agents and elements of initiating a ‘swing’ from path of real - time choice making. After all, entrepreneur are susceptible to various forces; seen and unseen, reflex actions, impulses, instincts and habits. It is here that brain, blood and eye have a role to play in gathering real time information and aiding real – time choice making.

Neuro - Management

1.7 For a pure Economist, prime goal of analysing humanoid choice centers on the world of prediction in a classical pair of spectacle. Based on strong axiomatic pedestals, arguments profess ‘should’ or ‘could’ directives. This is primarily based on a strict regimen of algorithms. Result is a package normative theories that formal

experimental developmental interactive propositions. Psychologists, on a congruent wave length, study mechanisms of judgement to appreciate psychological constructs that escort choice making. These processes predict behaviour and capture 'mental events' that go before choice. Neuromanagement appreciates neural structural design alleyways and calculations to arrive at choice making comportment.

1.8 Is there an exceptional function for neuromanagement or neuro economics? And, if so, what are its suitable exploratory philosophies? Choice necessities entrepreneur who is accountable for making choices. Convolution in business management world, lengthways with statistics magnitude, vagueness and risk, make it essential to deliver a rational choice architectural framework based on anthropological reasoning and choice making abilities. From a psychosomatic standpoint, it is essential to scrutinise discrete choices in architectural framework of a set of desires, predilections individual obligates and standards entrepreneur seek. From a perceptive view, choice process must be observed as continuous process integrated in interface with milieu. From normative perspective, analysis does address significant choices that comprises procedures, methods and tools for identifying, clearly representing and formally assessing important aspects of a choice condition.

1.9 Neuro entrepreneurial management challenges customary management postulates that choice making is a unitary process. It suggests that it is driven by interaction between automatic and controlled processes. Field in which consilience operates, expansion of neuro - entrepreneurial management parallels development of cognitive Science bridging contrasting fields of management and psychology into a unified discipline. This is towards providing single, general theory of behaviour to appreciate processes that connect perception and action by revealing neuro - entrepreneurial choice mechanisms. Despite substantial advances, question of how entrepreneur designs and crafts judgements and choices has engaged translational researchers for times.

1.10 This thesis attempts to outsmarts basic safekeeping that neuroscience, neuro economics and neuromanagement cannot sway business modeling. This is professed even in norm (or code) and concentration is on two disapprovals of assimilating 'Behavioural Sufficiency' (causal circuit explanations of behaviour) and 'Emergent Phenomenon' (touch matching physiognomies of necessity and independence)

guides. Each experience perceived by brain, blood and eye(s) are exceptional. Synchronised shifts of neuronal activity in brain, blood is associated with plan adaptations in behavioural tasks. Brain, blood and eye(s) require and mandate liveness to constantly adapt. This is achieved by each event being perceived on how cerebral procedures relate to neurophysiological proceedings.

1.11 Entrepreneurial prototypes are fundamentally simultaneous with methodological originality. Voyaging through ‘bustamination’ (‘business’ and ‘contamination’), entrepreneurial community is diagonally at cater - cornered with neuroscience, neuro economics, neuromanagement and entrepreneurship thereby covertly and overtly transmitting a perceptive organised linkage (‘Chess Board Matrix’) perceived as ‘nonconforming approximation’ with business replicas’ and ‘disruptors’. This is a chaotic ‘noise’ for disruptive strategy that call for entrepreneurial choices. Field brings emotional and sophisticated computational (neural mechanisms) knowledge (Kijpokin; 2016) from micromanagement, appreciation of emotional influences on behaviour (from psychology) and functional neural imaging (from neuroscience). Some issues are; how can entrepreneurs make an optimal choice? How can entrepreneurs bargain ‘hot buttons’ in entrepreneurial brain, blood and eye(s) that provide conceptual geometry for conducting neuro - entrepreneurial translational research Science. There is an imperious need to espouse kaleidoscopic and sprouting unceasingly embracing neural mechanisms fundamental to state of ‘Homo - Neuropsychoeconomicus by replicating how entrepreneurs are influenced by psychological, molecular, genetic and (neuro) cognitive conformations (involved in representation and selection of choice opportunities).

1.12 Entrepreneurial perception embraces reminiscence, partialities, reactions, mental representations, opportunities, expectation, erudition, ‘inferential’ data processing, appreciation, repetition, assessment and appreciation of events. Behaviourism is a mirror that reflects penchants, philosophies, and other psychological states. Of interest is how ‘entrepreneurial’ brain captivates to inform and improve ‘entrepreneurial’ choice mechanism in a state of complexity and uncertainty or imperfect knowledge (Satpathy and Gankar: 2020). With advent of crossbreed prototypes, questions that merit consideration are; Do entrepreneurs actually, grounded on facts, figures, data, information and statistics have a choice? How do they skim off on an action in a state of unbounded ‘scrolling’ and perpetual ‘disorders’? What ‘neuro pointers’ and ‘monikers’ relate to amenable conclusions? Will neuro entrepreneurial dynamics usurp orthodox cognitive arrangements

associating neuro - integrated course to reconnaissance neuro - milieus in entrepreneurial choices?

1.13 Entrepreneurial activities via brain, blood and eye(s) are powerful 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agent's / design parameters of information'. These help entrepreneurs to critically think, analyse, manage, ponder upon manage and make critical choice. In such a situation, applied neuroscience and neuromanagement helps entrepreneurs to make choice and take actions based on rules of brain, blood and eye(s) interactional dynamics. As a trade-off between accurateness and explicate ability, experiments based on methods and approaches from Eye Tracking, Blood Monikers and Sweat Conductance psycho - diagnostic data have been offered (Satpathy and Gankar: 2020). Attempt encompasses porches of biological basis of preferences traveling significant role of 'neurionics' in crafting entrepreneurial neuro - based preference flight path. This attempts at addressing how neuro apparatuses explore entrepreneurial preference making. (These are experimented in the Chapter -IV on experimentation).

Motivation

1.14 Brain is a bioelectric organ. Management and neural Sciences share a common interest. Interaction between business and Science is not that smooth with difference in expectations on either side. Attention theaters pervasive part in perception and reasoning. Choice making, with cognition and assumptions that underpin, is critical for any entrepreneur when crafting and executing strategies. Causality plays central role in choice Sciences. What typifies notion of causation in Sciences of mind and brain? Are dissimilar notions a prerequisite for different experimental approaches? Are there variances in notions that are explicitly and implicitly presumed? What counts as causal evidence in entrepreneurial choice Sciences? What role is played by information and physical mechanisms in identifying causal claims of entrepreneurial Sciences of mind and brain? Molecular and genetic markers precisely forecast rational physiognomies for cognitive and neural mechanisms of individual choice making. An emerging new paradigm, through brain's wiring diagram, thesis highlights potential cause - consequence linkage between biology (neurobiology of choice making) and management in explaining how entrepreneurs deal in choice dynamics.

1.15 Primary motivation to adopt this piece of translational research was an article titled 'Is the Era of the Neuromanagement upon Us' authored by James Heskett in Harvard Business Study dated Nov 6, 2014. Allied proposition was a paper titled "Neuroeconomics: Why Economics Needs Brains," by Colin Camerer, George Loewenstein and Drazen Prelec (2004). Coupled up was another paper titled; Are we entering an Era of Neuroscience (study of biological micro - foundations of choice perception and compartment)? Another inspiring and influencing work was 'Bringing Neuromanagement to the Business World by Patricia Polischuk. In these path breaking studies, authors state that Behavioural Scientists profess that they have a great deal to contribute to choice theory and management. Their writings, debates, arguments and discussions are appropriate to entrepreneurial dynamics.

1.16 To complement the encouraging voyage was a translational research paper titled, 'The Cognitive Neuroscience of Human Choice Making; A Review and Conceptual Architectural framework' by Lesley K. Fellows. Author has addressed that progression of selecting between options, is a central human behaviour studied expansively by disciplines vacillating from cognitive psychology to management. More inspiring works were pragmatic in writings of Peter Drucker, Daniel Kahneman, Tversky, Antonio Rangel, Antonio Bechara, Antonio Damasio, Agnieszka Tymula, Eileen Kowler, Fang Ying Yang, Guy Hochman, Jacob Orquin and others. The above standpoints perspectives and perceptions generate and trigger a consideration two dovetailed concerns. One, there subsists an exceptional spot for neuromanagement. And, two, if response is in affirmative, then what are its fitting crucial viewpoints? This proposition perfects choice theory's metaphysical titles based on pedestal of rational choice and extravagances normative matters based on epistemology and ethics. This debate particularly encourages and motivates to get motivation from a question; what *is* neuromanagement and how is entrepreneurial choice connected to its principles and philosophies? Central motivation is to appreciate nature of this hybrid scholarship. Considering the above, based on neural underpinnings, following questions can be raised: Is theoretical charter lacking in entrepreneurial neuroscience? Moreover, if not, to what magnitude does it have a theory? In what ways does theory or conceptual architectural framework compare to established Sciences? What consequences might these differences have for philosophy of neuroscience? Bottom contour issue is: Can

there be a philosophy of neuroscience without a broad or successful theory? All these prompted to explore links between entrepreneurial choice and neuroscience.

1.17 Perceptions into choice mechanisms help appreciate what is essentially on. Standard theoretical arguments posit that human beings are adept of making rational choices. Observing some entrepreneurial wrinkles, which needs to be ironed out, one assumption, is whether entrepreneurial world is entering into a phase where rationality adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agent / design parameters is waning off. At its basic, entrepreneurial choice making encompasses three steps; obtain information regarding possible actions, appraise those actions and choose between them. What is then role and connection of neuromanagement? What do brain, blood and eye(s) tell about management? How is the big picture for neuromanagement going forward?

Neuro - Continuum

1.18 Entrepreneurial organisations are at intersection with neuroscience and business spreading a linking that seemed an uncharacteristic guesstimate. Business atmosphere is witnessing ever - increasing quantum of multilevel research that assimilates demarcated inquiries and propositions with new lenses for understanding entrepreneurial practice. A recurrent singularity is plagued with 'non - orthodox entrepreneurial replicas' and 'disruptors'. There is a 'heterodoxian noise' for disruptive strategy to make choice making a reality via unconventional strategy. Comprehensive shifts have led to 'Homo - Psychoeconomicus' that replaces 'Homo Economicus' by reflecting how entrepreneurs are influenced by psychological factors, biological factors and situational factors.

1.19 Hybrid intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations are emerging as alternative to model complex systems under improbability. Do entrepreneurs have all information they need? Are entrepreneurs still using accurate models? Is there new analysis or heterodoxian insight that could make entrepreneurs more effective? And, crucially, do entrepreneurs choose what action to take? What heterodoxian physiognomies of substitutions would aid make entrepreneurial intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations'? How to help entrepreneurs develop judgement and intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations' skills? Do entrepreneurs really have a choice? How would solutions be integrated into approximations'? What

'heterodoxian variables', figured by brain, blood and eyes relate to receptive outcomes? Will heterodoxian neuromanagement replace conventional management? This thesis intends to experiment this set of issues.

1.20 Behavioural management has shown that entrepreneurs do not always work in ways that theories envisage. Entrepreneurs, as humans, are subject to thoughts, attention, logic, *mirror image* and speculation. All these subscribe to a series of emotions? *What are the questions and methods of neuromanagement? In such milieu, how are brain, blood and eye(s) systems responsible for choice making process?* Is it precise to think of brain, blood and eye(s) as calculating devices? Do entrepreneurs profess and thereby acknowledge as to what should neuromanagement inherit from scholarship of computationalism (neural mechanisms)? *How to craft experiments to study entrepreneurial choice making in choice - demanding situations?* In specific, how does biology, neuroscience and neuro management provision and oblige entrepreneurial choice. All above trends towards an inference that neuromanagement is a perfect podium to exhibit that neuroscience can provide answer. It is significant to arrive at '*Biological Plausibility*' (contributory linking between acknowledged derivation and conclusion that is unwavering with prevalent biotic appreciation).

1.21 Principally concerned with progressions by which entrepreneurs make a particular choice, there are four major motivations for shadowing this work of translational research: -

- First, few management investigators are passionate to study character of neuromanagement in entrepreneurial choice making dynamics. Herein exists an opportunity to undertake an examination.
- Second, neuromanagement translational research arrange for new way of computing entrepreneurial choice. This provides stimulus to undertake an inquiry.
- Third, 'inferential' information and neuroscientific representations stimulate to start a fresh inquiry into the subject, and
- Fourth, neuromanagement tests choice observables and computational (neural) mechanisms.

Problem Statement

1.22 Globalisation, glocalisation, localization and cross - border activities are fabric of business dynamics. Entrepreneurs are recurrently overstretched to reason for tests and occasions that exist in a frontier - less competitive environment. Entrepreneurs need to accept that change is often unpredictable, change is constant and they have to cruise in a state of VUCA. In a world of hyperactive - competition 'Survival of Fittest is the New Order'. Entrepreneurs get impacted focusing on elements of competition and gaining results. Making neuro - based choices, grounded on traditional or conventional paradigm considerations, becomes an unsafe underpinning. Variables that impact prior quarters may be external (conditions assumed 'constant') and internal (adaptive and affective adaptive). Entrepreneurs should be aware of external vicissitudes. Goal is to demonstrate how disparate views developed as appreciation of choice philosophy.

1.23 One major leading issue is that in spite of impressive progression, how entrepreneurs still sway to vagaries of forces affecting choice processes. It is substantiated beforehand that entrepreneur is well aware of the norms, standards and medians to be considered while processing a choice. Entrepreneur is well equipped to choose among alternatives, apply axioms knowing fully that which of applications would meet success - oriented factors and which ones would stand to be rejected. Also, entrepreneur knows efficacy of each application as well as philosophical undercurrents of each choice. Entrepreneur does strive to reduce uncertainty, probability and optimise towards 'absolute certainty' Entrepreneurs' do have and are ware of an algorithm to follow as to bring about a fixed result.

1.24 Over periods, translational researchers have been examining, investigating, exploring and analysing philosophy and psychology of choice making arrangements, counterintuitive presumptions, rational discernments and practical countersignatures regarding means by which one chooses. Entrepreneurial studies are based on discernment of dynamically changing and (r)evolving external world of core bodily milieu, which conduits cues that guide choice. Inquiries about what matters in factual sense, why and what occurs are symptomatically rational, cogent and coherent. Responses are informed by how one forms or devises a plan or idea in mind. Regurgitating the *issue* and classifying mandated information is key in such a situation. Behaviour comprises of choice made from microscopic to infinitesimal.

Repeatedly, entrepreneur cannot be persuaded of value to be ensued from choice. Choice made under predilections value 'deep' uncertainty (or, imperfect knowledge) form basis of architectural framework of choice making.

1.25 How to deal with this complex plus unstable atmosphere and make effective entrepreneurial choice is of prime concentration. Complexity and abundance of information lead to 'information noise' and 'cognitive overload' ('mental effort'). Having many assortments to pick from can, inappropriately, make it uncontainable to select. Translational research is looking into neurological ancestries of this stimulus, identified as 'choice overload' ('mental effort'). These provide map of 'path' less followed or 'unchartered routes /alleyways' signified by complex, embryonic behaviour and multiple evolutionary equipoise. This holds potential when making sense of 'chaotic' entrepreneurial choice world.

1.26 Complexity is a manner of deciphering as regards tactic of calculating choice perspectives with intricacies. How entrepreneurial model can be enhanced by integrating insights from evolutionary theory and complex systems theory? Insights from evolutionary and complexity perspective takes integrated interdisciplinary approach to entrepreneurial phenomena. As entrepreneurs move toward convoluted business environment, they must be able to interrelate efficaciously, anticipate ingeniously and adapt in choice of vacillations and oscillations besides alterations. How do parts of brain, blood and eye(s) direct business choice making, synchronise, face inconspicuousness and engross in premeditated clarification have encouraged studies of internal order of mind.

1.27 'Management Science and translational research are based on supposition that sound links between dissimilar parties in a choice do exist and can be found by diligent search and translational research. Precedent says that sound links can be established by means of reason. It goes on to say that reason is something that all share and that when men come to appreciate clearly, they inevitably will decide in the same ways' (Churchman; 1962). Appreciation complexities, concomitant with generation of brain, blood and eye(s) function, is difficult. We are at beginning of a 'get - up - and - go' situation that promises. Entrepreneurial choice making, based on multifaceted interlinked imaging technologies, requires degrees and varying magnitudes of cognitive, psychological, physiological or mental simulation. There is

a defined and prescribed variance between ‘reflecting about thinking’ and ‘augmenting brain, blood and eye(s) (mental) processes’ by emergent embryonic potential of choice making in a perception based action cycle (Neisser;1967).

1.28 Investigational concerns that aid in exploring the above issues are: -

- How does entrepreneur decide in state of Vulnerability, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity (VUCA)?
- What neuro - biological monikers aid entrepreneur in deciding?

Objective(s) of Study

1.29 Principal attempt being launched is to cast an eye on the tumultuous issues engulfing world of business and primarily that of choice processing. Care is being allotted for ‘disruptive mental’ approximations’. This is from principle - based outlook to report research problem based on an empirical study. Principal aim is to model entrepreneurs’ choice making by using tools from neuro - management. This is to create evidences for multiple systems involved in entrepreneurial choice making. Besides principal objective, following objectives are taken into consideration for present research work;

- Choice perspectives as regards (UVCA), and
- Undertake a neuro - based experiments on entrepreneurs’ choice making.

Scope of Study

1.30 Backbone of this thesis embodies translational research depicting link between management and neuromanagement to explicate how entrepreneurs make choice by integrating management Science, economics, neuroscience and psychology. Attempt encompasses traditional entrepreneurial hypotheses, appraise choice making by combining methods and develop choice models based on neural and psychological mechanism. Scope underlines previous and present translational research regarding each perception as it relates to scope of this thesis. Thesis addresses perceptions, theories and

models from cognitive Science, psychology and biology standpoint. The scope of study ranges from entrepreneurs in Bhubaneswar (India).

Hypotheses

1.31 The hypotheses, proposed to be adopted and tested are;

- Neuro monikers / agents and signatures influence entrepreneurs' choice,
- Choices are made based on measurable results, and
- Blood and eyes have distinct roles in entrepreneurs' choice mechanism.

Research Methodology

1.32 Meandering along among finite or infinite alternatives, research was conducted with use of theoretical and experimental approaches. This is according to procedures consisting of selecting the research question, searching literature in databases, gathering and selecting relevant literature, choice making processes and experiments neurophysiological techniques like eye tracking blood and moniker analysis as effective tools for experimental research. Based on an inter - connected and hybrid pathway, methodology adopted has been to develop theoretical foundations, models and systems to provision entrepreneurial choice making in highly complex, dynamic systems, operating in uncertain, resource - constrained situation. Although, based on neuro - operations translational research procedures, this translational research attempt includes multi - disciplinary emphasis to accommodate complex, multi - dimensional choice architectural frameworks.

1.33 For this purpose, methodology adopted for this study is outlined below;

Conceptual research has been directed consisting of following: -

- Choosing theoretical translational research queries,
- Literature probe in neuro - controlled 'inferential' catalogues,
- Congregation of selecting relevant literature, and
- Summarising and synthesising.

Empirical Journeys comprise of experiments on: -

- ‘Blood Signatures’ in entrepreneurial choice mechanism,
- ‘Eye Movements’ in entrepreneurial choice mechanism, and
- Empirical treatment of ‘Blood Signatures’ and ‘Eye Movements’.

Sample Population and Size

1.34 On radar are issues like, how to read minds, choice making ability (eye tracking and blood synthesis) and recommend a style of management in future. Moot question is what insights can behavioural science give us about entrepreneur’s choice. A sample of 150 (N = 150) representative entrepreneurs in Bhubaneswar have been chosen. Basic assumption is that samples so selected are best representative of population under study. This research incorporates stratified sampling methodology. Research architecture has been stratified into discrete layers. Each echelon has been experimented as a self-governing sub - population, of which specific rudiments have been designated casually. This has been facilitated to arrive at conclusions and interpretations about unambiguous subcategories. Such an exercise has facilitated package of statistical estimates. By means of stratified sampling, approach was deemed to be appropriate than accumulating data transversely towards groups. Since each stratum was viewed and subsequently treated as a self - determining populace, dissimilar sampling tactics has been adopted to dissimilar strata, theoretically empowering use of methodology best suitable for each acknowledged subcategory within populace.

Data Collection

1.35 **Primary data** and knowledge has been collected through process of pre - tested questionnaire, personal interviews and focus group interviews, personal observation, projective techniques, pilot survey to improve questionnaire, structured questionnaire, statistical judgement sampling and naturalistic observation. Some amount of ‘desk’ and ‘diary’ research was also resorted to. For empirical part, data has been collected through blood chemical analysis and eye training apparatuses. Blood analyzer equipment has been used for blood parametric analysis and Tobii equipment has been used for eye movement analysis.

1.36 **Secondary data** and knowledge has been chosen from Government Departments, Business Journals, Journals of Eyes and Brains, Plos One, Journals of Judgment and Choice Making, Scholarly Journals in Management, Conference Proceedings, Business Magazines etc. Engine Searches, where wide knowledge about different areas was easily available and hence banked upon. Data were corroborated from archival records and diary translational research sources

Tools and Techniques

1.37 **Questionnaire**: It was proposed to implement open-ended questionnaire. Paper - and - Pencil Questionnaire administration, Computerized Questionnaire administration and Adaptive Computerized Questionnaire administration can be contemplated for purpose of gathering information from respondents. Due to pandemic situation, questionnaires were floated through personal mails and through personal contacts.

1.38 **Statistical Techniques**: Once data / facts / information were obtained from primary and secondary sources, these were clinically tested through Blood Analyzer and Eye Movement Monitoring methodologies. This was to establish a co - relation between variables aimed at typically summing up discrepancy between observed values and values expected under the archetypal in question. Outcomes have been substantiated about entrepreneurs' choice making, dependency on characteristics, choice making biases and deliberate / intuitive reasoning approaches. Data obtained has been treated through;

- **T - Test**: Determine differences between means related in definite structures,
- **ANOVA**: Analyze differences among group mean and difference of variability,
- **Blood Analysis**: Check on physical and chemical properties of blood sample, and
- **Eye Movement**: Investigate dynamics of eye movements while deciding.

Assumptions

1.39 Assumptions engaged for this study are;

- Choice is clear and explicit ('Problematic Pellucidity').
- Entrepreneur identifies relevant alternatives ('Acknowledged Potentials').
- All substitutions and extents are known,
- Predilections are perfect, persistent and unchanging,
- There is no time or cost constrictions,
- Final choice maximises gainful payoffs,
- Changes are ranked and assigned weights ('Clear Penchants'),
- Weightiness assigned are unchanging over time ('Constant Predilections'),
- Full information is available ('No Time or Cost Constrictions'),
- Unconventional yield highest perceived value ('Concentrated Reckoning'),
- Explanatory schemes can be advanced at neuromanagement levels of analysis,
- There is judicious diagramming among above levels of elucidation.

Limitations

1.40 Current lack of attainment and determination, indispensable for corroborating models, are outlined to weak theoretic representation of choice making. Contemporary models are restricted in capacity to deliver all - inclusive appreciative of arena. Limitations envelop two crucial issues. These are primarily methodological and limit neuro - behavioural research that entrepreneurial Science has difficulty accepting in. Issues are (i) low influence in existing neuroscientific studies lead to questions over generalizability of results, and (ii) fundamental inability to localise phenomena in brain, blood and eye(s). This thesis gauges' prediction for emerging field of neuromanagement to cast light on customary affirmative and normative queries. It contends that possibility for evocative influences, nevertheless frequently misinterpreted and recurrently exaggerated, is however contemporaneous. Limitations encountered during this study were;

- Hematological aspects posed some manageable limits,
- Ophthalmic aspects posed some manageable limits
- Literature was scanned to study neuro - dynamics in entrepreneurial choice.

1.41 Application of hematological and eye tracking methodologies is currently a fresh attempt, in brain, eyes and blood dynamics in entrepreneurial choice making. This thesis appreciates that study - involving use of brain, eyes and blood dynamics in entrepreneurial is time - consuming than studies encompassing behavioural responses. Key limitation is that neuro - behavioural management approaches identify those regions of brain, blood and eye(s) that are stimulated when entrepreneurs are in constrained situations. These techniques, in some way, provide full explanation as to why entrepreneurs react in a certain fashion. A synergy between neuro - entrepreneurial techniques, eyes, brain, and blood experiments provide vision into appreciative entrepreneurial choice making.

Contributions to Scholarship

1.42 Some anticipated contributions to existing scholarship are as under;

- Neuro - management provisions for conjectural, experimental and investigational research,
- Study offers neuro - based solution to entrepreneurs' choice making,
- Study provides architectural framework for appreciation intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial Science and choice management,
- Dynamics of brain, blood and eye(s) activity affords information about underlying mechanisms in choice processes,
- Combining above disciplines gives interdisciplinary insight to fundamentals of neuro - entrepreneurial choice making, and
- Translational research findings are foundation for future translational research and scholarship would benefit from this study.

Chapterisation Schema

1.43 This work is compiled in the following tentative plan of Chapters.

- **Chapter - I: Introduction**

Within uncertainty, stress and strain environment, a prospect to anticipate about neural mechanisms underlying entrepreneurial choice making, this Chapter introduces the thesis under the title of 'Introduction'. Chapter revolves around 'human beings' and entrepreneurs as 'principal agents' who attempt to 'push' towards constancy in choice dynamics. Chapter presents 'biology - inspired entrepreneurial Science' revolutions that originate from management (Science of 'choice behaviour') and Psychology (discipline of 'thought') with reference to brain, blood and eye(s). Attempt has been made to reveal as to how rational events are concomitant to neurophysiological chronicles. There are incessant efforts to reveal brain, blood and eye (s) interrelations to appreciate how and why entrepreneurs make choices. Role of neuromanagement, brain and eye (s), possibly deliver answer to issues in entrepreneurial choice dynamics with orientation to '*Biological ('Mental Effort') Plausibility*'. Introduction introduces 'biology - inspired entrepreneurial Science' revolutions that emanate originate from Management (Science of 'choice behaviour') and Psychology (discipline of 'thought') with orientation to brain and eye(s), how cerebral events are associated to neurophysiological proceedings. Orientations have been made to a package of issues that confront a researcher in the laboratory and the entrepreneur in entrepreneurial organisation. Entrepreneurial issues have been highlighted that raise few fundamental issues and offers solution through measurement of brain activity at management levels of 'rationalism' analysis. *Entrepreneurial bio - linkages have been initiated that develop around hematological and ocular (eye movements) considerations. Some empirical processes have been recommended. Entrepreneurial neuro - linkages have been initiated that develop around hematological, brain imaging and ocular (eye movements) considerations.* Challenging observations, including some unexplained difficulties and objectives of proposed inquiry have been acknowledged. Hypothesis and research methodology have been offered that form pedestal of this analysis. A set of 'assumptions' and 'limitations' engaged for this inquiry is enumerated. Likely contributions to area of scholarship from this inquiry have been encouraged. Chapter - I culminate with Chapterisation Schema' of this thesis.

- **Chapter - II: Literature Survey**

This Chapter rationales to present an inter - disciplinary review of some neuro - based methods used in entrepreneurial choice. Literature Survey presents an inter - disciplinary

review of some neuro - based methods used in entrepreneurial choice making. Chapter describes basic strengths and weaknesses of each entrepreneurial aspect, provides examples of how each entrepreneurial aspect has been used with key orientations. Challenge is to promote models that apply outside lab and address complex challenges. Chapter describes rudimentary strengths and weaknesses of each characteristic with examples. In addition, review presents framework that organizes entrepreneurial (neuroscience) methods functionally. This is according to whether they afford trials of connotation between brain, blood and eye(s) activity and cognition or behaviour, or whether they test inevitability or modicum of brain, blood and eye(s) activity. Reviews include theories, investigational facts, figures, statistics, deductions, axioms, corollaries, inferences, conjectures and results of earlier studies well established in chosen area of inquiry; blood monikers, brain and eye (s). Review attempts to assimilate transdisciplinary research by integrating theoretical issues in choice, involvement of neuro - behavioural management, 'opportunities' and 'limitations', that allow fresh perceptions into in what way models can be corroborated or equated.

- **Chapter - III: Response Analysis**

This Chapter purports to craft an edifice of entrepreneurial neuro - choice making architecture via hybrid modeling attempts. Chapter depicts growing interest in exploiting and exploring probable links between human biology and management. Entrepreneurial Neuro - Architecture presents an edifice of entrepreneurial neuro - choice making architecture via hybrid modeling challenges. Chapter endeavours to establish relationship, through 'choice matrix' between 'commands of directive' between neuromanagement and entrepreneurial choice with orientation to neural actualities that endures 'orientation'. V - U - C - A situation has been demonstrated in form of new theory, examination of phenomena and advancement of analytic approaches. 'Entrepreneurial neuro - order' has been advocated that confer selective advantage in development of models. Neuro - choice operant; blood monikers and eye movements, have been examined using cognitive and emotional processes. These include exploring anatomy of neuro - discourses to functions of 'neuro - biologism'. This purports to cast greater attention to psychological processes in explaining entrepreneurial behaviour and choice effectiveness. Chapter endeavours to create connection, through 'choice matrix' between neuromanagement and entrepreneurial

choice with reference to neural actualities in development of models. Questionnaire analysis with psychological, neuro - behavioural and choice linkages have been presented. Interview responses add to analysis from a qualitative perspective. Neuro - choice operands have been examined using between brain, blood and eye(s) activity measurement processes. This is to offer neuro - based activity of entrepreneurial choice making, describe standard archetypes capable of envisaging observed entrepreneurial choice behaviour. These include pointers at functions of 'neuro - biologism'.

- **Chapter - IV: Neuro - Centric Experiments**

Chapter presents gist of neuro - centric experiments, results obtained, inferences drawn and a general discussion on 'cause' - and - 'effect' relationship in gamut of entrepreneurial choice. Chapter emphasizes on abstract concerns involved by means of diverse practices. Principal aim is to conduct neuro - centric experiments by likening its message / outcome implications with experimental observations, explore causes, establish empirical regularities as basis for new theory, comparing environments by protuberance of neural activity. Methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary neuro-centric approach. Principal neuro - centric methodologies tested are; hematological tests, eye movement tests by using Tobii apparatus and drawing deductions with reference to entrepreneurial choice. The first clinical analysis (Haematological 'Situation Reaction' Test) presents results of blood monikers from 150 respondents. For blood signatures examination, inputs from primary analyzer analysis have been dovetailed for understanding intersection of neuroscience, management and psychology. The second clinical analysis (Neuro - Ocular 'choice' Test) presents results of eye movements from 30 respondents. Methodology adopts inputs from Kowler, Hochman and Fang models for eye movement examination. Inputs from Kowler Model, Fang Model, Orquin Model and Hochman Model has been adopted and incorporated in experimental portions of this thesis. Objective is to learn about relevant eye tracking, design research questions, tasks and possible metrics, testing stimulus, create tests, analyse tracking 'inferential' data and generate result deliverables. Neuro - ocular analysis has been recommended as a framework for understanding and conducting research at intersection of brain and eye - based models capable of predicting and explaining entrepreneurial choice making.

- **Chapter - V: Summary and Conclusions**

Question of how entrepreneurs make choices continues to pose important challenges for scientific research. This Chapter summarises all Chapters contained in this thesis. Chapter summarises salient aspects as depicted in the thesis. This chapter pools all inferences drawn at various segments of the thesis with analytical homilies. Chapter *suggests fundamental change in Biological ('Mental Effort') Plausibility 'of how entrepreneurs need to think, observe and model business choice in all its contexts.* With a package of issues for further research, chapter attempts to advocate intersection of neuroentrepreneurial Science, management and psychology) towards providing conceptual framework towards conducting neuroentrepreneurial choice research, offering solution through measurements of neuro - activity at time of choices and prescribing a standard model for choice making. With package of issues for further research, Chapter attempts to advocate intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial Science, management and psychology towards providing conceptual framework for understanding and conducting entrepreneurial choice research.

Concluding Remarks

1.44 A complex choice progression takes many stages. Business of choice making is central to entrepreneurs. Despite inspiring accomplishments, neuro - behavioural management is at best a decade and half old and is yet to embody critical role in neuro - behavioural management. Researchers are still rhetoric whether neuroscientific 'inferential' information will expansively provide for entrepreneurial choice. Focus is on obligatory frameworks for interdisciplinary alliance. Being a maiden inquiry, thesis attempts to underwrite towards existing scholarship in following mode;

- | |
|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide frame for appreciating entrepreneurial choice research, and• Offer elucidation through dynamics of brain, blood and eye(s) during choices. |
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CHAPTER - II

LITERATURE SURVEY

Introduction

2.1 Decisions or choices are made relentlessly, vacillating from the tiniest of stuffs to key judgement that cast an influence from and on the brain. Is neuroscience an off - shoot of behavioral science or does cognitive science fit the bill? Does neuroscience influence human behavior or preference crafting, in particular. Homo Sapiens do appreciate, associate and operate data, statistics and information. How does human (entrepreneurs, as is the case) brain allocate value to diverse alternatives under consideration? How do they associate apportioned values in order to project a choice? How is 'process of valuation' changed when rheostat is used? How is value calculated in complex / abstract domains? How can neuromanagement be applied to strategy elucidations to real - time problems? For a long time, it has been argued that humans make choices by obeying laws of rationality. Expected Utility Theory has dominated understanding of choice analysis by postulating that under majority of circumstances, entrepreneur makes choices (whether under pure uncertainty, under risk or by pushing a problem towards deterministic 'pole') and choices by maximizing utility of any given outcome. There has always been an inter - twined approach with respect to resilience and chaos in preference architecture. However, in observing compartments, it is perceived that often this is not the case. This holds true for both risky and non - risky choices. Many compartmental experiments have been conducted. Diverse theories have been proposed to better explain compartment under risky situations.

2.2 Since ancient times, Scholars have studied choice - making from various perspectives and approaches. Over course of a few decades, social researchers and natural scientists have exasperated to appreciate how one makes choices. But, in general, analysis of choice is partitioned into three principal approaches. For most Economists, goal of studying human choice compartment is prediction. But, observation is that they have been applying various strategies using entirely diverse approaches. Since 1990s, groups of researchers embodying interdisciplinary attitude have initiated to combine social and natural scientific approaches to study dynamics of choice. Central assumption is that by coalescing both theoretical and empirical apparatuses from Neuroscience,

Quantitative Sciences, Psychology, Management Studies, Organizational Behaviour and Economics into a single tactic, resulting synthesis ensures provisioning insights valuable to three parent disciplines.

Methodology

2.3 This thesis relates an assimilated economic - psychological viewpoint. Scholarship of economic psychology lessons psychological progressions in entrepreneurial comportment by engaging philosophies and approaches from psychological science. To conduct a comprehensive review, Chapter confronts its scope to published Journals, Thesis and Books plus research literatures linked to bases, philosophies, methods and principles of Neuro Choice Making. Some key words punched for purpose of reviews were Neuro choice, Neuro Choice - Making, types of neuro Choice - Making, methods of Neuro Choice, classification of Neuro Choice, Neuro Choice Reinforcement, Neuro Choice Facilitation, Neuro Choice Reduction, Neuro Choice Deficiencies, Neuro Choice Optimization, Neuro Choice Assessment and Neuro Choice evaluation. Secondary sources were primarily extracted from published literatures by academic bodies and web search engines.

2.4 This Chapter purports to extant an inter - disciplinary analysis of some neuro - based approaches used in entrepreneurial choice. Challenge is to endorse representations that apply external lab and discourse multifaceted tests. This propositions rudimentary strengths and weaknesses of each specific and provides paradigms of how each characteristic has been used with key orientations. In calculation, review dowries frame that organizes (neuro) entrepreneurial approaches functionally. This is conferring to whether they manage to pay for choice rulings of undertone amongst brain, blood and eye(s) motion and cognition or comportment or whether they test inexorableness or modicum of brain, blood and eye(s) activity for understanding and comportment. Reviews include theories, investigational facts, figures, statistics, deductions, axioms, corollaries, inferences, conjectures and results of earlier studies well established in preferred area of inquiry; blood monikers, brain and eye(s). Review attempts to assimilate trans disciplinary research by integrating theoretical issues in choice, involvement of neuro - comportment management, 'opportunities' and 'limitations', that allow fresh discernments into in what way models can be corroborated or equated.

2.5 Neurosciences, closely followed by neuromanagement, is witness to activity associated with neurons, nerves or neuronal activates that clearly reflect essence of a 'Noise' or 'Chaos'. This is bound to take place as unpredictable nature of such natural dynamics do reflect certain unimaginable character that can only be ascertained and deciphered in a lab like condition. Neuropsychology takes care of indications for possible preferences that entrepreneur usually aims at. Along with Neurobiology, Neuropathology, Neuroeconomics and aspects related to magnitudes that encompass factors in flight path of crafting preferences and choices these seem to be inconsonance on a neural platform. This is in spite of argument whether there is an element of 'determined' or 'undetermined'. At lower level of reduction, Neurobiologists have been trying to understand neural pathways and computations that give rise to choice.

2.6 From point of emotions or emotional parallelism, search indications reflect elements of perceptive, motivation common emotion and characteristics that indicate towards a vivacious aspect. Impression that preferences are arrived at probable, logical or rational (logical and principal bases) conduits are severely being debated by experiments, lab propositions and philosophical agents. As these revolve around Neurobiological and allied Neuromanagement perspectives primarily pointing out at Cellular and Molecular structure and arrangements ('Signals of Origin'). Such points of origin do support or negate with (duly weighing costs and benefits of each potential response) evidence or justifications the perceptive conformations as to how choice dynamics is impacted or influenced.

2.7 *Entrepreneurs have to take choices under all situations and circumstances.* An issue arises; Is notion of rationality not in sync with aspects of stochastic complexity. Is 'Preference Anxiety or Alarm a cause of worry for *entrepreneurs*? It is a deduction from classical era that entrepreneurs have had an idiosyncratic methodology to indicate preferences. With onset of neuro - algorithms, are agents finding it difficult to conduct with unmanageable dosages of uncertainty, ambiguity and time pressure? Has this led to a stage and era of expressive stress (as in state of VUCA)? Why do entrepreneurs assume that almost all Choices, Preferences or Viable Options they choose are quite rational, optimal and based on best accessible neuro - based calculations?

2.8 *Is* such a belvedere, is this scenario an indication of what can be termed as ‘Preferential Compartments’? If answer is in affirmative, then entrepreneurs need to cross bridge and embrace essence of neuromanagement. Principal reason is that such debates (how preferential progressions transgress in brain pathways), arguments (how brain considers sources of intrinsic progressions) and counter argument are now subject to a pair of lens or prisms (design ‘rational’ preferences) in continuum of molecular researches or neurobiology of choice or preference - indication.

Objective

2.9 There are unexplained problems in entrepreneurial reasoning. Principal issue is, how do entrepreneurs make scientific preferences? If at all there is an attempt, do blood, eyes and brain aid in computing and help signify abstract thoughts? If this is accepted, then what about those entrepreneurs who are suffering from ‘Tensity’ (a new announcement by combining ‘Tension’ plus ‘Density’), worry, concern, tension, pressure, anxiety, strain, disquiet, alarm, distress, agitation, agony, angst, apprehension, stress, strain, pressure, stress, difficulty, demands, burden. *In simple words, what about those who are undergoing ‘hypotension’ or ‘hypertension’? This necessitates explorations on neuro - perspectives, hematological monikers and eye movement observations. Some allied propositions are that entrepreneurs can be subjected to advanced tests viz. Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Magneto Encephalography, Electroencephalography Positron Emission Tomography, Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation, Electro - Dermal Activity and Blood - Oxygen - Level Dependent Contrast Imaging with management experts in collaboration with medical researchers).* This Chapter attempts to scan available literature as regards studies conducted to study determinants of entrepreneurs’ choices, role of blood monikers and eye movements choice progressions.

Neuromanagement

2.10 Traditionally, neuromanagement researches were not interested in neuro - underpinnings of choice compartments. Over the past couple of decades, researchers exploring psychology of choice making have presented counterintuitive conclusions and deep perceptions besides recommendations concerning choice selections. In practice,

arena has coped with central inquiries about entrepreneurial 'equanimity' and influenced thinking on intuitively plausible axioms. This wave has transformed and fresh approach has appeared with focus on 'real' neuro - management. Therefore, it seems functional to investigate origin and explore its implication (Takizawa; 2018).

2.11 As regards management embracing neuroscience, Lukasz Sulkowski and Michal Chmielecki (2017) opine that scrutiny of unique entrepreneurial brain in a contemporary format is an interdisciplinary scholarship with subtle and fine line diversification between natural and social sciences ably supported by pillars of Neurology, Neuroscience, Psychiatry, Anthropology and Sociology with substantial contributions from include biology and psychology. Such a unified approach has ushered in a branching out approach to explore and exploit cognitive, emotional and cerebral perspectives into the realm of choice making. Application of neuroscience in management is the 'New Order 'of 21st Century management research and is big opening for innovative scholarships.

2.12 Emotion researchers continue to argue what might constitute a good choice. Humans are particularly adept at transforming comportment in accordance with changing demands. Through cognitive control, human beings tailor actions to fit complex goals. In measurable procedures support choice making. There is inquisitiveness in inspecting probable associations between Biological Science and Management. This conveyances consideration on rational progressions in expounding entrepreneurial comportment. What follow are engagements of propositions which fraught scope of revealed - predisposition philosophy to entrepreneurial choices with uncertain consequences? (Satpathy; 2020).

2.13 Satpathy et.al (2016) raised specific query in a paper titled 'Investigating Some Neuroentrepreneurial Models' as all undergoes in an activated entrepreneurial brain especially in the pipeline of about to arrive at intended or envisioned choice? Author(s) have raised query as to whether progressions in arena of neuromanagement are pertinent to entrepreneurs? This debate has cast a viewpoint that entrepreneurs seek to spend more time on information assimilation. As a result, more information gets assimilated causing state of 'Information Overload', 'Information Chaos' and 'Infoplosion' (a new announcement by combining 'information' plus 'explosion'). This paralyses effectiveness in choice making, ability. So how does brain deal with such a perilous

situation? The study states that entrepreneurial brain dynamics underlying prediction, control and choice making (linking neuro - psycho and management levels of analysis) undertakes this through neural computations.

2.14 Shiv et.al. (2015) in a study on choice neuroscience applications in (business) management have stated that in matrix of 'bridge' between neuroscience and management, attention is on how exponential accretion of knowledge in neuroscience can possibly enrich range of techniques. Study identifies challenges that neuro researchers need to be acquainted with. Authors opine that neuroscience can help management sciences, theory and practical combined by provisioning assenting indication about presence of singularity. Neuroscience can create a central neuronal conceptualization by accepting underlying progressions. Such aids in providing methodologies towards analysis of a 'Big Science' Model. In a web based anthology, Satpathy and Mishra (2019) have raised certain issues pertaining to choice management. A moot question raised is how does entrepreneurial brain analyze and evaluate choice making? What genetic and environmental aspects lend support? What are the strategy of cognitive intricacy? In a study on dynamics of neuro - management choice making, Satpathy (2015) has highlighted on assumptions, beliefs, habits and tactics that entrepreneurs use to make choices. Author is in consonance that entrepreneurial brain considers various sources of information that generally lead to impulsive, indecisive, and confused choices as a result of information chaos evidential reasoning and fusion.

2.15 Some literature on neuro choice making and modeling have been found in 'Anthological Commentary on Cerebral Guesstimates' by Satpathy, J., Gankar, S, S., and Okeyo, W. (2021), 'Neuro - Calibrations In Business Choice rulings' by Mallik, B., Satpathy, J., Gankar S. S., Rodriguez C. M., Hejmadi, A., Laza, S. and. Okeyo,W. (2021), 'Construal on Satpathy-Gankar 'Hemachocovation' Model by Satpathy, J. and Gankar, S, S (2021), 'Hematological Signatures in Technopreneurial Choice Corridors' by Satpathy, J., Gankar, S, S., Malik, B, Okeyo, W. and Chhaniwal P. (2021), 'Insightful Entrepreneurial Compartment Department' by Satpathy, J., Mishra, I., Padhi. S and Das, D. P., (2020), 'Neuro - Milieus in Technopreneurial Choices' by Satpathy, J. (2020), Century 'Tabula Rasa' Personnel Entrepreneur by Gankar, S. S. and Satpathy, J. (2020), 'Perceptive Entrepreneurial Choice Compartment' by Satpathy, J., Mishra, I., Laza, S., Padhi, S. and Das, D.P. (2020), 'Noetic Alleyways: Choosing to Choose or Deciding to

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2.16 In larger frame, challenges to standard view are challenges to homo economicus utility function. In addition, there are problematic aspects of homo economicus conception that create questions regarding standard view of rationality. Connotation is; individuality can be supposed to be 'bounded', (Kahneman and Tversky) and

'evolutionary' (Herbert Simon). Concept related to prospect theory, descriptive models of choice and choice making is of reference - dependent preferences. How entrepreneur assesses outcome of choice is ascertained in contrast with 'reference point', as by intrinsic taste for outcome itself (Kahneman and Tversky; 1979 and Koszegi and Rabin; 2006). Several authors proposed alternatives to Simon's phases (Glueck; 1976, Hofer, Schendel; 1978, Mazzolini; 1981, Schwenk; 1984, Gore, Murray, Richardson; 1992, Van de Ven; 1992 and Lu, Zhang, Ruan and Wu; 2007). Inquiry show that each contribution consists of disaggregating or aggregating phases identified in contributions. The above argument spectacles how diverse bounded entrepreneurial conceptions operate in relation to management of bounded rationality. Attempts to explain entrepreneurial comportment share ontological assumptions and practices that 'Adaptationist Model' in biology has been criticised for. This was largely abandoned as poorly motivated and replaced with active testing of adaptive and non - adaptive hypotheses regarding spread and maintenance of traits. This has been welcomed by biological community. This is laconically surveyed in Kirman's Marseille 'Scrutiny'. Author extends to include individuality to act in a purely self - regulating way. This is precluded in comprehensible derivation of distinctiveness (Satpathy' 2020).

2.17 An important process is based on high degrees of conscious progressions to decipher entire gamut of dynamics that bio - agents and brain plays in realm of choice making. Entrepreneurial brain considered as most complex, intricate and multifarious is observed to be playing domineering role in field of neuromanagement (neural circuitry). In fact, entrepreneurial brain is pivot of contemporary entrepreneurial activities. Physiology of cognitive progressions and multicellular (nerve cells of neural circuits) configurations of activity help to control choice comportment in entrepreneur. Of paramount importance is role of individual variances in choice making and topographies of brain neuroanatomy ('biomarkers') and neurophysiology ('Biomarkers').

2.18 Conceptual issues include, role of 'models' (Richard Gonzalez), contribution of neuro - comportment management, 'Opportunities' and 'Limitations' (Alan Sanfey) choice from 'Description' vs. choices from 'Experience' (Hertwig), 'unconscious' progressions (Balcetis), 'Meta Cognition' (Koriat) and models in 'reasoning' (Frederick). Multiple facets include; choice under 'Risk' (Craig Fox), choices under 'Ambiguity' (Trautmann), choice under 'Conflict': 'Hedonic' vs. 'Utilitarian'

approaches (Dhar), 'Time Pressure', 'Inter - Temporal Choice' (Gal Zauberman), 'Probability Assessments', 'Calibration' and 'Overconfidence' (Moore). Methodological lines include; 'Imprecision' and 'Noise' in choice making (Loomes), 'Experimental' Practices (Ortmann), information 'Sampling', 'Reasoning' Biases (Fiedler) and 'Joint' Vs. 'Separate' Modes of 'Evaluation' (Hsee). Contributions propose measurement techniques and paradigms that allow fresh insights into in what way models can be corroborated or equated (Satpathy; 2020). 'Cognitive Configuration' was acknowledged by Ausburn (1978). Messick (1976) connotes configurations as stable attitudes, preferences or habitual strategies that determine entrepreneurs' modes of problem solving. Witkin, (1977) characterizes cognitive configurations as how entrepreneurs perceive, think, solve problems, learn and relate (Satpathy; 2020). Although there are differences, it is not obvious how best to characterize such differences (determine significance). Several authors use 'Perceptual Affordances, 'Dispositions,' 'Configurations of Learning' and 'Learning Orientations' to conceptualise such differences. Turpin (2004) compares models of entrepreneurs 'Configuration' choice rulings. Significant variations are observed as apportioned by Argyris and Schön (1978), Hahn, Doh and Bunyaratavej (2009), Vendelo (2009), Easterby - Smith (2009), Cha, Pingry and Thatcher (2008), Hult, et al. (2000), Barrados and Mayne (1999), Daft and Huber (1987), Dekker and Hansen (2004), Dery (1983), Griswold (2003), Garvin (1993), Huber (1991), Levit and March (1988), West (1994) and Fiol (1985).

Eye Movements

2.19 Eye movement is supposed to be a significant indicator of how an individual is going to take a choice. Eye movement encompasses eye tracking (computing eye movements to regulate where an individual is watching, what they are observing at, and for how extended the duration is), eye tracing (how eyes move when a doppelgänger is visible in front) and eye gazing (act of viewing into something intensely or look securely and attentively at something). Eye tracking measures have been conceptualised in different approaches. Liversedge, Paterson, and Pickering (1998) illustrated use of time measures (Satpathy; 2020) and provided discussion of temporal measures versus spatial measures. Goldberg and Kotval (1999) evaluated spatial measures based on eye movement locations and scan paths for evaluation (Satpathy; 2020). Jacob and Karn (2003) have reviewed eye tracking techniques and abridged measures as fixation count,

proportion of time spent on each 'Area of Interest' (AOI), Average Fixation Duration, Fixation Count on each AOI, Gaze Duration means on each AOI, and Fixation Rate (Count/s). Radach and Kennedy (2004) grouped tracking measures into temporal scale (measured by time) and spatial scale (measured by space) (Satpathy; 2020).

2.20 Attempt was made to review available literature on role of eye movements in processing dynamics. Eye tracking method has been broadly applied to research involving information processing (Radach and Kennedy; 2004 and Rayner; 1998 / 2009). Measures have revealed fundamental cognitive processes and methodologies (Rayner, Chace, Slattery and Ashby; 2006) and visual perception (Liversedge and Findlay; 2000). Techniques have been applied to investigate human - computer interactions (Goldberg and Helfman; 2011 and Jacob and Karn; 2003). As for high level cognitive processing, some studies have attempted to utilise trackers for exploring process of choice - problem solving (Hegarty et. al.; 1992), complex choice contexts and problem solving (Tsai et. al.; 2012; van Gog and Scheiter, 2010). Reviews observe comprehensive eye tracking methods and practices in Duchowski; 2007, Holmqvist et al.; 2011 and Liversedge, et. al.; 2011.

2.21 In 2004, Radach and Kennedy describe fundamentals of eye movement to perfect corrective measures on unresolved issues and lacunas in realm of entrepreneurial choice making. Authors opine that there are limited studies in eye movements and this is an indicator that new researches need to emerge to support empirical findings and arguments towards a theoretical locus. This statement has gained judicious support from researches of Hyona, Radach and Deubel; 2003, Kennedy, Radach, Heller and Pynte; 2000, Liversedge, Gilchrist, and Everling; 2011, Radach, Kennedy and Rayner; 2004, Underwood; 2005, Van Gompel, Fischer, Murray and Hill; 2007. Rayner (1998, 2009) provides abridged overview in thesis.

2.22 Neuro - choice rulings lead to selection of path of action among alternative circumstances. Specific brain and eye(s) structures potentiate choice rulings making depending on strategy, traits and framework. Entrepreneurs' resources rely on careful simulated neuro - models to display relationship between 'Cause' and 'Neuro Incongruity'. Choice rulings, via. introspection, leads to model selection problem reflected as cohesive incessant process. This is concerned with Rationale,

Reasonableness and Invariant techniques. These reflect compensatory crossing point of neuro entrepreneurial choice rulings related expanse. Problem is to identify 'Regions of Rationality,' i.e., areas for which heuristics are antagonistic. Prevailing deliberations have lineage in making allowance for discipline of brain and eye(s) dynamics (Satpathy; 2015). Psychological models clarify evidence for choice rulings over time when evidence reaches critical level. When faced with obscure choice rulings, they engage in simplifications of choice rulings problems. Satpathy (2015) designed to help understand what effective entrepreneurs really do, examine personage variance in conjecture of (psyche) and entrepreneurial functions to clarify variation in symptoms that account for unpredictability. This consists of continuum ranging from 'Quantity - Oriented' entrepreneur ('Significant Performance') to 'Quality - Oriented' traditional entrepreneur ('Crossing Point' performance).

2.23 Eileen Kowler (2011) has undertaken a review of eye movements and states that researchers have remained focused on rudimentary (progress and transformations) and elementary issues like; what mechanisms and contrivances keep gaze dynamics of eyes stable with either mobile or static objects. How vision is impacted by the retina on which impacts the image motion. Where do individuals look and why do they look there? What prompts them to look where they look? When eyes are in either a state of gaze, trace or track, why is it that environment looks stable and static. Author argues that choice compartment remains to be a focus of dynamic curiosity. Kowler is of the view that normal day to day interactions involve movement of eyes that assimilates trillions of visual information and transfers it to human brain. Observed here is a connectionism between eyes and human brain. Need is towards understanding planning dynamics of each eye movement, how movements are approved by sensory organs and how do eye movements set to defeat incessant changes in visual array of human being. Focus is on link between eye movements and attention plus integration of eye movements with ongoing visual and cognitive progressions. Kowler (2011) has generally contributed in arena of predictive smooth pursuit eye movements, perceptual - motor costs, smooth pursuit eye movements, saccadic eye movements, pre - saccadic shifts, speed / accuracy trade - offs and role of priors in controlling smooth pursuit eye movements

2.24 What is revealed is that eye tracking approach, verifiable and testable algorithms, techniques, tools and applications propositions understandings into hominoid

responsiveness. Facts, figures and data generated from eye tracking expertise have potential and capability to deliver imperative information about choice maker compartment configurations and cognition. Literature scans lead to detection of pertinent literature on eye dynamics, neuro choice making and modeling. A paper by Satpathy, J., Hejmadi, A., Mishra, D. and Singh, S. (2018) on entrepreneurial eyes for business choices reveals that there's always an optimal effort by entrepreneurs to arrive at an optimal state of choice making progressions as to arrive at a near real choice. Question is; How? This has been dealt in a paper titled 'Neuro - Geometry in Choices' by Satpathy and Mishra (2019) wherein they have stated that choices is a new arena for research in neuro - geometrical entrepreneurial science. Such areas warranting interest need to revolve around multifarious cobweb of parameters, choice agents and elements. Anchoring on causal 'forward - backward posturing', authors have researched issues like; what is absorption dynamics as regards information by brain, how does brain deal with problematic issues and does brain flush out 'neuronal sewerage'? If yes, then how and when? Does it help in a (clinical - based) choice process? What then is the nuclei effect of brain mapping (dynamic capability) / imaging (evolutionary architectures) / scanning (cumulative quantum of evidence)? Authors have set forward archetypal for choice in which interaction between geometrical characteristics of choice progressions are designated through gradation of brain activity at time of choices.

2.25 Satpathy and Mallik (2018), in a study on mathematical exposition on eye movements in choice dynamics have protracted from a calculated choice compartments slant to cognitive tactic that emphasizes on mathematical choice progressions. Authors profess that in choice making, initially entrepreneurs must determine choice to be prepared, convoluted in mathematical choice route, time lined and expanses or consequences be attained. Additionally, entrepreneurs need to recognize as many replacements as plausible. Replacements need to be scrutinised. Substitutions need to be rank ordered and generated to implement appropriate options or amalgamations of selections. Issue is can scientific usage of eye tracking / gazing / tracing techniques be effectively utilised by entrepreneurs towards expanding information base? If yes, then how? This has received support from Fachhochschule Oberosterreich (2014) wherein the author has argued that information is basis of any qualitative choice making process. Hence, it all depends on capability, ability and potential and characteristic brain to process input information in an efficient and effective manner. Author highlights absence

of empirically backed strategies on how to use unambiguous graphical designs to influence perception.

2.26 Important problem is: what signals are used in guiding different types of choices? How does brain and eye(s) compare to make a choice? Emerging theme is that entities need to make value - related computations to make choices. Research suggests that it is useful to organise patterns in hierarchic mode (Satpathy 2020).

- Neural processes underlying how entrepreneurs design choices,
- Understand methodologies of choice making using neuroimaging methodologies and,
- Integrating transdisciplinary research to choice management.

2.27 Investigators are progressively attracted in role played by instincts and sentiments in choice processes (Baron,1998; Bonabeau, 2003; Gilovich, Griffin, and Kahneman, 2002 , Agor, 1986; Blattberg and Hoch, 1990; Hogarth, 2001; Klein, 2003; Pondy, 1983, Finucane, Peters, and Slovic, 2003; Hammond, Hamm, Grassia, and Pearson, 1987; Shapiro and Spence, 1997; Yaniv and Hogarth, 1993; Hogarth, 2001; Isen and Patrick, 1983; Khatri and Ng, 2000; Klein, 1998, 2002; Lowenstein, 1996; Lowenstein, Weber, Hsee, and Welch, 2001; Organizational Comportment and Human Choice Processes, 2001; Phillips, Klein, and Sieck, 2004; Parikh et al., 1994; Agor, 1986; Peters, Vastfjäll, Gärling, and Slovic, 2006; Rottenstreich and Shu, 2004; Schwarz, 2000). It is an axiom that choice dynamics departs from principles of established models (exploration has been piloted in experimental background) in realm of rational and cogent data (data inputs and outputs) processing.

Research Gaps

2.28 Neuro - entrepreneurial choice (contextual and complex process) has arisen as subfield within management. General distinction is between what Ross (2008) calls 'Neurocellular Management' (NE) and 'Emotional Choice'. This calls for critical inter - disciplinary inquiry on methodological practices of 'Neuro - Entrepreneurial Choice'. Issue in question is peculiarity between 'reflective' and 'Formative' paradigms. Former are identified or signposted by sets of observable markers. These perfectly replicate

single underlying embryonic variable. Such constructs are based on factor inspection high - loading items and discard low - loading ones. Determinative constructs have logical character of dependent variables in choice models. That is, they summarize interactions of range of independent (perhaps causally linked) variables (Glenn and Ross; 2005).

2.29 There is rising interest in exploring potential links between biology, management and entrepreneurial inquiry. This casts attention to bear on place of cerebral processes in entrepreneurial comportment. Biologists bring rigor by turning attention to management. There are concerns about relevance of neuro - comportment management for managements (Bennett - Hacker; 2003, Legrenzi - Umilta; 2011, Satel - Lilienfeld; 2013 and Tallis; 2014). Philosophy of neuro - comportment management tries to apply orthodox questions and models on explanatory strategies. Whereas this is considered skeptical or destructive, neuro - philosophy takes another 'contour'. Findings are applied to 'emotion' (Bermond; 2008) to gain empirically (Jungert; 2015). Issues are; which methods / theoretical assumptions are used in rationale of neuro - comportment management? What explanatory and theoretical basis claim to integrate neuro - scientific findings? These merit an inquiry. This encompasses: -

- Neural level which proposes neural networks in choice,
- Biological attributes in evolutionary and cerebral relevance in choice,
- 'Anthropological' components that describe conscious among species, and
- 'Psychological' aspects that provide definition to exact cognitions and emotions.

2.30 Some inherent gaps in entrepreneurial choice making are;

- Entrepreneurial choice under risk and ambiguity,
- Multi attribute entrepreneurial choice,
- Inter-temporal preference,
- Causal reasoning,
- Role of emotions,
- Imprecision and noise,
- Biases: implications, joint vs. distinct modes of evaluation, and

- Innovative directions, topical perspectives and conceivable future developments.

2.31 Questions that need to be answered include; how to choose in tough situations where stakes are high and multiple conflicting objectives? How should entrepreneurs' plan? How can entrepreneurs' deal with risks and uncertainties involved in choice? How entrepreneurs' can create options and become better choice makers? In this, inter - disciplinary review, research gaps identified for investigations are;

- How does entrepreneur decide in a state of Risk, Uncertainty and Probability?
- What is role of 'bio - 'agents' in entrepreneurial choice?
- What is role of 'eye - movements' in entrepreneurial choice?
- What is role of 'blood monikers' in entrepreneurial choice?

Conclusion

2.32 There seems to be clear and consistent mappings between events at neural level and events at compartment level. Details of neurobiological function provide valuable constraints for 'Psychoneuroeconomic' designs. Study requires extensive empirical study to offer solution through 'inferential' data obtained via. series of measurements of brain, blood monikers and eye(s) activity at time of choices. This provides framework for understanding research at crossing of neuroscience, management and psychology. It describes standard model for entrepreneurial choice process inquiry (Satpathy and Gankar; 2016). There is a need to ascertain 'Neuro - Based Agents' that help model a 'Rational Choice Mosaic'. This investigation communiqué effort at pointing out how neuro contraction reconnoiters entrepreneurial rational choice making. Attempt has been to identify some genetic basis of rational choices traversing significant role of 'neuromanagement' in arch typing entrepreneurs' rational choice strip. There is an imperative need to discuss results and information to chaperon neuro discipline in rational choices. Research presumably offers 'Quay' of 'Hematological Neuro - Agents' and 'Rational Choices Schemes' to appreciate how entrepreneurs make rational choices.

CHAPTER - III

RESPONSE ANALYSIS

Introduction

3.1 Is choice making 'rectilinear' with straight lines and shapes? Is choice making 'curvilinear' depicting some different connotations? Are choices representative(s) offshoots of molecular movements offering flexible and accurate alternatives along 'choiceal pathways'? Is choice making 'Autotrophic' crafting its own procedural protocols? Is choice making 'heterotrophic' crafting procedural protocols from external 'Agents'? Is choice making 'Saprotrophic' depending on protocols from external 'Agents'? Is choice making an assembly of well - defined 'Symmetry of Torics' with moment angled manifolds and complexes? Do all these reflect some degrees of combinatorics? Entrepreneur has to take choices with insufficient experimented facts. It is stimulating to compare several courses of action and select one to be executed. The question is does the brain oscillate between actions? Why do entrepreneurial choice researchers undertake experiments? Is it to test a notion or outcome implications with experimental observations? Does abstract representations aid comparison or plots in the sensorimotor map have a round about? Is it to establish empirical regularities as basis for new notion(s)? Is it for comparing choice settings? Dynamics of Eye movements and Blood monikers are 'catalysts' of neuro entrepreneurial choice. When entrepreneurs sort choices, they commit deviations in their signature behaviour. In neural computational simulations, each entrepreneurial choice task is signified by protuberance of neural activity. Choice related neural activity has constituents of spiraling of activity and choice initiation to overcome choice to be completed. It seems like there is a scattered accord transversely planes of portrayal. One way is to scan entrepreneurial choice behaviour. Blood Monikers and Eye Movements are crucial measure indistinctly concomitant to choice reflection. Both are chromatic prospects for rational processing which measures and calibrates to reveal or reflect what entrepreneurs are contemplating.

3.2 Is designing prototypes of cognition an efficient means of answering entrepreneurial choice? Methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary review approach. As a dynamic between theoretical and applied entrepreneurial choice dynamism, attempt has been to combine conception and experiments. This is to

undertake task of disentangling subtleties and implications of distinction between risk, ‘deep’ uncertainty and ambiguity. To make a choice when strata - layering is ambiguous, all possible layering of situation have been factored. Information across categories is integrated. Attempts employ multi - method approach and triangulation drawn on positivist and interpretive conceptual paradigms. This likens methodology to building with ‘foundation’ (philosophical premises), ‘pillars’ (consisting of conceptual research approach / strategies / ‘inferential’ data collection / inquiry matrix) and ‘subsidiary inclusive structure’ (operational architecture). This starts from theoretic inter - disciplinary review leading to specificities. It is a waterfall - based (‘Top - Down’) approach.

3.3 Appreciation of how eye movement and Blood monikers are premeditated and carried out notwithstanding recurrent vicissitudes has remained a fundamental question; What dynamisms keep choices clear and stable despite occurrence of VUCA? This proposes that Eye movement and Blood monikers have contributory stimulus on entrepreneurial choice formation in rational fashion. This study employs Eye movement and Blood monikers monitoring as method in entrepreneurial choice. Major effort is appreciating how should entrepreneurs’ decide, deal with ‘risks’ (‘Swim With Sharks In Muddy Waters’) and ‘uncertainties’, create options better than initially available, latent responses to problems and weigh strengths / weaknesses of prospective action using apparatus of choice making and eye movement (Satpathy and Mallik; 2016).

Research Methodology

3.4 Aim is to comprehend subjects’ relevance judgment based on Eye movement and Blood monikers method. Fundamental exploration has two components; first, how Eye movement and Blood monikers ‘inferential’ data is concomitant with fortitude of bearing of portions of content displayed. Next, connections crop up between eEye movement, Blood monikers and Cognitive Loads (‘Mental Effort’) during exploration tasks? Besides analyzing questionnaire responses, principal methodologies adopted for this inquiry are as under: -

- Hematological tests,
- Eye movement tests, and

- Drawing inferences with reference to entrepreneurial choice mechanism.

3.5 A 'questionnaire' was distributed amongst 156 entrepreneurs from various sectors; small scale, medium scale and large scale, as on available / accessible basis. This was done primarily to bring about a near - perfect distribution of entrepreneurs from spectrum of entrepreneurs in VUCA menacing world. There were some negligible anomalies in responses received. Choice was exercised to accept 150 (out of 154 - all correct) responses received. For clinical tests in hematology, 150 volunteer entrepreneurs were chosen free from any medical or clinical restrictions. These entrepreneurs enjoyed top physically fitness, 'good' trim and shape, fine fettle, not diseased and possessed robustness, ruggedness, stamina, strength, toughness, vigour and vitality. For eye movement test, inquiry considers measurement and exploration of variables that influence response. Emphasis was on Eye movement to get prevue into choice making tasks. 30 - subject research design has been used to serve as a heuristic model that facilitates clinical reference to undertake the test.

Questionnaire Exploration **(Neuro - Behavioural Aspects)**

3.6 A questionnaire set was distributed among 156 entrepreneurs of which 154 all - correct responses, without any blank responses, were received. Questionnaire was designed in a manner that responses to questions could be scored and figured to acquire complete extent of attitudes and opinions of entrepreneurs. It was aimed at unswervingly realise research purposes through assumingly wide - ranging and precise 'inferential' data to be investigated quantitatively. Caution was adopted to lessen total expanse of measurement inaccuracy. Responses and inferences are presented in the subsequent sections and sub - sections.

3.7 For purpose of exploration, entrepreneurs have been categorised in the following groups; Group 1: Male subjects - (Aged : 25 - 40 years) - Total: 32, Group 2: Male subjects - (Aged : 41 - 55 years) - Total: 29, Group 3: Male subjects - (Aged : 56 - 70 years) - Total: 19, Group 3: Male subjects - (Aged : 56 - 70 years) - Total: 19, Group 4: Female subjects - (Aged : 25 - 40 years) - Total: 31, Group 5: Female subjects - (Aged : 41 - 55 years) - Total: 30 and Group 6: Female subjects - (Aged : 56 - 70 years) - Total: 09. The entire scatter of respondents is shown in Table - 1.

3.8 The first question in questionnaire, pertaining to psychological linkage, concerns with 'Openness to Experience'. Question was aimed at soliciting views as regards vigorous imaginings, ocular understanding, focus on inner feelings, penchant for variability and rational inquisitiveness. Question was posed from point of view of human personality as depicted in conventional 'Five - Factor' Model. Aim was to observe whether entrepreneurs were receptive and welcoming new ideas, fresh approaches and innovative thought processes. It was conjectured that any entrepreneur who was 'high' on 'Openness to Experience' would be a go - getter / risk - taker on path of business - adventurism.

3.9 Responses in Table - 2 is suggestive of the fact that majority of entrepreneur - entrepreneurs in Group 1, 2 and 3 accord more than 72% as regards multi - faceted, resourceful, deep, reflective and knowledgeable factors are concerned. Range is between 72% to 91%. But, as regards factors like 'rational' is concerned, range is between 61% to 64%. As regards 'unproductive' factor, range is between 09% to 12% and 'unchallenging' factor commands a range between 27% to 34%. Group 1 being an appreciably young age, they seem to establish powerful cognitive reflections (absorb in supplementary consideration). Same trend is somewhat parallel in case with Group 2. There is some degree of lop - sidedness with Group 3. Comparable argument stands valid for Group 3, 4 and 6, respectively. It is circumstantial that high percentage of entrepreneurs belong to 'creative - flock' (massed together). These elements are carriers of unambiguous cognitive aptitude, intellectual, ocular and emotion - laden engagement. There is a drive to engage in philosophies, cogent - oriented and sense of openness (genii by which brain gets evidence). These open opportunities for creativity. This abundance of input is equally matched with ounces of output. In such a scenario, element of decentralized choice making atmosphere is projected.

3.10 Above exploration can be focused on brain dynamics in that openness to experience is allied with distinction in brain assembly. They are comprehensive in thinking, spread - out in how they process information and those with higher percentage on any of above factors tend to reason and act resourcefully. They view world of business creatively different. Their brains and mind harbour significant ocular and cognitive responses. There is an experiential superior 'extensiveness, penetration and

penetrability of business and choice awareness' and inclination to 'cognitively reconnoiter' intellectual information (ideas and arguments) plus sensory 'inferential' data. All these lend a significant part in shaping business choice making inventiveness. The role of 'chromosomal - influence' is factored at this stage of exploration.

3.11 The second question, pertaining to psychological linkage, concerns with 'choice to join business'. When issues are being debated as regards changing work - life balance, VUCA, changing dynamics of work, market fluctuations, anxiety etc., why is it that prompted entrepreneurs to join world of business? This question was engaged to solicit the entrepreneurial mind set to join vocation of business. A set of 29 'appealing - factors' were offered to entire cluster of entrepreneurs whose response percentages are shown in the Table - 3. Question was aimed at soliciting views with simple options of 'Agree' or 'Disagree'.

3.12 Advances in neuromanagement offers packages of modules like 'Neurofeedback' and 'Capito' models as to how training for the brain and brain for training act and interact amongst themselves. Broadly, these have an umbilical connect with Neuroleadership as defined by entrepreneurial personae. Indicative of comprehensive skills for entrepreneurial development, aimed at holistic skill set and mind - set, was the first option offered to entrepreneur - entrepreneurs. It is experiential that 94% of male entrepreneurs and 91% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour. Inference drawn is that training is a catalyst towards cultivating subjective efficiency and team concert. This is envisioned critical in direction of client connections and inclusive *business* progress. Issue is how is brain concerned about training perspectives in business arena? Corollary is that a positive mental attitude in business is indispensable. It is learnt from neurosciences that patterns of brain activity changes subsequent to training. Attention is drawn to 'Capito Model' by Thomas Feiner of Institute for EEG Neurofeedback (IFEN), Munich (Germany) which is recommended for future researchers but outside the scope of this Thesis. Slight shift in dynamics of brain activity does reflect adoption of control strategy. It is conjectured that entrepreneur - entrepreneurs are quite alert to comebacks as regards emotions of stake - holders. They allot space towards turning possibilities and probabilities into near - perfect outcomes and results. Entrepreneurs are (perhaps) attentive towards mind - set, relationships, perception, influence and thinking. They are tactical Agents, trendsetters and

transformation Agents. They are dedicated to distinction, pellucidity and exactness. Training seizes opportunity to capture emotional reactions that help initiate unconscious judgements. Demand for training is up - curve as entrepreneurs who are at top edge of curve see that emotion does influence business performance. Neuro - scientifically, training leads to swing in sensory motor information from slow to fast and alleyways. Training results in separation of neuronal ensembles generating self -regulating torrents of information handling. Effectual multitasking develops through prefrontal cortex.

3.13 Economic life as characteristically considered by self-centeredness, convenience and profit escalation. 'Long run profit maximisation', in gamut of variable costs of factors of production (land, labour, capital and organisation) was second option offered to entrepreneur - entrepreneurs. It is experiential that 78% of male entrepreneurs and 59% female entrepreneurs opined in favour. Inference drawn is that entrepreneurs aim at profit maximisation in short as well as in long - run. This can be an exception as regards philanthropic organisations. Given techniques of production, choice of techniques, favourable and non - advantageous factors, business environment, regulated price, input, and production planes, it is an undeniable fact that principal aim of commercial entity is to spiral profit intensification. If entrepreneurs are registering usual profits in short run there will be development of productivity and they presume to see new competitors in market. These act as pointers for re-arrangement of capitals.

3.14 Neuropsychology embraces that there exists strong link between *profit maximisation* and survival in unpredictable business. When profit maximisation is reliable with high rates of persistence, entrepreneurs adjust conclusively towards optimal state. When survival and profit maximisation are counter balancing, entrepreneurs improve effort to persistence rates. Comprehensions into tenacious sequences of affluence and out of order are reflective as to how brain aims at equilibria thereby influencing choices. A significant conjecture is that non - conformities from profit maximization cannot help entrepreneur to survive long in playground of business. Observation is that 59% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour. On lines of argument presented above, it is experiential that 94% of male entrepreneurs and 79% of female entrepreneurs favour maximisation of sales. Similarly, 91% of male entrepreneurs and 66% of female entrepreneurs have opted for improving market shares as intent to join business. Likewise, 87% of male entrepreneurs and 53% of female entrepreneurs

opted for **maximisation of shareholder value**. Neuroscience holds that emotions are influencing factor in business dynamics. A thought process is that these entrepreneurs are happy, satisfied and contented with roles in business play and life, in general. 'Symptomatic Bias' is experiential here. These are experiential methodical designs of non - conformity from standard or judiciousness in choice making. This is adequate to thwart process of choice and need is to identify, challenge and inject innovative dosages. These forecasts of strong relevance for 'ordering' entrepreneurial elements of future.

3.15 Entrepreneurs, continuously attempt to act in phase - wise manner of eternal business surveillance and intuitively poised based on business information. Strategic intelligence enables to control things that thwart prospects. Entrepreneurs are supposed and expected to be 'good' business citizens. Corporate Social Responsibility was third option offered to respondent - entrepreneurs. It is experiential that 12% of male entrepreneurs and 18% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour. Likewise, for option of service to Society, 16% of male entrepreneurs and 37% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour as reason to join business. It is experiential that as regards corporate social responsibility and service to society are concerned, opinion is somehow a state of near - balance. With such falling percentages, choice to join business appears to be strong by majority of entrepreneurs.

3.16 Branded as 'Business - Conscience', corporate social responsibility (whether right or wrong) is supposed to take care of socio - economic and environmental concerns of stake - holders. It is significant towards ushering in (internal) business environmental invigoration. This is aimed at business - profit and social welfare balance. These promote sense and satisfaction of business accountability. There appears to be a mind - set that social responsibility reduces profit margin as such projects do not lend towards rising profit curve. Entrepreneurs pronounce that such schemes mean 'stealing of rightful assets'. They need to focus on bottom line towards survivability. In view of profit maximisation psychology, there exists no repudiating potency of this dispute. Irrefutably, corporate social responsibility has been accorded low priority. This section can be branded as objectivity, evidence, quantification; rationality as far as corporate social responsibility is concerned. Rational approach 'left brain' is recognized to be 'weak'. Concentration is on business profit maximisation rather than social responsibility

agenda. Hence, low proportion of entrepreneurs opining social responsibility reason to join business stands evidenced.

3.17 As regards reason to join business, opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work found favour with 79% of male entrepreneurs and 55% of female entrepreneurs. It is boost for any firm to offer challenging and interesting work to entrepreneurs. This is aimed at human resources management and development that ultimately leads to organisation development. In a fast - paced, dynamic, erratic nature of economy and challenging business world, these act as top 'Motivating Agents'. In case obverse is experiential, then it is a wake - up call for management of work dynamics and environment. An impressive high percentage of entrepreneurs opting for these options are suggestive of the fact that 'mind set' to perform are high on joining business organisation. It is indicative that entrepreneurs are ready to move out of their 'comfort zones' and jump across periphery. Management of potential, with respect to 'Optimal Anxiety' is call of hour.

3.18 As regards option of 'reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard', in current scenario, is concerned, found favour with 32% of male entrepreneurs and 45% of female entrepreneurs. This seems to be a discouraging response. An interesting 'inferential' data set is experiential. There seems to be an air of pessimism. Is it that entrepreneurs felt that they lack cutting edge skills and expertise to compete with modern forces of business competition? Is it that entrepreneurs lacked some bundle of professionalism? Is it that entrepreneurs **have failed to erect adequate backing in net of advisers, backers, and envois around them?** Is it that entrepreneurs failed *to distinguish zones that could be used to register improvement?* Is it that entrepreneurs have anticipated a 'Grey Ceiling'? Was it a mere temptation to opt for such an option whose final results read '32% for male entrepreneurs and 45% for female entrepreneurs'. This can be discounted as an aberration. Nonetheless, micro - neuroscience based treatment may reveal that entrepreneurs, in this thesis, can ward off with this pessimistic tone if they develop air of aficionado. This is presented from point of view of role of emotion in choice making. Entrepreneurs are performing keeping in view that 'brain is never truly at rest'. Robust optimism is alley forward towards progress. *Perhaps, based on* analytic and scientific thinking, *concept of* 'Transcendence' (based on a 'Gut Feeling'), not definable in terms of customary appreciative or experience, still keeps them performing as effective and

efficient entrepreneurs. Inference is that entrepreneurs perhaps have put their faith on intuition (reference is drawn to the concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception), certain that choice to join business is a viable intention?

3.19 Universe is a harbour of unlimited choices that generates fountain of ridiculously high expectations. 'Expectation to grow with career path clearly mapped' found favour with 44% of male entrepreneurs and 57% of female entrepreneurs. Presently, many educated people are coming with idea of joining early start - ups where expectation to grow with career is clearly mapped out or at least a blue print is available. There is a set of well - defined purpose, vision, goal, skill, knowledge, attitude, competence, networking, mentorship etc. where career path is well - projected. This is a clear cut case of career mapping. An ideal career path is diagrammed along dotted lines. These lead to prescription in progression of jobs, traditional straight up career striking order, dual occupation striking order and level occupation frameworks. Entrepreneurs feel that such resources are premeditated to help recognise skills and aptitudes to advancement within business domain. Issue is; how is brain a catalyst in depicting expectation to grow in career path? Fact is that such expectation takes birth from environmental and societal realisms. When one participates in cognitive information flow, it is by default that blue print appears to decide as to what is required to subsist in business world. In fact, 'attention to thriving' gains ascendancy. Since 'expectation to grow with career path' is a course of action, brain starts journey in unmapped terrains. It is factored that figures of 44%, in respect of male entrepreneurs and 57% in respect of male entrepreneurs, respectively is may be due to experiential and unexperiential forces of VUCA. To lend credibility, an interesting observation is that as far as 'opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work' option is concerned, 79% of male entrepreneurs and 45% of female entrepreneurs have opted for the same.

3.20 Peter Drucker has voiced, 'Wherever you see a successful business, someone once made a courageous choice.' Wilfred A. Peterson voiced, 'choice is the spark that ignites action. Until choice is made, nothing happens. Choice is but courageous facing of issues, knowing that if they are not faced, problems will remain forever unanswered.' Option was offered pertaining to 'I come to work purely to get business done'. Interestingly, 96% of male entrepreneurs and 87% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour. This clearly sparks element of 'dedication' and 'commitment' as far as

entrepreneur - entrepreneurs are concerned. This seems to be a visible, transmittable passion, attitude and character, initiative and work ethics. There is perhaps an idea to bring about a metamorphosis from urge to practical reality. Neuro - based judgements report that letting passion die is the worst episode than not possessing passion at all. Entrepreneurs are perhaps subscribing the quote, ‘‘There is far more opportunity than there is ability’ (Thomas Edison) and ‘Don’t worry about failure’. You only have to be right once’’ (Drew Houston). Captivatingly, 85% of male entrepreneurs and 84% of female entrepreneurs have preferred to opt for option ‘My loyalty is defined and I feel a part of a team in businesses. This subscribes to neuroscience of trust in joining business. There is a sense of loyalty, brains hardwired to trust, air of evolutionary psychology (explains mental and psychological traits) besides allied reasons that have prompted them to join business. Such forces design adaptation to changing conditions and patterns of choice behaviour. This apparently provides cognitive suppleness to acquire from practices, monitor business world based on calculations and fine - tune activities when estimates are violated. From neuro - science angle, this is a case of neuro - plasticity (either way; functional as well as structural) that depicts changes in brain of respondent entrepreneur to adapt behaviour in face of changing demands. Path is critical to developing choice stratagems. Strong parallels are experiential between understanding of entrepreneurial brain and how businesses work. These must have prompted entrepreneurs to join business.

3.21 Brain is basis and carter of emotions and behaviors. Grit is a successful venture only if immersed in controlled - perseverance and controlled - passion. To lend credence, it is experiential that as regards, ‘I feel reciprocated efforts put in by me’, 77% of male entrepreneurs and 59% of female entrepreneurs have designated in favour. It seems that big motivation for entrepreneurs was ‘norm of reciprocity’. There is subscription to the fact that ‘inferential’ data on brain function and structure employ unique supremacy and stimulus in emotional status that aids in choice making. This appears to be a state of honoured web of commitment. As regards motivation to contribute cent percent to business for future benefits, 96% of male entrepreneurs and 89% of female entrepreneurs have designated in favour. It is neuroscientifically established that motivation guides behaviour. It involves and capitalises upon biological, responsive, societal and reasoning forces. Even opportunity of ‘chance to learn new things in my work’ has been supported by 89% of male entrepreneurs and 92% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Chance of

achieving something worthwhile has been supported by 93% of male entrepreneurs and 91% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Option of 'chance to use my abilities' has been supported by 94% of male entrepreneurs and 87% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Option of 'Supplementary options like 'I will work for business indefinitely registered favour with 78% of male entrepreneurs and 79% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Option of 'carrot and stick policy' has received unexcited response with 57% of male entrepreneurs and 68% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Entrepreneurs were perhaps aware that there exist explorations and observations which certify that human behaviour is influenced by change efforts and threats and infrequently prosper in long run. Option of 'being able to change things' ('Change Management') has been chosen by 91% of male entrepreneurs and 88% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Also, 'I work to achieve goals of businesses was preferred by 98% of male entrepreneurs and 94% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. This may have elicited spirits of acknowledgment. Perhaps entrepreneurs are aware that above line of reasoning makes it conceivable to shape ongoing interactions and interfaces. Hence, strong choice to join business.

3.22 Mankind is 'under a cowl of mindful attentiveness' A couple of soft - option like; 'entrepreneurs in business evaluate different management practices' has been preferred by 69% of male entrepreneurs and 71% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Additionally, option of 'business in high concert organisation' has been opted by 94% of male entrepreneurs and 92% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. These options were offered from point of view of entrepreneurial psychology and ascertain as to why entrepreneurs were inclined to join business. It is gestimated that entrepreneurs are aware of intrinsic and extrinsic aspects aligned to soft - options offered. 'Having a say in matters of businesses' has been preferred by 95% of male entrepreneurs. 91% of female entrepreneurs have opined for the same. It is presumed that entrepreneurs are under influence of being administrated by subconscious routes as well as unconscious route paths. Supporting the proposition is option 'choice to remain involved' which has been chosen by 93% of male entrepreneurs' and 91% of female entrepreneurs. Consequently, a strong choice to join business.

3.23 Human beings have got boundless *potential and are* hardwired for regeneration and reinvention by injection of fresh perspectives, new experimental models, new technologies and innovative pathways of operations. Final option 'business harnesses

your potential' has been preferred by 79% of male entrepreneurs and 76% of female entrepreneurs, respectively. Is this master - option a strong choice to join business? It can be safely inferred that entrepreneurs are aware about neuroscience of leadership. They are apparently aware of practical strategies they would encounter as an entrepreneur. They are enthusiastic towards better understanding to advance business leadership behaviours. They are self-aware, proficient in motivating and appealing towards business goals.

3.24 As regards 'proficiency about choice making' is concerned, options offered were, no proficiency little proficiency, average proficiency, 'good' proficiency very 'good' proficiency and rich proficiency. The readings indicate increasing order of 'overall' choice proficiency as experiential Table 4. It can be inferred prima facie that choice making capacity of entrepreneurs seems to grow with each passing age. 'inferential' data was collated by amalgamating responses received under heads; no proficiency little proficiency, average proficiency, 'good' proficiency very 'good' proficiency and rich proficiency. This may primarily be linked to business experience, business acumen and business awareness. In age - group of 25 - 40 years, figure of 51% for males and 49% for females is experiential. This is self - explanatory as entrepreneurs are in their initial stages of entrepreneurial responsibility and there can be some room for inconsistency of actions which can impinge choice process. It is conjectured that there could be unpredictability in performing practices, displacement of responsibility and the like. In age - group of 41 - 55 years, we observe a figure of 68% for males and 54% for females. As can be experiential, in age - group of 56 - 70 years, we observe a 87% for males and 73% for females. It can be safely assumed that choice maturity by these entrepreneurs could be, overtime, acquired by spotting choice behaviour of fellow entrepreneurs. In phonology of neuroscience, prefrontal cortex is the last that develops fully. This 'definitely impacts 'executive choice'. Neuroscience enables explore dynamics of brain to understand how women and men decide differently. There are authentic differences in brain structure, responsible for ability to function, between them. Neuroscience establishes that prefrontal cortex modifies its edifice and role in response to experiences. This is reflective of supplementary unfolding of genetic choice making blueprint. Such flexibility and protracted growth provides prospect for incessant adjustment of cognitive 'choice' function (through combination of brain organisation, hormones plus 'neurotransmitters'). These direct choice making command in 'hard - disk' of brain.

3.25 Pertaining to 'Person - Business Fit' options offered were; 'Personal values are 'good' fit with business', 'Business has same values as I do with regard to concern for others', 'Business has same values as I do with regard to honesty and ethics' and 'Business has same values as I do with regard to fairness and justice'. These are presented in Table - 5. There is overwhelming response from all categories of age - groups as regards option of 'Person - Business Fit'. In age - group of 25 - 40 years, we observe 71% of males and 69% of females have voiced in favour of 'Strongly Agree'. In age - group of 41 - 55 years, we observe 88% for males and 84% for females have voiced in favour of 'Strongly Agree'. In age - group of 56 - 70 years, we observe figure of 97% for males and 93% for females have voiced in favour of 'Strongly Agree'. There is perhaps general arrangement that entrepreneurs make choice by using expectations, philosophies, behaviours, mentality and approaches. Value congruence leads to optimistic consequences. Factual worth of 'value congruence' is when it is put into framework. Research is yet to provide valid instrument to extent 'Person - Organisation Fit' or 'Value Congruence'. Possible instrument of judging is through deep semi - structured interviews that possibly may divulge how entrepreneur views values and assesses these. Interestingly, some neuro - based studies establish a relationship between 'Entrepreneur - Organisation Fit' and 'Career Success' plus 'Satisfaction'. With age, maturity and development, notion of 'Person - Business Fit' is on ascendancy. These may prompt entrepreneurs towards 'good' 'choice making' ability. Hypothesis in neuro entrepreneurial research; 'Brain Makes the Fit' is quite pertinent here. This is because entrepreneurial neuroscience accepts the dictum that behaviours are driven from cataleptic somatic processes in brain. This thesis recommends further research in 'entrepreneur - organisation fit implementation', 'success factors' and measures. This ricochets Nagel (1974) who said, 'it may be impossible for us to abandon certain ways of conceiving and representing ourselves, no matter how little support they get from scientific research'.

3.26 As regards 'Work - Personal Interface', options were 'business philosophy defines how to operate business', 'amount of work responsibility and norms of performance are centered on business', 'ties with present business are difficult to break and are central to existence', 'business shows concern and cares about opinions and well-being', 'business strongly considers goals and values' and 'help is available when I have a problem. There is a metaphysical touch to this questionnaire item with 'that resonates'. Observations are presented in Table - 6.

3.27 It is experiential that more than 70% of all age - groups in each gender have opined to strongly agree for options offered. Conventionally considered as province of social philosophy, these options reveal flashes of neuro-theology and neuro-psychoexploration. It seems probable that in VUCA, there appear some elements of 'consciously cultivated trust'. Trust is pedestal on which entire edifice of work - personal interface revolves. This is an ideal strategy for inter and intra - organisational choice oriented work flow. It gives idea that 'business psychology' or 'occupational psychology' is influencing entrepreneurs. There appears to be a flow of balance between somatic, psychological and emotive dynamisms. This certifies 'single mindedness on development mind set'. This has apparently led to stable attention, better attention and mediator judgements ('creative ability'). Studies find neurobiological substrates in using neuroscience towards optimising philosophy of trust interpositions on brain to endure reasonable improvement in choice behaviour. This thesis calls for experiments in future measuring trust, changing environment of trust and trust as critical success factor in organisations. These do aid in choice process.

3.28 As regards 'Profit and Wages', options offered were; 'reward procedures in business are fair, 'if I work hard and am productive, I am compensated by profits, 'I have plenty of opportunities for growth / reward, 'those who deserve rewards receive them with fairness', 'business will notice if productivity or work quality declines' and 'are you satisfied with amount of profit you generate'? This questionnaire item is oriented to motivation to join / continue in entrepreneurial profession. Observations are presented in Table - 7

3.29 It is experiential that as regards options offered, male entrepreneurs in age bracket 25 - 40 years are secured at 74% closely followed by their female counterparts at

59%. With maturing age and experience, figure steadily rises to 78% and 74% in case of male entrepreneurs. On the other side, figure rises to 87% and 73% in respect of female entrepreneurs. It is obvious that with dynamics of market economics, entrepreneurs must have shifted their options for continual entrepreneurship skewed in favour of profits ('profit motive'). By introducing fresh ideas and by infusing business with injections of innovative practices, entrepreneurs perhaps feel that think that profit maximisation is a prime motivation in entrepreneurial behaviour. It has been opined that as regards, 'reward procedures in business are fair, 'if I work hard and am productive, I am compensated by profits, 'I have plenty of opportunities for growth / reward, 'those who deserve rewards receive them with fairness', 'business will notice if productivity or work quality declines' and 'are you satisfied with amount of profit you generate', profit motive is locomotive that certifies progress of entrepreneurial discipline.

3.30 As regards option, 'How satisfied were you with overall business benefit package', observations are presented in Table - 8. True passion germinates from package of strong belief. This might end up in embracing satisfaction. This is a direct reference to 'ultimate concern' or 'grit'. When aspirations, objective and targets are met, brain feels satisfied (brain releases dopamine which propels one to feel satisfied). On an average of different age groups, by incorporating facets like 'very satisfied', 'satisfied', 'neutral', 'dissatisfied' and 'very dissatisfied', it is experiential that in age group 25 - 40 years, 76% of male entrepreneurs and 71% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour, respectively. In age group 41 - 55 years, 81% of male entrepreneurs and 79% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour, respectively. In age group 56 - 70 years, 88% of male entrepreneurs and 83% of female entrepreneurs have opined in favour, respectively. Such trends reflect 'biologic reinforcements 'through evolutionary approaches to entrepreneurial choice behaviour. This appears to be indicative trend pertaining to client satisfaction. Neuroscientific studies indicate that orbitofrontal activity and brain parts like, prefrontal cortex, orbitofrontal cortex, ventral pallidum, cingulate cortex, insula, nucleus accumbens, substantia nigari and ventral tegmental area are linked to satisfaction. This aid in choice making for entrepreneur. This thesis is of the firm notion that synthesis of evolutionary and psychological 'Agents' promise generation of plausible models of entrepreneurial choice making.

3.31 Rationality prescribes that entrepreneurs should gather evidences as regards alternatives. They should examine pros and cons. Also, they ought to cautiously consider factors, and as a final point, come to a functional judgement. Options like, were offered to factor in biases and shortcuts pertaining to complicated procedure of choice making. Multifarious neural paths are formed besides being redesigned during evolvement of brain. Do entrepreneurs weigh ‘plusses’ and ‘minuses’ before deciding? Options offered were ‘recurrently’, ‘intermittently’, ‘occasionally’, ‘hardly ever’ and ‘certainly not’. It is experiential that such act promotes deeper thinking. Observations are presented in Table - 9. Above statistics show that an appreciable 75% and above of all entrepreneurs have chosen for options like ‘recurrently’, ‘intermittently’. entrepreneurial brain *analyses* as to what lies between ‘inferential’ data and result expected or anticipated. An associated item in questionnaire was ‘do you decide on your own’? The observations are presented in Table - 10.

3.32 It is experiential that figures between options, ‘entrepreneurs weigh ‘plusses’ and ‘minuses’ before deciding’ and ‘do you decide on your own’ is near - tallying. Statistics show that appreciable 75% and above of all entrepreneurs have chosen for options like ‘recurrently’, ‘intermittently’. There appears to be a correlation between both the concepts. It is a stated truism that *choice* making is a skill; easy for some, difficult for others and not so easy for many. Choice making is tough and brain wrestles between options and alternatives to guide towards ‘choice’. Brain helps entrepreneurs compute ‘expected value’. Brain utilises **dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, orbitofrontal cortex** anterior, **cingulate cortex (ACC)** and **ventromedial prefrontal cortex** for such mechanisms within a specific span of time. It would be safe to assume that limbic system plays a major role in choice making process.

3.33 On issue of ‘Do you take ‘intelligence’ over choices selected’, entrepreneurs are presented in Table 11. ‘Inferential’ data offers interesting results. 88% of male entrepreneurs and 77% of female entrepreneurs in age group 25 - 40 years feel that intelligence can be passed over choices selected. Percentage appreciably rises for both genders as age cohort rises. This merits some discussion. It has been scientifically proved that genetics plays imperative role than environment. Correspondingly, brain function and arrangement relate to intelligence (inter - oriented with each other). A clinical exploration as regards ‘phases’ of choice making divulges ‘intelligence’ as

a search 'Agent' for setting a call in choice dynamics. Entrepreneurs who are intelligent are assumed to be endowed with ability to think and reason. So why this variation in statistics above? Perhaps, answer lies in the fact there exists 'discrepancy of intellect within species or amongst diverse species'. This is based on underpinnings of 'neural basis of intelligence' and 'brain case or brain volume' ('cranial capacity'). This has relationship with choice making. This thesis asserts association between inherent brain events and brain volume.

3.34 An significant option was to gather 'inferential' data as regards 'psychological time' element in choice making. Two inter - oriented questions were asked; one, 'Do you deliberate when psychological time is at premium' and 'Do you plan in adequate psychological time - frame'? This exploration plotted observations and observes that 'psychological time' element has been plotted above 90% by both genders of all age groups in cumulative fashion. Neuroscientific posits subscribes that span of eagerness possibilities replicate choice making in entrepreneurial brain. This incorporates incentive programming, perceptual cataloguing, response assortment and reaction presentation. 'Psychological time' dimension includes appraising substitutions that vary on a set of characteristics, traits and characters. Such a 'Play' centers on extent of possibilities, length of anticipated deferment for appreciating options and 'psychological time' obtainable to grasp an entrepreneurial choice.

3.35 Other items in questionnaire inquired about 'Do you factor in 'ancillary' choice choices', when deciding, do you provision for 'first - look option', is your choice administrated by principles? Answers were 'Recurrently' by almost 79% and above by both respondent groups. Cumulative responses are experiential over 73% for both genders. Ancillary choice choices supplement main process of entrepreneurial choice making. 'Inferential' data obtained from ancillary brain Blood flow analyses, ancillary eyes analyses, ancillary heart beat analyses and ancillary eye movement analyses do support clinically choice mechanism. These are tested in experimental inferences presented in this Chapter. These helps answer supplementary demanding questions in choice designing.

3.36 Other items in questionnaire solicited responses as regards, 'Do you talk about choice making to others' and 'do you often change your mind? The young entrepreneurs, of both genders, in age group 25 - 40 years have responded in affirmative to the tune of 87%. This is obvious as entrepreneurs observe that to frame sustainable choice and ensure mid - course corrections, consulting peers and superiors is 'safe bet'. Entrepreneurs perhaps conjecture that consulting helps revitalise business, generate business model and come out on winning side of inchoice and 'deep' uncertainty. Rigidity spells deceleration. 'Mental flexibility' aids them conceive strategic plots, feedback, independent thinker, analytical mind set and web of synergy. Also, it helps in evolving strategic goals and augment bidding stratagem. Such results corroborate through Electroencephalography (EEG) and Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) tests. As regards, 'do you often change your mind, it can be experiential as open door policy or attitude towards inviting fresh ideas and models. In such a situation, brains are engaged through engagement of amygdala or hypothalamus. These initiate 'flight' or 'fright' response. Research suggests that fresh 'inferential' data help change mind when it pertains articulating to daily choices. This supports new thinking and strong emotional experiences. This thesis subscribes to a quote, 'minds are simply what brains do'.

3.37 'Do you make choices without seeing implications'? This item was striking by low - affirmative responses with each age group marking less than 50% replies. It can be well experiential that entrepreneurs are aware of implications of VUCA and its effects. This menace is a significant 'factor' to be factored in business choice making. On platform of fast changing dynamics and information overload ('Mental Effort'), consequences are pre - designed and forecast. Call is for 'flexibility' and 'adaptability'. Entrepreneurs search for solutions to VUCA matrix. Agile entrepreneurs shall 'definitely be well equipped to be successful'. Solution lies in metamorphosis from straight jacket models to problem solving with concurrent philosophy.

3.38 To inquire about stability aspects of mind, item posed was, 'do you identify 'control of things' and 'do you remain calm during 'sudden' choices? Coincidentally, almost all entrepreneurs of both genders of all age groups have opined for proposition in 63% - 65% range. All depends on how value

information is represented and manner of such representation. Apparently, entrepreneurs are attentive to business choice, there is need for 'sense of control'. This would factor in near - certainty, culmination of pending requirements, sense of understanding as to how things take shape and of forecasting. This is parallel view that brain discreetly tips 'scale', where preferences drive choices in choice making. Major role is played by dorsomedial prefrontal cortex here by identifying preference of others than self. All these are estimated in air of trust, faith and belief. It is experiential that 'sense' would minimise forces of VUCA as 'control' ensures 'calmness' during 'sudden choices'.

3.39 Human brain is Animal Kingdoms' largest, widest and deepest workshop. Brain uses logic and emotion. One significant information sought from entrepreneurs was on 'gut feeling' with a significant question; Do you rely on 'Gut Feelings' when making choices? This thesis is based on presumption that 'gut feeling' is a prime element in entrepreneurial choice mechanism. Neuroscience network of gut feeling supports that **intuition is shaped by past understandings and familiarities plus information from nerve cells**. When brain attempts to 'recollect' or 'retrieve' past information / 'inferential' data, it lays attention on 'gist or theme'. One cannot promulgate heightened ideology simply by one's knowledge or intellect. There has to be equilibrium between 'sentient' and 'static'. Optimal choice is presumed to be arrived through accurate intuition (reference is drawn to concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception). This is considered neuro - based strategy in choice making. 78% of male entrepreneurs and 84% of female entrepreneurs replied that they based choice mechanism on gut feeling. Issue is whether it is rational to trust (conviction) feelings. This is a complicated issue but neuroscience is clearing fog slowly. Different brain regions act, react and interact with various parts to create role played by ventromedial prefrontal cortex in frontal lobe at bottom of cerebral hemispheres. This thesis recommends clinical neuroanatomical insight for prospective research and improved understanding.

3.40 Behaviour comprises of individual and organisational factors. Belief about how minds work is interesting area of exploration. With availability of big 'inferential' data, artificial intelligence, automation software, cutting - edge technology and management sophistication, choice is confronted by high degrees of VUCA regarding prospective developments of dominating compound structures. This requires entrepreneurs to incorporate new ways of thinking due to undercurrents of anxiety and fear. Anxiety is central characteristic of entrepreneurial functioning. 'To what range better 'industrial relations' aid towards choices'? This is a significant question that was adopted towards this inquiry. Entrepreneurs ranked preferences according to 'very operative', 'greatly operative', 'somewhat operative', 'little operative' and 'not operative'. This questionnaire item was marked with high - affirmative responses of more than 92% responses in age bracket of 25 - 40 years. Figure recedes to 76% and 72% in succeeding age brackets. Neurological mechanisms inform web of correlation between choice making and gamut of industrial relations. Entrepreneurs are receptive to 'business citizenship' and 'business voice' as regards conception and competitive strategies to be pursued. This marks strong correlation of choice contrivance that embraces entrepreneurial psychology. This line of argument supports conjecture that choice making is oriented to and based on entrepreneurial functioning. Further research on neuroscientific methodologies, agendas, approaches and apparatuses could provide direct measures to get at fundamentals of this inquiry.

3.41 As regards 'choice dynamics', almost all (97% of both genders in all age groups) have accorded top ranking to options like 'remain confident to make choices', 'know steps in choice making', 'have feel of commitment to crafting a right choices', 'influence choices with 'certainty' factor', 'make choices under 'time' density', 'control level of concentration', 'think openly and keep pertinent factors', 'narrow down list of options', 'determine assortment of alternative', 'handle quantitative 'inferential' data to classify preferences, difficulties and explanations', 'obtain information', 'weigh consequences of each option', 'evaluate business choice problem situation', 'choose best alternative', 'secure resources', 'make choice and persevere with engagements' and 'refrain from postponing choice making'. A study by Satpathy and Gankar (2016) is reproduced that

lends credence; “New brain imaging technologies have motivated neuroentrepreneurial studies of internal order of mind. We are only at beginning of an enterprise. Its promise suggests a fundamental change in how we think, observe and model choice in context. Brain absorbs information, recognises and frames problematic situations concerning appropriate responses. choice making in neuromanagement is based on complexly interlinked imaging technologies with links to bandwidth of human choice. entrepreneur often fail to design ‘rational’ choices. Processes by which entrepreneurs reach choices embody conflicting tenets. Question is how entrepreneur makes choices. How are choices carried out in brain? Interest is on assumptions, beliefs, habits and tactics that entrepreneur uses to make choices. How do parts of brain govern choice-making, coordinate, face obscurity and engage in strategic simplification while deciding? What happens in brain or is activated? Is study of choice-making geometry via neuromanagement relevant? What are the limits? How does previous experience alter behaviour? There are unsolved problems in entrepreneurial) cognition. What are the general implications? entrepreneurial cognition plays a role. Sensing is as an significant aspect and there is evidence of how evolutionary patterns are shaped by beliefs and attention allocation. How does entrepreneur decide in state of VUCA (‘deep’ uncertainty, Vulnerability, Complexity and Ambiguity? In this, neuromanagement seeks to explain choice-making, ability to process alternatives and choose optimal course of action. It studies how management behaviour shape understanding of brain and guide coherent brain geometry towards choice-making? This attempts to explore above phenomenon to put forward a model for neuro-management choice, in which interaction are addressed through measurements of brain activity. Attempt is to model choice-making linking neuro-management of choice behaviour. This provides conceptual geometry for conducting neuro entrepreneurial) research at intersection of neuro entrepreneurial) science, raises a few fundamental issues and offer solution through measurements of brain activity at management levels of exploration”.

3.42 Is VUCA the expiration of Strategy and Leadership? VUCA and choice making in arena of business and entrepreneurial affairs does have a link with stress. It is generally stressful when one does not know forecast of events or outcome. It commands signal to brain to kick start beginning of cognitive processing. Inquiry was whether entrepreneurs experienced stress consequences. Observation is that young and middle age group suffered most with over 86% of them reporting ‘Yes’ while elder age group

showed some degree of resilience with average of 63%. Correspondingly, similar number or percentages of entrepreneurs have reported that while deciding, they were. Entrepreneurs have reported factors that create choice oriented stress. Entrepreneurs have cited management, regular fluctuations and amplified assignment as ‘primary’ causes. Secondary causes are, high degree of ‘deep’ uncertainty, lack of ‘inferential’ data challenging demands. Tertiary causes include, goals, long operational hours and commuting time. It can be argued that entrepreneurial brains are adequately wired to safeguard from menace of VUCA. Responsiveness of entrepreneurial positivity to negativity ratio is imperative. Elder age bracket has shown higher degree of resilience and elasticity because they are calm, collected and encourages confidence. This may primarily be due to age and experience factor. Amygdala helps to harden arteries and handle increased Blood flow for a fight or flight response. Taking a cue, to invoke brain’s higher capacity, entrepreneurs can deploy attention to alter brain, cultivate mind set and generate possibilities for tackling VUCA. Future research is suggested through use of **‘Opportunity Readiness Level (ORL)’ model that promotes ways and means for entrepreneur and, takes care of ‘deep’ uncertainty framework.**

3.43 Based on behavioural methodology, ‘STAR (‘Situation, Target, Action and Result ‘Method’ of interview was adopted in interview phase by presenting a challenging situation (also scripted for the eye movements tests), intrinsic motivation tasks of the entrepreneur, actions and alternatives adopted by the entrepreneur and outcome of entrepreneurial actions or reactions. Responses from interviews have been factored where it was felt quantitative gaps could be filled in or some generalisation could be factored in to lend support to logical arguments. Some inquiries investigated during interviews were;

- How much ‘time’ do you give in choice making?
- How confident are you in correct choice making?
- What pointers indicate that choice making confidence has increased?
- What habits influence choice making?
- What are the ‘risks’ associated in choice making?
- Do you sometimes postpone choice making?
- Do values and principles play a role in choice making?

- Do choice making align with your priorities?
- Do you guestimate consequences of choice making?
- Do you change your mind after creating choice making?
- What complexities are intricate in choice making?
- How do you deal with engagements in choice making?
- What steps you anticipate as regards risks in choice making?

Conclusion

3.44 *Entrepreneurial sciences have witnessed spread at dawn of 21st Century. Neuroscience conglomerates disciplines to study entrepreneurial choice. Value representations describe choice behaviour that challenges empirical results. Each revision unswervingly goads differing evidence. This is reflection of mix of volatility, ‘deep’ uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity (VUCA). One appropriate issue is, does VUCA result in lower choice making enactment? Prima facie, reply seems to be ‘not necessarily’. It is experiential that information factoring is appropriate when entrepreneurs are processing high quality ‘inferential’ data that is seemingly accurate, well - timed, comprehensive and contributes towards choice making. Although practical circumstances do not parallel to this ‘ideal’ situation, this places or positions entrepreneur on a ‘mode of calculated caution’. It is vital to understand intricacy of entrepreneurial in exploring how brain and eyes choose appropriate responses. In order to explicate neural basis of choice making, capacity to process alternatives and choose optimal course, research combines methods to figure models for answering choice questions. Brain and eyes structure imaging technologies stimulate bandwidth of choices.*

Table: 1

GROUPING OF RESPONDENTS

M	Group 1: Male subjects	(Aged : 25 - 40 years)	Total: 32	}	Total: 80
	Group 2: Male subjects	(Aged : 41 - 55 years)	Total: 29		
	Group 3: Male subjects	(Aged : 56 - 70 years)	Total: 19	}	
	Group 4: Female subjects	(Aged : 25 - 40 years)	Total: 31		

Group 5: Female subjects (Aged : 41 - 55 years)	Total: 30	Total: 70 F
Group 6: Female subjects (Aged : 56 - 70 years)	Total: 09	

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table: 2
OPENNESS TO EXPERIENCE

Factor	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
Multifaceted	81 %	80 %	76 %	78 %	81 %	74 %
Resourceful	91 %	90 %	87 %	88 %	92 %	86 %
Deep	79 %	81 %	77 %	76 %	84 %	73 %
Reflective	76 %	86 %	84 %	74 %	85 %	88 %
Knowledgeable	76 %	79 %	72 %	79 %	77 %	77 %
Rational	61 %	68 %	64 %	64 %	65 %	65 %
Unproductive	12 %	10 %	09 %	19 %	08 %	08 %
Unchallenging	34 %	31 %	27 %	29 %	32 %	26 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female =

70)

Table: 3
CHOICE TO JOIN BUSINESS

Factor	Male Agree	Male Disagree	Female Agree	Female Disagree
Training for business skills	94 %	06 %	91 %	09 %
Long run profit maximisation	78 %	22 %	59 %	41 %
Corporate social responsibility	2 %	78 %	8 %	32 %
Service to Society	6 %	34 %	37 %	53 %
Maximisation of sales	94 %	06 %	79 %	21 %
Improve market shares	91 %	09 %	56 %	34 %
Maximisation of shareholder value	37 %	63 %	53 %	47 %
Opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work	79 %	21 %	55 %	45 %
have reasonable chance of promotion	52 %	48 %	45 %	55 %
Company is expected to grow and my career path is	74 %	26 %	57 %	43 %
come to work purely to get business done.	96 %	04 %	37 %	63 %
My loyalty is defined and I feel part of	35 %	65 %	34 %	66 %

team in business.				
feel business reciprocates effort put.	77 %	23 %	59 %	11 %
am motivated to contribute 100% to	96 %	04 %	89 %	1 %
Business for future benefits.				
will work for business indefinitely.	78 %	21 %	79 %	21 %
work to achieve goals of business.	98 %	02 %	94 %	06 %
Being able to change things,	91 %	09 %	88 %	12 %
Having a say about the way I do things	95 %	05 %	91 %	09 %
Chance to learn new things in my work.	89 %	11 %	92 %	08 %
Chance to use my abilities within	94 %	06 %	87 %	13 %
Chance of achieving something worthwhile.	93 %	07 %	91 %	09 %
work for profit and expect	99 %	01 %	97 %	03 %
Business is a high - concert occupation.	94 %	06 %	92 %	08%
Choice to remain involved (so) influential?	93 %	07 %	91 %	09 %
Business harnesses your potential.	79 %	21 %	76 %	24 %
Carrot and stick' approach of motivating	57 %	43 %	58 %	42 %
works in business.				
Managers in business evaluate different	59 %	41 %	71 %	29 %
practices of management.				
Above factors, reflect desired values	77 %	23 %	79 %	21 %
and virtues in business				
Above factors contribute	89 %	11 %	88 %	12 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table: 4

OVERALL PROFICIENCY ABOUT CHOICE MAKING

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	51 %	49 %
41 - 55 Years	68 %	54 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	73 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No: 5

OVERALL PERSON - BUSINESS FIT

Age Group	Male	Female
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25 - 40 Years	71 %	69 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	84 %
56 - 70 Years	97 %	93 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 6

WORK - PERSONAL INTERFACE

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	71 %	69 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	84 %
56 - 70 Years	97 %	93 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 7

PROFIT AND WAGES

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	74 %	59 %
41 - 55 Years	78 %	74 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	73 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 8

Benefit Satisfaction Index

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	76 %	71 %
41 - 55 Years	81 %	79 %
56 - 70 Years	88 %	83 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 9

Satisfaction Index

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	79 %	76 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	77 %
56 - 70 Years	89 %	87 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 10

Deciding on Own

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	78 %	77 %
41 - 55 Years	86 %	75 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	85 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 11

'Intelligence' Over Choices Selected'

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	88 %	77 %
41 - 55 Years	89 %	78 %
56 - 70 Years	90 %	80 %

CHAPTER - IV

NEURO - CENTRIC EXPERIMENTS

Prologue

4.1 Charting neuronal (relating to neuron or neurons) - directed rational human (multicellular eukaryote) centric choice corridor, **has countersigned unconceivable headway since turn of 21st Century.** Together with cognito-management, neuromanagement, has made incomparable sensitivities into an anthropological reason. Crannies in neuronal - focused changeovers marshal behavioural investigation inclines to epicenter on competencies to 'perceptive mosaic' with focus on neuro - corridors. Entrepreneurs' attempt to arrive at optimal rational choice till 'response threshold' is stretched. Cognito - management examines this 'Charting' by means of 'Cognito -

Premeditated Monikers' to probe how brain performs in journey of higher cognitive functions. There is a need to identify 'neuro - based drivers' that craft an 'entrepreneurial centric choice mosaic'. This thesis attempts at addressing how neuro apparatuses ('hematological drivers') explore entrepreneurial choice making. Attempt comprises porticoes of biological basis of rational choices exploring significant role of 'neuronics' in prototyping entrepreneurial choice corridor. Objective is to exhibit theoretic and empirical mosaics in 'neuro - corridors' of entrepreneurial 'choice mosaic'. Methodology includes emphasis on hematological drivers that entrepreneur endeavors to address. Research communication discusses findings and future directions to guide hematological neuro science in choice dynamics. Research offers 'Anchorage' of 'hematoneuro - drivers' and 'rational choice corridor schemes' to appreciate how entrepreneurs make rational choices.

Introduction

4.2 Human choices define human beings. How to introduce a 'human centric choice'? In fact, what is a human centric choice? Is it a beginning or end to a specific contemplation? Do they have a biological basis? Do these have bio - philosophical computational connotation? Are they regulated by some genetic 'drivers' like human sense organs? Such an archetype is concerned with perception underpinning a driver's choice. If yes, then who serves as a 'driver'? Entrepreneurial replicas are concomitant with technical novelty. Voyaging through 'bustamination' ('business' and 'contamination'), entrepreneurial community is transversely at cater - cornered with neuroscience and entrepreneurship transmitting a perceptive organised linkage ('Chess Board Matrix'). Key regeneration originates with rational information as 'control'. Final question is; are these networked neurologically ('neural roulette')? This amounts to '*rationality*'. Do these represent sweeping renaissance of primary concerns in understanding biology of choice apparatus?

4.3 Neuro - centric choice modeling aligns to higher cerebral order towards amplification of perceptive and neural foundation of choice crafting. Competency to manner manifold changeovers, select optimum corridor of act, explicitly in management framework are the pillars in choice dynamics. Some facets include; cognitive processes, choices under risk and seismicity of uncertainty (unknown

nature of future) and operational studies of fMRI, EEG, fNIRS and eye tracking. **Charting** neuronal - directed choice corridor, alongside cognito - management, has made unrivaled sensitivities into neuronal - focused changeovers. These rationalize behavioural investigation on 'actors', 'representations' and 'maxims' with 'cognito - premeditated monikers'. Brain's wiring diagram calls to identify 'drivers' (frontal cortex, orbit frontal cortex, anterior cingulate cortex and ventromedial prefrontal cortex) that craft 'entrepreneurial choice mosaic'. Attention is on 'Bereitschaftspotential' (German) meaning 'readiness potential'. This is a 'noise' that calls for 'entrepreneurial choices'. There is an imperative need to embracing neural mechanisms of perceptual practices fundamental to a state of 'Homo - Neuropsychoeconomicus' that buttons 'Homo Economicus'. This is by replicating how entrepreneurs are influenced by psychological, genetic and cognitive conformations. Of interest is how 'entrepreneurial' brain captivates to acclimate and improve 'entrepreneurial' choice mechanism in a state of complexity and seismicity of uncertainty. With advent of crossbreed choice prototypes, questions that merit consideration are; Do entrepreneurs actually arrive at centric choice? How do they handpick an action in a state of unbounded 'scrolling' and interminable 'disorders'? What 'neuro signatures' relate to receptive inferences? Will neuro entrepreneurial dynamics supplant orthodox cognitive alignments associating neuro - integrated mosaic to reconnoiter neuro - corridors in 'entrepreneurial' choices? As a trade - off between accuracy and explain - ability, experiments based on methods and approaches from hematological and ocular data are offered in this thesis. This research represents a neuro entrepreneurial model system to reflect upon 'entrepreneurial' choices signifying interdisciplinary turf of neuro - corridors in choice complexities.

Scope and Aim

4.4 Is there a perceived problem with entrepreneurial choice making? Investigation reveals that neurons receive signals, perform appreciation and transduction to grow and die in randomly determined process corridors. Impression that choices are taken through rational or logical thought process are questioned by experimentations that analyse estimation during choice manufacture. Rationality is indistinct with randomly determined process complexity. Reference is drawn to cells that impact

centric choices, genes that stimulate alteration of functional values with respect to variation in signals of origin, circumstances that provision or negate results that aid understanding of how hematological and ocular configurations influence choice making. Are entrepreneurs being threatened by a ‘centric choice panic’? Entrepreneurs assume that choices they take are rational, optimal and based on best accessible data. They assume that they are in total appreciation of choice behaviours. Such patterns are now skimmed under lens of hematological and ocular prisms.

4.5 Scope of this thesis encompasses how neuro apparatuses (hematological and ocular) explore entrepreneurial choice crafting. Attempt comprises corridor of neuro - hematological roots of preferences scrutinizing considerable role of ‘hematological and ocular neurotics’ in prototyping entrepreneurial choice corridor. Cursors are on dynamic ‘drivers’ and ‘elements’ to exhibit theoretic and empirical mosaics in ‘neuro - corridors’ of choice corridor. Methodology includes hematological and ocular - based observations with results displaying pointers for adlibbed counterfactual imitation in dominion of high - level cognitive. Major finding is that entrepreneur endeavours to address neuro - mosaic using ‘neuro - drivers’. Research communication discusses findings and future directions to guide hematological neuro science in choice corridors.

Drivers

4.6 Entrepreneurial centric choices take place in energetic corridors. Behaviour is embraced of pronouncements made from second to flash. There have been efforts to explicate properties of blood and ocular parameters on fundamentally substantive reasoning and behaviour. Two streams of elucidations surface. First, is a package of ‘Constraint Models’ (outcome of each centric choice controlled by minimum and maximum range of limits) backed up by psychological connotations. Second, is the package of signal models backed up by Economics and Biology. Biological micro - practicalities of centric choice crafting has conventionally received substantial gentility from Loewenstein (2001), Slovic (2002), Tversky and Kahneman (1975), Bechara (2004), Clark (2003), Damasio (1996), Lhermitte (1986), Shallice and Burgess (1991), Ernst (2004), Paulus (2003), Rogers (1999), Clark (2004), Glimcher (2002), Gold and Shadlen (2001), Platt and Glimcher (1999). Preliminary incursions originate from

Bechara (2004) and Damasio (1996). These unique incursions brand brain areas indispensable for adaptive choice crafting and provisioned abstract representations of critical facets of entrepreneurial choice hewing (Damasio; 1996). Common issue to cast attention is, how is data encrypted by neurons? Such data needs to be collected, cleaned, managed, through an assortment of statistical methods, filtered through content analysis methods and scientific reporting for reconnoitering contiguous questions. Choice crafting is contingent on three progressively discrete arrays of progressions; one, valuation plus creation of predilections amongst conceivable possibilities, two, assortment plus implementation of an act, and three, understanding or assessment of consequence. One possible option here is to 'hammer out' compound proxies into dual possibilities.

4.7 Entrepreneurs make centric choices based on patterns unorthodox from traditional rationality and data dispensation models. Business centric choices need to approve 'real time' of changes probable to ensue for a 'gap' between past considerations and imminent transformation. Neuroscientific results suggest that business centric choices surface on preference ordering; what action to take, what characteristics of alternatives make choice difficult, how inconsistencies create prospects and challenges in behavioural choice making etc. Cells receive signals, perform recognition and transduction to grow and die in randomly determined process corridors. On an embryonic plane, neuro procedures include apparatuses connected to Electroencephalograph (EEG), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Magneto encephalography (MEG), Computerized Tomography (CT), functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), Skin Conductance and Positron Emission Tomography (PET), to list a few. These propose; neuroimaging of brain, neurophysiologic techniques, examination of nerve cells, neuropsychological techniques via. Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), Eye Tracking and Electroencephalography. Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) quantity plasma stream and Single Neuron Measurement (SNM) quantity reactions of solitary neurons. Each have dissimilar paybacks and approximate outlays associated. Magneto Encephalography (MEG) records magnetic instincts shaped by electrical fluxes in brain using magnetometers. Electrocardiography (ECG) records electrical activity of heart by means of electrodes. Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) habits continual, low current conveyed to area of interest via electrodes. Electroencephalography (EEG) records electrical activity of brain. Positron Emission

Tomography (PET) yields 3-D carbon copy of functional progressions. Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) arouses minor regions of brain. Eye Tracking Measures point of gaze (where subject is looking) or motion of eye relative to head. Electrodermal Activity (EDA) or, Skin Conductance, Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), Electro Dermal Response (EDR), Psych Galvanic Reflex (PGR), Skin Conductance Response (SCR), Skin Conductance Level (SCL), Reasons Continuous Variation in electrical characteristics of skin. Brain Mapping centered on charting of (biological) quantities or spatial images occasioning in maps, Blood - Oxygen - Level Dependent Contrast Imaging (BOLD) spots 'Zones of Brain' originate to be active at any given time. Fresh neuro - based hematological (especially *complete blood count*) and ocular investigations promise assistances to understand entrepreneurial centric choice making at behavioural and neural echelons.

4.8 Is there a problem with entrepreneurial centric choice making? Impression that choices are taken through rational or logical thought process have been exposed to questioning by experiments that analyse estimation during choice making. Reference is drawn to cells that impact choices, genetic factors they activate to discriminate based on multiple indications of origin, circumstances that support or negate findings that aid understanding of how hematological and ocular configurations influence centric choice making. Cellular - based choice making infer from 'noisy signals' and anticipated state of business choice setting. They weigh costs and benefits of each potential response. Third, cells decide in presence of potentially competitive makers. These choices are separate. Rationality is unclear with randomly determined process complexity. Are business actors being threatened by 'choice alarm'? Entrepreneurs assume that choices they take are rational, optimal and based on best accessible data. They postulate that they are in total appreciation of choice behaviours. Such propositions are now scanned under lens of cellular and hematological prisms. Issues like how choice processes transgress in brain corridors, how brain considers sources of data and what intrinsic processes embody conflicting values have been explored to design 'rational' choices. This thesis attempts at address molecular research to explore data - driven entrepreneurial choice making.

Experiments

4.9 This research communication does not reason to account inferences that are comprehensively and everlastingly germane, nor beached resolutely in theoretic or pragmatic exploration. It submits to abstract conundrum (Meta - Explicandum). It does not report distinct, well - defined concern, abruptly fixated on specific disciplinary theme. As an alternative, it accounts on investigative explorations, whose amalgamating strand is message of real - world difficulties. The non - concrete interpretations are grounded on crevices or insufficiencies in methodical norm which can be articulated as queries to trail where clarifications may lie (Satpathy, J. et. al.; 2018).

Respondent Population

4.10 Thesis presents results of an experiment in exploring choice making behaviour via. hematological perceptions. Administering a Situation Reaction Test (*convincing circumstances of concrete nature were fashioned*), in empirical facet, series of clinical explanations were administered to 150 subjects (n = 150; n = 80 Male subjects and n = 70 Female subjects). Behaviour of each subject (primary data) was spotted constantly over development of interposition ('Continuous Assessment'). Behavioural propensities (whole systems approach), if any, were chronicled ('Baseline Assessment'). Since comportment was assessed intermittently, subject hodgepodge recommended to estimate vicissitudes in conduct over phase through instruments of dynamic contraptions. Such an assortment was favoured as it was seemingly mutable and could mark inconsistencies in reaction to intervention paraphernalia.

Equipment Used

4.11 Complete Blood Count Analyzer equipment was used for haematological tests. This gadget helped sort out marks of complete blood count (CBC) tests and recognized what various statistics reported with CBC mean. This was primarily to discern where subject is observing, ascertain indicator, responsiveness and attentiveness of subject. This permitted distinctive acumens into entrepreneurial deportment and what data to comprehend effects on behaviour and choice making.

Findings

4.12 The first set of data as offered in Table - 1 relates to 43 (out of 80) male subjects. It is pragmatic that in a state of ordinariness, hematological indices are normal within normal assortment. However, in a traumatic circumstance, there is an observed severe drip in indices like Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post - Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Low Density Lipo Protein, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, S Bilirubin Total, S Bilirubin Direct, S Bilirubin Indirect, Aspartate Trans Amines (AST), Alanine Trans Amines (ALT), Creatine Phosphate K, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. However, minor drips have been pragmatic in parameters like Creatine, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. Question is whether young male entrepreneurs have lack of 'perfect' resilience to absorb shocks (due to varying dependences, extemporaneity and adaptive behaviour) in business. In such a case, entrepreneurs feel a state of tiredness, weariness, exhaustion, overtiredness, lethargy, sluggishness, lassitude, debility, enervation, listlessness, prostration, lack of energy, lack of vitality, tired, wear out, drain, make weary, weary, wash out, tax, overtax, overtire, jade, make sleepy. May be, the race against time to achieve targets leads to stress symptoms that affect body, thoughts, feelings and behaviour. This is inferred in the broad - spectrum scrutiny. This calls for contemplation as regards best practices in intertwined as aspects of sustainability in business, modeling adaptive behaviour and pro - active transformational analysis leading towards a 'delta - change'.

Table - 1

MALE SUBJECTS (Aged: 25 - 40 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
N = 43, Total Male = 80, Total Subjects = 150				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN DURING STRESS
	NO STRESS	STRESSED		
Blood Glucose Fasting	70 mg /dl	61 mg /dl	60 - 100	Severe Drip
Blood Glucose Post -	110 mg / dl	90 mg / dl	< 140	Severe Drip

Prandial				
Blood Glucose Random	179 mg / dl	159 mg / dl	< 200	Severe Drip
Urea	27 mg /dl	21 mg /dl	15 – 40	Severe Drip
Creatine	0.6 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Severe Drip
Sodium	141 mEq / L	129 mEq / L	130 - 145	Severe Drip
Potassium	3.9 mEq / L	3.2 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Severe Drip
Lipid T – Cholesterol	138 mg / dl	108 mg / dl	< 200	Severe Drip
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	78 mg / dl	58 mg / dl	60 - 150	Severe Drip
Low Density Lipo Protein	79 mg / dl	59 mg / dl	60 - 130	Severe Drip
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	31 mg / dl	17 mg / dl	00 – 36	Severe Drip
High Density Lipo Protein	56 mg / dl	36 mg / dl	40 – 60	Severe Drip
S Bilirubin Total	0.9 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Severe Drip
S Bilirubin Direct	0.12 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	< 0.3	Severe Drip
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Severe Drip
Aspartate Trans Amines	24 IU / L	16 IU / L	15 – 40	Severe Drip
Alanine Trans Amines	23 IU / L	16 IU / L	15 – 40	Severe Drip
Creatine Phosphate K	21	4	M : 6 - 37	Severe Drip
CPK - Muscular / Brain	14	12	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drip
T - Protein	6.3 g / dl	5.3 g / dl	6 – 8	Minor Drip
Albumin	3.9 g / dl	3.4 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drip
Globulin	1.9 g / dl	1.8 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drip

4.13 The second set of data (Table - 2), offered below, relates to 18 (out of 80) male subjects. It is pragmatic that in a state of normality, hematological indices are normal within normal assortment. However, in atraumatic circumstance, there is an observed severe drip, as well as minor drip, in indices like Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post - Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Low Density Lipo Protein, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, S Bilirubin Total, S Bilirubin Direct, S Bilirubin Indirect, Aspartate Trans Amines (AST), Alanine Trans Amines (ALT), Creatine Phosphate K, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. Question

is whether middle - aged male entrepreneurs have mixed - resilience to absorb shocks in business? It is assumed that entrepreneurs have put in some appreciable quantum of business experience. They are by now well - versed with dynamics of business in a complex but informative world. Middle - aged entrepreneurs have nearly consolidated their business and entrepreneurial activities. May be, earning profits is no longer a macro - aim but consolidation of business in the roller coaster series of profit - loss enables them to absorb a drip in glucose levels and associated effects. Hence, minor drip, in - indices. This is inferred in the broad - spectrum scrutiny.

Table - 2

MALE SUBJECTS (Aged: 40 - 55 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
N = 18, Total Male = 80 Total Subjects = 150				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMA L VALUE	OBSNDURIN G STRESS
	NO STRESS	STRESSE D		
Blood Glucose Fasting	71 mg / dl	70 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Post – Prandial	87 mg / dl	85 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Random	113 mg / dl	111 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Urea	19 mg / dl	14 mg / dl	15 – 40	Minor Drip
Creatine	0.6 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Severe Drip
Sodium	141 mEq / L	131 mEq /	130 - 145	Severe Drip
Potassium	3.7 mEq / L	3.4 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Severe Drip
Lipid T – Cholesterol	119 mg / dl	114 mg / dl	< 200	Severe Drip
Lipid Tri – Glyceride	71 mg / dl	64 mg / dl	60 - 150	Severe Drip
Low Density Lipo Protein	79 mg / dl	69 mg / dl	60 - 130	Severe Drip
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	24 mg / dl	21 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drip
High Density Lipo Protein	48 mg / dl	45 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Total	0.8 mg / dl	0.5 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Direct	0.13 mg / dl	0.10 mg / dl	< 0.3	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Severe Drip

Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	22 IU / L	19 IU / L	15 – 40	Minor Drip
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	19 IU / L	17 IU / L	15 – 40	Minor Drip
Creatine Phosphate K	21	18	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drip
CPK - Muscular / Brain	26	13	F : 5 - 27	Severe Drip
T - Protein	6.7 g / dl	6.2 g / dl	6 – 8	Minor Drip
Albumin	3.6 g / dl	3.4 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drip
Globulin	1.2 g / dl	1.0 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drip

4.14 The third set of data (Table - 3), offered below, relates to 19 (out of 80) male subjects. It is pragmatic that in -state of normality, hematological indices are normal within - near - normal assortment. However, in - traumatic circumstances, there is a severe drip, as well as minor drip, in indices like Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post - Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Low Density Lipo Protein, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, S Bilirubin Total, S Bilirubin Direct, S Bilirubin Indirect, Aspartate Trans Amines (AST), Alanine Trans Amines (ALT), Creatine Phosphate K, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. It is pragmatic that majority of indices have registered minor drips. Question is whether aged male entrepreneurs have heavy resilience to absorb shocks in business. In such a scenario, either entrepreneur is cruising in his business after a long passé of seasoned business acumen, or has adopted his off - springs to business activities. Wealth, in any form, accumulation must have been ensured or assured by now. Business shocks are no longer a deterring factor. Ethical framework becomes no longer a burdensome constraint. Emphasis is on ethical integrity of entrepreneurial actors. A spiritual sense of satiety has perhaps been achieved. This is inferred in broad-spectrum scrutiny.

Table - 3

<p><u>MALE SUBJECTS (Aged: 55 - 70 Years)</u> (ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS) N = 19, Total Male = 80 Total Subjects = 150</p>			
INDEX	RESULT	NORMA	OBSERVATIO

			LVALUE	N
	NO STRESS	STRESSE D		
Blood Glucose Fasting	74 mg / dl	73 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Post - Prandial	113 mg / dl	111 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Random	126 mg / dl	123 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Urea	25 mg / dl	22 mg / dl	15 – 40	Minor Drip
Creatine	0.9 mg / dl	0.7 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Minor Drip
Sodium	137 mEq / L	131 mEq / L	130 - 145	Minor Drip
Potassium	3.9 mEq / L	3.1 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Minor Drip
Lipid T - Cholesterol	124 mg / dl	120 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	76 mg / dl	71 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drip
Low Density Lipo Protein	79 mg / dl	73 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drip
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	14 mg / dl	12 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drip
High Density Lipo Protein	43 mg / dl	41 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Total	0.5 mg / dl	0.6 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Rise
S Bilirubin Direct	0.1 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	< 0.3	Minor Rise
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.5 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Minor Rise
Aspartate Trans Amines	21 IU / L	18 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Alanine Trans Amines	23 IU / L	21 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Creatine Phosphate K	8	06	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drip
CPK - Muscular / Brain	11	08	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drip
T - Protein	6.4 g / dl	6.1 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drip
Albumin	3.7 g / dl	3.1 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drip
Globulin	1.7 g / dl	1.3 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drip

4.15 The fourth set of data (Table - 4), offered below, relates to 31 (out of 70) female

subjects. It is pragmatic that in state of normality, hematological indices are normal within normal assortment. However, in traumatic circumstances, there is marked severe drip, as well as minor drip, in indices like Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post - Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Low Density Lipo Protein, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, S Bilirubin Total, S Bilirubin Direct, S Bilirubin Indirect, Aspartate Trans Amines (AST), Alanine Trans Amines (ALT), Creatine Phosphate K, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. It is pragmatic that majority of - indices – register- mixed drips. Question is whether - young female entrepreneurs have mixed resilience to absorb shocks in business. It is experiential that majority of - indices have registered mixed drips. In contrast to their male counterparts, females have registered mixed fluctuations indicating good levels of tolerance. It can be safely assumed that they can tolerate (or survive within) a certain range of a particular factor, but cannot survive if there is too much or too little of the factor. They perhaps subscribe to - allowable departure from specification or standard, considered non - harmful to functioning of part, process, or product over its life cycle. They have ability to withstand high levels of stress or overloading without suffering irreparable harm. This is inferred in broad-spectrum scrutiny. Sense of purpose is exhibited by the respondents here.

Table - 4

<u>FEMALE SUBJECTS (Aged: 25 - 40 Years)</u>				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
N = 31, Total Female = 70, Total Subjects = 150				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMA L VALUE	OBSN DURING STRESS
	NO STRESS	STRESSED		
Blood Glucose Fasting	76 mg / dl	56 mg / dl	60 - 100	Severe Drip
Blood Glucose Post - Prandial	112 mg / dl	98 mg / dl	< 140	Severe Drip
Blood Glucose Random	124 mg / dl	100 mg / dl	< 200	Severe Drip
Urea	22 mg / dl	12 mg / dl	15 – 40	Severe Drip
Creatine	0.4 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Severe Drip
Sodium	121 mEq / L	101 mEq / L	130 - 145	Severe Drip

Potassium	3.1 mEq / L	2.1 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Severe Drip
Lipid T - Cholesterol	102 mg / dl	92 mg / dl	< 200	Severe Drip
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	62 mg / dl	61 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drip
Low Density Lipo Protein	76 mg / dl	72 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drip
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	12 mg / dl	11 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drip
High Density Lipo Protein	43 mg / dl	37 mg / dl	40 - 60	Severe Drip
S Bilirubin Total	0.7 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Severe Drip
S Bilirubin Direct	0.2 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	< 0.3	No Drip
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	No Drip
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	22 IU / L	18 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	21 IU / L	19 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Creatine Phosphate K	7	4	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drip
CPK - Muscular / Brain	9	6	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drip
T - Protein	7 g / dl	6 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drip
Albumin	3.1 g / dl	30 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drip
Globulin	1.6 g / dl	1.4 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drip

4.16 The fifth set of data (Table - 5), offered below, relates to 21 (out of 70) female subjects. It is pragmatic that in a state of normality, hematological indices are normal within the normal assortment. However, in a traumatic circumstance, there is severe drip, as well as minor drip, in the indices like Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post -Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T -Cholesterol, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Low Density Lipo Protein, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, S Bilirubin Total, S Bilirubin Direct, S Bilirubin Indirect, Aspartate Trans Amines (AST), Alanine Trans Amines (ALT), Creatine Phosphate K, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. It is pragmatic that majority of - indices have registered minor drips. Question is whether - middle - aged female entrepreneurs have heavy (surprising results!) resilience to absorb shocks in business. It is experiential that majority of - indices have registered mixed drips. In contrast to their male counterparts, females have registered mixed fluctuations indicating good

levels of tolerance. It can be safely assumed that they can tolerate (or survive within) a certain range of a particular factor, but cannot survive if there is too much or too little of the factor. They perhaps subscribe to an allowable departure from a specification or standard, considered non-harmful to the functioning of a part, process, or product over its life cycle. They have - ability to withstand high levels of stress or overloading without suffering irreparable harm. This is inferred in - broad-spectrum scrutiny.

Table - 5

<u>FEMALE SUBJECTS (Aged: 40 - 55 Years)</u> (ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS) N = 21, Total Female = 70 , Total Subjects = 150				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN DURING STRESS
	NO STRESS	STRESSED		
Blood Glucose Fasting	00 mg / dl	80 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Post - Prandial	59 mg / dl	56 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Random	98 mg / dl	94 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Urea	16 mg / dl	11 mg / dl	15 – 40	Minor Drip
Creatine	0.6 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Minor Drip
Sodium	121 mEq / L	110 mEq / L	130 - 145	Minor Drip
Potassium	3.2 mEq / L	2.2 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Minor Drip
Lipid T - Cholesterol	79 mg / dl	72 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	71 mg / dl	68 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drip
Low Density Lipo Protein	65 mg / dl	62 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drip
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	12 mg / dl	09 mg / dl	00 – 36	Minor Drip
High Density Lipo Protein	41 mg / dl	38 mg / dl	40 – 60	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Total	0.4 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Direct	0.1 mg / dl	0.1 mg / dl	< 0.3	No Change
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Minor Drip
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	22 IU / L	19 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip

Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	21 IU / L	18 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Creatine Phosphate K	7	5	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drip
CPK - Muscular / Brain	9	7	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drip
T - Protein	7 g / dl	5 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drip
Albumin	3.6 g / dl	3.2 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drip
Globulin	1.9 g / dl	1.7 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drip

4.17 The sixth set of data (Table - 6), offered below, relates to 18 (out of 70) female subjects. It is pragmatic that in a state of normality, hematological indices are normal within the normal assortment. However, in a traumatic circumstance, there is a severe drip, as well as minor drip, in the indices like Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post – Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Low Density Lipo Protein, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, Bilirubin Total, S Bilirubin Direct, S Bilirubin Indirect, Aspartate Trans Amines, Alanine Trans Amines , Creatine Phosphate K, CPK - Muscular / Brain, T - Protein, Albumin and Globulin. It is pragmatic that majority of the indices have registered minor drips. Question is whether - aged female entrepreneurs have heavy (surprising results!) resilience to absorb shocks in business. It is experiential that majority of indices have registered mixed drips. In contrast to their male counterparts, females have registered mixed fluctuations indicating good levels of tolerance. It can be safely assumed that they can tolerate (or survive within) a certain range of particular factor, but cannot survive if there is too much or too little of the factor. They perhaps subscribe to an allowable departure from a specification or standard, considered non-harmful to functioning of a part, process, or product over its life cycle. They have ability to withstand high levels of stress or overloading without suffering irreparable harm. This is inferred in the broad-spectrum scrutiny.

Table - 6

FEMALE SUBJECTS (Aged: 55 - 70 Years) (ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS) N = 18, Total Female = 70 Total Subjects = 150			
INDEX	RESULT	NORMAL	OBSN

	STRESSE D	NO STRESS	VALUE	DURING STRESS
Blood Glucose Fasting	47 mg / dl	46 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Post - Prandial	78 mg / dl	76 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drip
Blood Glucose Random	110 mg / dl	100 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Urea	14 mg / dl	13 mg / dl	15 – 40	Minor Drip
Creatine	0.4 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Minor Drip
Sodium	115 mEq / L	113 mEq / L	130 - 145	Minor Drip
Potassium	3.1 mEq / L	3.0 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Minor Drip
Lipid T - Cholesterol	78 mg / dl	75 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drip
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	48 mg / dl	45 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drip
Low Density Lipo Protein	56 mg / dl	54 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drip
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	24 mg / dl	22 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drip
High Density Lipo Protein	39 mg / dl	37 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Total	0.3 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Drip
S Bilirubin Direct	0.1 mg / dl	0.1 mg / dl	< 0.3	No Change
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.3 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Minor Drip
Aspartate Trans Amines	14 IU / L	12 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Alanine Trans Amines	13 IU / L	11 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drip
Creatine Phosphate K	5	4	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drip
CPK - Muscular / Brain	4	3	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drip
T - Protein	4.9 g / dl	4.7 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drip
Albumin	3.2 g / dl	3.0 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drip
Globulin	1.6 g / dl	1.4 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drip

Empirical Behaviour Estimates

4.18 Based on the One-Way and Two-Way Analysis below it is observed that:

- Gender of a person has statistically significant impact on Blood Sugar Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T – Cholesterol.
- Age level groups has no statistical significance on any one of these characteristics.

- Stress of a person has statistical significance on Potassium.
- The interaction effect of Gender and Stress is not statistically significant in case on any of these characteristics
- The interaction effect of Age and Gender is statistically significant on Blood Sugar Fasting, Blood Sugar Post - Prandial, Blood Sugar Random, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, Alanine Trans Amines and Globulin.
- The interaction effect of Age and Stress has no statistical significant on any of these characteristics.
- The main effect of 'Gender' and the interaction effect of 'Age and Gender' has influence on Blood Sugar Random. Similarly, The main effect of Gender and Stress influence on Potassium.

One-Way Analysis By Gender

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Blood Sugar Fasting	Between Groups	85.333	1	85.333	.566	.469
	Within Groups	1506.333	10	150.633		
	Total	1591.667	11			
Blood Sugar Prandial	Between Groups	1140.750	1	1140.750	3.491	.091
	Within Groups	3266.167	10	326.617		
	Total	4406.917	11			
Blood Sugar Random	Between Groups	2852.083	1	2852.083	6.481	.029
	Within Groups	4400.167	10	440.017		
	Total	7252.250	11			
Urea	Between Groups	133.333	1	133.333	7.221	.023
	Within Groups	184.667	10	18.467		
	Total	318.000	11			
Creatine	Between Groups	.120	1	.120	3.781	.080
	Within Groups	.317	10	.032		
	Total	.437	11			
Sodium	Between Groups	1386.750	1	1386.750	32.431	.000
	Within Groups	427.500	10	42.750		
	Total	1814.250	11			
Potassium	Between Groups	1.688	1	1.688	9.161	.013

	Within Group	1.842	10	.184		
	Total	3.529	11			
Lipid T -	Between Group	4218.750	1	4218.750	35.52	.000
Cholesterol	Within Group	1187.500	10	118.750		
	Total	5406.250	11			
Lipid Tri	Between Group	330.750	1	330.750	3.95	.075
Glyceride	Within Group	836.167	10	83.617		
	Total	1166.917	11			
Low Density	Between Group	234.083	1	234.083	3.35	.097
Protein	Within Group	696.833	10	69.683		
	Total	930.917	11			
Very Low De	Between Group	70.083	1	70.083	1.56	.239
Lipo Protein	Within Group	446.833	10	44.683		
	Total	516.917	11			
High Density	Between Group	96.333	1	96.333	3.71	.083
Protein	Within Group	259.667	10	25.967		
	Total	356.000	11			
S Bilirubin T	Between Group	.163	1	.163	4.85	.052
	Within Group	.337	10	.034		
	Total	.500	11			
Bilirubin D	Between Group	.000	1	.000	.086	.775
	Within Group	.024	10	.002		
	Total	.024	11			
S Bilirubi	Between Group	.001	1	.001	.077	.787
Indirect	Within Group	.108	10	.011		
	Total	.109	11			
Aspartate T	Between Group	14.083	1	14.083	1.11	.317
Amines	Within Group	126.833	10	12.683		
	Total	140.917	11			
Alanine Tra	Between Group	21.333	1	21.333	1.59	.235
Amines	Within Group	133.667	10	13.367		
	Total	155.000	11			
T - Protei	Between Group	.480	1	.480	.718	.417

	Within Group	6.687	10	.669		
	Total	7.167	11			
Albumin	Between Group	52.083	1	52.083	.871	.373
	Within Group	598.237	10	59.824		
	Total	650.320	11			
Globulin	Between Group	.041	1	.041	.481	.504
	Within Group	.848	10	.085		
	Total	.889	11			

One-Way Analysis By Age

ANOVA

		Sum of Squ	df	Mean Squ	F	Sig.
Blood Suga	Between Group	508.167	2	254.083	2.111	.177
Fasting	Within Group	1083.500	9	120.389		
	Total	1591.667	11			
Blood Suga	Between Group	2036.167	2	1018.083	3.865	.061
Post - Prandi	Within Group	2370.750	9	263.417		
	Total	4406.917	11			
Blood Suga	Between Group	2814.500	2	1407.250	2.854	.110
Random	Within Group	4437.750	9	493.083		
	Total	7252.250	11			
Urea	Between Group	62.000	2	31.000	1.090	.377
	Within Group	256.000	9	28.444		
	Total	318.000	11			
Creatine	Between Group	.062	2	.031	.740	.504
	Within Group	.375	9	.042		
	Total	.437	11			
Sodium	Between Group	15.500	2	7.750	.039	.962
	Within Group	1798.750	9	199.861		
	Total	1814.250	11			
Potassium	Between Group	.087	2	.043	.113	.894
	Within Group	3.442	9	.382		
	Total	3.529	11			

Lipid	Between Group	429.500	2	214.750	.388	.689
T - Cholesterol	Within Group	4976.750	9	552.972		
	Total	5406.250	11			
Lipid	Between Group	145.167	2	72.583	.639	.550
Tri - Glyceride	Within Group	1021.750	9	113.528		
	Total	1166.917	11			
Low Density Lipoprotein	Between Group	72.167	2	36.083	.378	.696
	Within Group	858.750	9	95.417		
	Total	930.917	11			
Very Low Density Lipoprotein	Between Group	5.167	2	2.583	.045	.956
	Within Group	511.750	9	56.861		
	Total	516.917	11			
High Density Lipoprotein	Between Group	24.000	2	12.000	.325	.730
	Within Group	332.000	9	36.889		
	Total	356.000	11			
S Bilirubin	Between Group	.080	2	.040	.857	.456
	Within Group	.420	9	.047		
	Total	.500	11			
S Bilirubin Direct	Between Group	.011	2	.006	3.971	.058
	Within Group	.013	9	.001		
	Total	.024	11			
S Bilirubin Indirect	Between Group	.002	2	.001	.070	.933
	Within Group	.108	9	.012		
	Total	.109	11			
Aspartate Transaminases	Between Group	43.167	2	21.583	1.987	.193
	Within Group	97.750	9	10.861		
	Total	140.917	11			
Alanine Transaminases	Between Group	15.500	2	7.750	.500	.622
	Within Group	139.500	9	15.500		
	Total	155.000	11			
T - Protein	Between Group	1.182	2	.591	.888	.444
	Within Group	5.985	9	.665		
	Total	7.167	11			

Albumin	Between Group	121.580	2	60.790	1.035	.394
	Within Group	528.740	9	58.749		
	Total	650.320	11			
Globulin	Between Group	.112	2	.056	.646	.547
	Within Group	.778	9	.086		
	Total	.889	11			

One-Way Analysis By Stress

Stress has statistical significance impact on Potassium characteristic.

ANOVA

		Sum of Squar	df	Mean Squ	F	Sig
Blood Sugar Fast	Between Group	96.333	1	96.333	.644	.44
	Within Group	1495.333	10	149.533		
	Total	1591.667	11			
Blood Sugar Pos Prandial	Between Group	154.083	1	154.083	.362	.56
	Within Group	4252.833	10	425.283		
	Total	4406.917	11			
Blood Sugar Ran	Between Group	330.750	1	330.750	.478	.50
	Within Group	6921.500	10	692.150		
	Total	7252.250	11			
Urea	Between Group	75.000	1	75.000	3.086	.109
	Within Group	243.000	10	24.300		
	Total	318.000	11			
Creatine	Between Group	.120	1	.120	3.789	.080
	Within Group	.317	10	.032		
	Total	.437	11			
Sodium	Between Group	310.083	1	310.083	2.061	.18
	Within Group	1504.167	10	150.417		
	Total	1814.250	11			
Potassium	Between Group	1.268	1	1.268	5.604	.039
	Within Group	2.262	10	.226		
	Total	3.529	11			

Lipid T - Cholest	Between Group	290.083	1	290.083	.567	.469
	Within Group	5116.167	10	511.617		
	Total	5406.250	11			
Lipid Tri - Glyce	Between Group	126.750	1	126.750	1.219	.299
	Within Group	1040.167	10	104.017		
	Total	1166.917	11			
Low Density Li Protein	Between Group	168.750	1	168.750	2.214	.169
	Within Group	762.167	10	76.217		
	Total	930.917	11			
Very Low Dens Lipo Protein	Between Group	52.083	1	52.083	1.120	.319
	Within Group	464.833	10	46.483		
	Total	516.917	11			
High Density Li Protein	Between Group	108.000	1	108.000	4.355	.069
	Within Group	248.000	10	24.800		
	Total	356.000	11			
S Bilirubin Tot	Between Group	.120	1	.120	3.158	.109
	Within Group	.380	10	.038		
	Total	.500	11			
S Bilirubin Dire	Between Group	.002	1	.002	.831	.389
	Within Group	.023	10	.002		
	Total	.024	11			
S Bilirubin Indir	Between Group	.021	1	.021	2.358	.159
	Within Group	.088	10	.009		
	Total	.109	11			
Aspartate Tran Amines	Between Group	44.083	1	44.083	4.552	.059
	Within Group	96.833	10	9.683		
	Total	140.917	11			
Alanine Trans Ar	Between Group	27.000	1	27.000	2.109	.179
	Within Group	128.000	10	12.800		
	Total	155.000	11			
T - Protein	Between Group	2.083	1	2.083	4.098	.079
	Within Group	5.083	10	.508		

	Total	7.167	11			
Albumin	Between Groups	52.083	1	52.083	.871	.371
	Within Groups	598.237	10	59.824		
	Total	650.320	11			
Globulin	Between Groups	.141	1	.141	1.882	.200
	Within Groups	.748	10	.075		
	Total	.889	11			

Two-Way Analysis Interactions

Gender and Stress interaction affect is not significant in case of any factor

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender * Stress	Blood Sugar Fasting	12.000	1	12.000	.069	.800
	Blood Sugar Post Prandial	2.083	1	2.083	.005	.943
	Blood Sugar Random	14.083	1	14.083	.028	.872
	Urea	.333	1	.333	.024	.880
	Creatinine	.003	1	.003	.138	.720
	Sodium	2.083	1	2.083	.145	.714
	Potassium	.008	1	.008	.106	.753
	Lipid Total Cholesterol	30.083	1	30.083	.277	.613
	Lipid Triglyceride	52.083	1	52.083	.634	.449
	Low Density Lipoprotein	60.750	1	60.750	1.040	.338
	Very Low Density Lipoprotein	14.083	1	14.083	.296	.601
	High Density Lipoprotein	16.333	1	16.333	.966	.355
	S Bilirubin Total	.003	1	.003	.125	.733
	S Bilirubin Direct	.002	1	.002	.733	.417
S Bilirubin Indirect	.001	1	.001	.077	.789	

Aspartate Trans Amines	2.083	1	2.083	.207	.662
Alanine Trans Amines	1.333	1	1.333	.101	.758
T - Protein	.163	1	.163	.294	.602
Albumin	63.480	1	63.480	1.051	.335
Globulin	.001	1	.001	.009	.925

Age and Gender interaction affect is statistically significant on Blood Sugar Fasting, Blood Sugar Post – Prandial, Blood Sugar Random, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Very Low Density Lipoprotein, Alanine Trans Amines and Globulin characteristics.

Source	Dependent Variable	Type I Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age * Gender	Blood Sugar Fasting	754.167	2	377.083	9.273	.015
	Blood Sugar Post Prandial	921.500	2	460.750	8.961	.016
	Blood Sugar Random	1033.167	2	516.583	5.610	.042
	Urea	24.667	2	12.333	.755	.510
	Creatine	.125	2	.063	2.885	.132
	Sodium	9.500	2	4.750	.071	.932
	Potassium	.140	2	.070	.260	.779
	Lipid T - Cholesterol	208.500	2	104.250	1.138	.381
	Lipid Tri - Glyceride	444.500	2	222.250	5.410	.045
	Low Density Lipoprotein	342.167	2	171.083	3.634	.092
	Very Low Density Lipoprotein	330.167	2	165.083	8.883	.016
	High Density Lipoprotein	4.667	2	2.333	.061	.942
	S Bilirubin Total	.027	2	.013	.348	.720
S Bilirubin Direct	.004	2	.002	1.428	.311	
S Bilirubin Indirect	.052	2	.026	2.818	.137	

Aspartate Tran Amines	28.167	2	14.083	1.523	.292
Alanine Trans Am	81.167	2	40.583	6.581	.031
T - Protein	2.315	2	1.157	2.177	.195
Albumin	114.427	2	57.213	.948	.439
Globulin	.572	2	.286	10.394	.011

Age and Stress interaction affect is not significant in case of any factor

Source	Depender Variable	Type I Sum Squares	Mean Squ	F	Sig.	
Age * Stress	Blood Sug Fasting	117.167	2	58.583	.404	.685
	lood Sugar I Prandial	145.167	2	72.583	.210	.816
	Blood Sug Random	204.500	2	102.250	.157	.858
	Urea	18.000	2	9.000	.331	.730
	Creatine	.005	2	.002	.060	.942
	Sodium	72.167	2	36.083	.153	.862
	Potassium	.080	2	.040	.115	.894
	Lipid T - Cholesterol	158.167	2	79.083	.105	.902
	Lipid Tri Glyceride	24.500	2	12.250	.084	.920
	ow Density Protein	33.500	2	16.750	.153	.861
	ery Low De Lipo Protein	17.167	2	8.583	.116	.892
	igh Density Protein	74.000	2	37.000	1.480	.300
	3 Bilirubin T	.080	2	.040	1.091	.394
	Bilirubin D	.002	2	.001	.850	.473

S Bilirubi Indirect	.012	2	.006	.467	.648
Aspartate T Amines	7.167	2	3.583	.462	.650
Alanine Tra Amines	3.500	2	1.750	.096	.910
T - Protei	.542	2	.271	.484	.639
Albumin	122.407	2	61.203	1.037	.410
Globulin	.012	2	.006	.056	.940

BLOOD SUGAR

Blood Sugar Fastin	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	70	61
M_40_55	71	70
M_55_70	74	73
F_25_40	76	56
F_40_55	82	80
F_55_70	47	46

Anova: Two- Factor

Without Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum
M_25_40	2	131
M_40_55	2	141
M_55_70	2	147
F_25_40	2	132
F_40_55	2	162
F_55_70	2	93
NO_STRESS	6	420
STRESSED	6	386

ANOVA

Source of Variatio	SS	df
Rows	1347.66666	5
Columns	96.3333333	1

Error 147.666666 5
 Total 1591.66666 11

Multiple Comparisons						
Dependent Variable:						
Tukey HSD						
(I) Gender_Agge	Mean Difference (I-	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
F_25_40	F_40_55	-15.0000	5.43446	0.212	-38.1829	8.1829
	F_55_70	19.5000	5.43446	0.094	-3.6829	42.6829
	M_25_40	0.5000	5.43446	1.000	-22.6829	23.6829
	M_40_55	-4.5000	5.43446	0.949	-27.6829	18.6829
	M_55_70	-7.5000	5.43446	0.739	-30.6829	15.6829
F_40_55	F_25_40	15.0000	5.43446	0.212	-8.1829	38.1829
	F_55_70	34.5000*	5.43446	0.010	11.3171	57.6829
	M_25_40	15.5000	5.43446	0.194	-7.6829	38.6829
	M_40_55	10.5000	5.43446	0.476	-12.6829	33.6829
	M_55_70	7.5000	5.43446	0.739	-15.6829	30.6829
F_55_70	F_25_40	-19.5000	5.43446	0.094	-42.6829	3.6829
	F_40_55	-34.5000*	5.43446	0.010	-57.6829	-11.3171
	M_25_40	-19.0000	5.43446	0.102	-42.1829	4.1829
	M_40_55	-24.0000*	5.43446	0.044	-47.1829	-0.8171
	M_55_70	-27.0000*	5.43446	0.027	-50.1829	-3.8171
M_25_40	F_25_40	-0.5000	5.43446	1.000	-23.6829	22.6829
	F_40_55	-15.5000	5.43446	0.194	-38.6829	7.6829
	F_55_70	19.0000	5.43446	0.102	-4.1829	42.1829
	M_40_55	-5.0000	5.43446	0.925	-28.1829	18.1829
	M_55_70	-8.0000	5.43446	0.694	-31.1829	15.1829
M_40_55	F_25_40	4.5000	5.43446	0.949	-18.6829	27.6829
	F_40_55	-10.5000	5.43446	0.476	-33.6829	12.6829
	F_55_70	24.0000*	5.43446	0.044	0.8171	47.1829
	M_25_40	5.0000	5.43446	0.925	-18.1829	28.1829
	M_55_70	-3.0000	5.43446	0.990	-26.1829	20.1829

M_55_70	F_25_40	7.5000	5.43446	0.739	-15.6829	30.6829	
Blood Sugar Random	40_55	NO_STRESS	8.0000	5.43446	0.739	-30.6829	15.6829
	55_70		27.0000*	5.43446	0.027	3.8171	50.1829
M_25_40	M_25_40	179	159				
M_40_55	M_25_40	8.0000	5.43446	0.694	-15.1829	31.1829	
M_40_55	M_40_55	113	111				
	M_40_55	3.0000	5.43446	0.990	-20.1829	26.1829	
Based on observed means.							
The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 29.533.							
*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.							

BLOOD SUGAR
POST – PRANDIAL

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	200	100	200
M_40_55	2	172	86	2
M_55_70	2	224	112	2
F_25_40	2	210	105	98
F_40_55	2	115	57.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	154	77	2
NO_STRESS	6	559	93.16667	493.3667
STRESSED	6	516	86	357.2

ANOVA

Source of Variati	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	<i>F crit</i>
Rows	4098.416667	5	819.6833	26.54128	0.0013119	5.05032905
Columns	154.0833333	1	154.0833	4.989207	0.07581635	6.60789097
Error	154.4166667	5	30.88333			
Total	4406.916667	11				

M_55_70	126	123
F_25_40	124	100
F_40_55	98	94
F_55_70	110	100

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	338	169	200
M_40_55	2	224	112	2
M_55_70	2	249	124.5	4.5
F_25_40	2	224	112	288
F_40_55	2	192	96	8
F_55_70	2	210	105	50
NO_STRESS	6	750	125	803.2
STRESSED	6	687	114.5	581.1

BLOOD SUGAR RANDOM

UREA

Urea	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	27	21
M_40_55	19	14
M_55_70	25	22
F_25_40	22	12
F_40_55	16	11
F_55_70	14	13

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	48	24	18
M_40_55	2	33	16.5	12.5

M_55_70	2	47	23.5	4.5
F_25_40	2	34	17	50
F_40_55	2	27	13.5	12.5
F_55_70	2	27	13.5	0.5
NO_STRESS	6	123	20.5	25.9
STRESSED	6	93	15.5	22.7

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F
Rows	220	5	44	9.565217
Columns	75	1	75	16.30435
Error	23	5	4.6	
Total	318	11		

CREATINE

Creatine	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	0.60	0.40
M_40_55	0.6	0.3
M_55_70	0.9	0.7
F_25_40	0.4	0.2
F_40_55	0.6	0.4
F_55_70	0.4	0.3

Anova: Two-Factor Without Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	1	0.5	0.02
M_40_55	2	0.9	0.45	0.045
M_55_70	2	1.6	0.8	0.02
F_25_40	2	0.6	0.3	0.02
F_40_55	2	1	0.5	0.02
F_55_70	2	0.7	0.35	0.005

NO_STRESS	6	3.5	0.5833	0.033667
STRESSED	6	2.3	0.3833	0.029667

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F
Rows	0.306666667	5	0.0613	30.66667
Columns	0.12	1	0.12	60
Error	0.01	5	0.002	
Total	0.436666667	11		

SODIUM

Sodium	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	141.00	129.00
M_40_55	141	131
M_55_70	137	131
F_25_40	121	101
F_40_55	121	110
F_55_70	115	113

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	270	135	72
M_40_55	2	272	136	50
M_55_70	2	268	134	18
F_25_40	2	222	111	200
F_40_55	2	231	115.5	60.5
F_55_70	2	228	114	2
NO_STRESS	6	776	129.3333	135.0667
STRESSED	6	715	119.1667	165.7667

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	1411.75	5	282.35	15.27592	0.00475258

Columns	310.0833333	1	310.0833	16.77638	0.0093924
Error	92.41666667	5	18.48333		
Total	1814.25	11			

POTASSIUM

Potassium	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	3.90	3.20
M_40_55	3.7	3.4
M_55_70	3.9	3.1
F_25_40	3.1	2.1
F_40_55	3.2	2.2
F_55_70	3.1	3

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	7.1	3.55	0.245
M_40_55	2	7.1	3.55	0.045
M_55_70	2	7	3.5	0.32
F_25_40	2	5.2	2.6	0.5
F_40_55	2	5.4	2.7	0.5
F_55_70	2	6.1	3.05	0.005
NO_STRESS	6	20.9	3.48333	0.15366
STRESSED	6	17	2.83333	0.29866

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	1.914166667	5	0.38283	5.50839	0.04224764
Columns	1.2675	1	1.2675	18.2374	0.00793477
Error	0.3475	5	0.0695		
Total	3.529166667	11			

LIPID T – CHOLESTEROL

Lipid T -	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
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Cholesterol		
M_25_40	138	108
M_40_55	119	114
M_55_70	124	120
F_25_40	102	92
F_40_55	79	72
F_55_70	78	75

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	246	123	450
M_40_55	2	233	116.5	12.5
M_55_70	2	244	122	8
F_25_40	2	194	97	50
F_40_55	2	151	75.5	24.5
F_55_70	2	153	76.5	4.5
NO_STRESS	6	640	106.6667	608.6667
STRESSED	6	581	96.83333	414.5667

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	4856.75	5	971.35	18.72181	0.00297591
Columns	290.0833333	1	290.0833	5.59107	0.06438691
Error	259.4166667	5	51.88333		
Total	5406.25	11			

LIPID TRI - GLYCERIDE

Lipid Tri - Glyceride	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	78	58
M_40_55	71	64
M_55_70	76	71

F_25_40	62	61
F_40_55	71	68
F_55_70	48	45

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	136	68	200
M_40_55	2	135	67.5	24.5
M_55_70	2	147	73.5	12.5
F_25_40	2	123	61.5	0.5
F_40_55	2	139	69.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	93	46.5	4.5
NO_STRESS	6	406	67.66667	123.46667
STRESSED	6	367	61.16667	84.56667

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	920.4166667	5	184.0833333	7.686152	0.02148547
Columns	126.75	1	126.75	5.292276	0.0697294
Error	119.75	5	23.95		
Total	1166.916667	11			

LOW DENSITY LIPO PROTEIN

Low Density L Protein	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	79	59
M_40_55	79	69
M_55_70	79	73
F_25_40	76	72
F_40_55	65	62

F_55_70	56	54
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Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	138	69	200
M_40_55	2	148	74	50
M_55_70	2	152	76	18
F_25_40	2	148	74	8
F_40_55	2	127	63.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	110	55	2
NO_STRESS	6	434	72.33333	93.46667
STRESSED	6	389	64.83333	58.96667

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	648.4166667	5	129.6833	5.700366	0.03949332
Columns	168.75	1	168.75	7.417582	0.04159989
Error	113.75	5	22.75		
Total	930.9166667	11			

VERY LOW DENSITY LIPO PROTEIN

Very Low Density Lipoprotein	NO_STRES	STRESSEI
M_25_40	31.00	17.00
M_40_55	24	21
M_55_70	14	12
F_25_40	12	11
F_40_55	12	9
F_55_70	24	22

Anova: Two-Factor With
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	48	24	98
M_40_55	2	45	22.5	4.5
M_55_70	2	26	13	2
F_25_40	2	23	11.5	0.5
F_40_55	2	21	10.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	46	23	2
NO_STRESS	6	117	19.5	63.1
STRESS	6	92	15.3333	29.8666

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	405.416666	5	81.0833	6.82328	0.0274979
Columns	52.0833333	1	52.0833	4.38288	0.09049276
Error	59.4166666	5	11.8833		
Total	516.916666	11			

HIGH DENSITY LIPO PROTEIN

High Density Lipoprotein	NO_STRESS	STRESS
M_25_40	56.00	36.00
M_40_55	48	45
M_55_70	43	41
F_25_40	43	37
F_40_55	41	38
F_55_70	39	37

Anova: Two-Factor With
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	92	46	200

M_40_55	2	93	46.5	4.5
M_55_70	2	84	42	2
F_25_40	2	80	40	18
F_40_55	2	79	39.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	76	38	2
NO_STRES	6	270	45	38
STRESSEI	6	234	39	11.6

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	125	5	25	1.01626	0.49315484
Columns	108	1	108	4.39024	0.09029128
Error	123	5	24.6		
Total	356	11			

S BILIRUBIN TOTAL

S Bilirubin T	NO_STRES	STRESSEI
M_25_40	0.90	0.40
M_40_55	0.8	0.5
M_55_70	0.5	0.6
F_25_40	0.7	0.4
F_40_55	0.4	0.3
F_55_70	0.3	0.2

Anova: Two-Factor With

Replication

SUMMAR'	Count	Sum	Average	Varianc
M_25_40	2	1.3	0.65	0.125
M_40_55	2	1.3	0.65	0.045
M_55_70	2	1.1	0.55	0.005
F_25_40	2	1.1	0.55	0.045
F_40_55	2	0.7	0.35	0.005

F_55_70	2	0.5	0.25	0.005
NO_STRES	6	3.6	0.6	0.056
STRESSEI	6	2.4	0.4	0.02

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	0.27	5	0.054	2.45454	0.17341910
Columns	0.12	1	0.12	5.45454	0.06675305
Error	0.11	5	0.022		
Total	0.5	11			

S BILIRUBIN DIRECT

S Bilirubin Direct	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	0.12	0.20
M_40_55	0.13	0.1
M_55_70	0.1	0.2
F_25_40	0.2	0.2
F_40_55	0.1	0.1
F_55_70	0.1	0.1

Anova: Two-Factor Without Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	0.32	0.16	0.0032
M_40_55	2	0.23	0.115	0.00045
M_55_70	2	0.3	0.15	0.005
F_25_40	2	0.4	0.2	0
F_40_55	2	0.2	0.1	0
F_55_70	2	0.2	0.1	0
NO_STRESS	6	0.75	0.125	0.00151

STRESSED 6 0.9 0.15 0.003

ANOVA

Source of Variati	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	0.01577	5	0.003154	2.32841	0.18754691
Columns	0.00187	1	0.001874	1.38376	0.29241147
Error	0.00677	5	0.001354		
Total	0.02442	11			

S BILIRUBIN INDIRECT

S Bilirubin Indirect	NO_STRES	STRESSEI
M_25_40	0.40	0.20
M_40_55	0.4	0.2
M_55_70	0.4	0.5
F_25_40	0.4	0.4
F_40_55	0.4	0.3
F_55_70	0.3	0.2

Anova: Two-Factor With
Replication

SUMMAR'	Count	Sum	Averag	Varianc
M_25_40	2	0.6	0.3	0.02
M_40_55	2	0.6	0.3	0.02
M_55_70	2	0.9	0.45	0.005
F_25_40	2	0.8	0.4	0
F_40_55	2	0.7	0.35	0.005
F_55_70	2	0.5	0.25	0.005
NO_STRES	6	2.3	0.38333	0.00166
STRESSEI	6	1.8	0.3	0.016

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
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Rows	0.05416666	5	0.01083	1.58536	0.31270090
Columns	0.02083333	1	0.02083	3.04878	0.14123477
Error	0.03416666	5	0.00683		
Total	0.10916666	11			

ASPARTATE TRANS AMINES

Aspartate Trans Amines	NO_STRESS	STRESSED
M_25_40	24.00	16.00
M_40_55	22	19
M_55_70	21	18
F_25_40	22	18
F_40_55	22	19
F_55_70	14	12

Anova: Two-Factor Without Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	40	20	32
M_40_55	2	41	20.5	4.5
M_55_70	2	39	19.5	4.5
F_25_40	2	40	20	8
F_40_55	2	41	20.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	26	13	2
NO_STRESS	6	125	20.83333	12.16667
STRESSED	6	102	17	7.2

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	85.41666667	5	17.08333	7.481752	0.02272990
Columns	44.08333333	1	44.08333	19.30655	0.00706181
Error	11.41666667	5	2.283333		

Total 140.9166667 11

ALANINE TRANS AMINES

Alanine Trans Ami	NO_STRESS	STRESS
M_25_40	23	16
M_40_55	19	17
M_55_70	23	21
F_25_40	21	19
F_40_55	21	18
F_55_70	13	11

Anova: Two-Factor Without Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	39	19.5	24.5
M_40_55	2	36	18	2
M_55_70	2	44	22	2
F_25_40	2	40	20	2
F_40_55	2	39	19.5	4.5
F_55_70	2	24	12	2
NO_STRESS	6	120	20	14
STRESSED	6	102	17	11.6

ANOVA

Source of Variatic	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	118	5	23.6	11.8	0.008503895
Columns	27	1	27	13.5	0.01437973
Error	10	5	2		
Total	155	11			

CREATINE PHOSPHATE K

Creatine Phosphate K	NO_STRESS	STRESS
M_25_40	21	4
M_40_55	21	18
M_55_70	8	6
F_25_40	7	4
F_40_55	7	5
F_55_70	5	4

Anova: Two-Factor With
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	25	12.5	144.5
M_40_55	2	39	19.5	4.5
M_55_70	2	14	7	2
F_25_40	2	11	5.5	4.5
F_40_55	2	12	6	2
F_55_70	2	9	4.5	0.5
NO_STRESS	6	69	11.5	55.1
STRESS	6	41	6.83333	30.56666

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	335.666666	5	67.13333	3.62230	0.09204081
Columns	65.3333333	1	65.33333	3.52518	0.11925191
Error	92.6666666	5	18.53333		
Total	493.666666	11			

CPK - MUSCULAR BRAIN

CPK - Muscular Brain	NO_STRESS	STRESS
M_25_40	14.00	12.00
M_40_55	26	13

M_55_70	11	8
F_25_40	9	6
F_40_55	9	7
F_55_70	4	3

Anova: Two-Factor Without
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	26	13	2
M_40_55	2	39	19.5	84.5
M_55_70	2	19	9.5	4.5
F_25_40	2	15	7.5	4.5
F_40_55	2	16	8	2
F_55_70	2	7	3.5	0.5
NO_STRESS	6	73	12.16667	56.56667
STRESSED	6	49	8.166667	14.16667

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	303.6666667	5	60.73333	6.073333	0.03481547
Columns	48	1	48	4.8	0.08000685
Error	50	5	10		
Total	401.6666667	11			

T - PROTEIN

T-Protein	NO_STRES	STRESSE
M_25_40	6.30	5.30
M_40_55	6.7	6.2
M_55_70	6.4	6.1
F_25_40	7	6
F_40_55	7	5

F_55_70	4.9	4.7
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Anova: Two-Factor With
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	11.6	5.8	0.5
M_40_55	2	12.9	6.45	0.125
M_55_70	2	12.5	6.25	0.045
F_25_40	2	13	6.5	0.5
F_40_55	2	12	6	2
F_55_70	2	9.6	4.8	0.02
NO_STRESS	6	38.3	6.38333	0.61366
STRESS	6	33.3	5.55	0.403

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	3.97666666	5	0.79533	3.59337	0.09333697
Columns	2.08333333	1	2.08333	9.41265	0.02784698
Error	1.10666666	5	0.22133		
Total	7.16666666	11			

ALBUMIN

Albumin	NO_STRESS	STRESS
M_25_40	3.90	3.40
M_40_55	3.6	3.4
M_55_70	3.7	3.1
F_25_40	3.1	3.0
F_40_55	3.6	3.2
F_55_70	3.2	3

Anova: Two-Factor Without

Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
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M_25_40	2	7.3	3.65	0.125
M_40_55	2	7	3.5	0.02
M_55_70	2	6.8	3.4	0.18
F_25_40	2	33.1	16.55	361.805
F_40_55	2	6.8	3.4	0.08
F_55_70	2	6.2	3.1	0.02
NO_STRESS	6	21.1	3.516667	0.093667
STRESSED	6	46.1	7.683333	119.5533

ANOVA

Source of Variat	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	288.09	5	57.618	0.928883	0.531274508
Columns	52.08333333	1	52.08333	0.839657	0.401530302
Error	310.1466667	5	62.02933		
Total	650.32	11			

GLOBULIN

Globulin	NO_STRES	STRESSE
M_25_40	1.90	1.80
M_40_55	1.2	1
M_55_70	1.7	1.3
F_25_40	1.6	1.4
F_40_55	1.9	1.7
F_55_70	1.6	1.4

Anova: Two-Factor With
Replication

SUMMARY	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M_25_40	2	3.7	1.85	0.005
M_40_55	2	2.2	1.1	0.02
M_55_70	2	3	1.5	0.08
F_25_40	2	3	1.5	0.02
F_40_55	2	3.6	1.8	0.02

F_55_70	2	3	1.5	0.02
NO_STRES	6	9.9	1.65	0.067
STRESSEL	6	8.6	1.43333	0.08266

ANOVA

Source of

Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Rows	0.72416666	5	0.14483	29.9655	0.00098312
Columns	0.14083333	1	0.14083	29.1379	0.00294713
Error	0.02416666	5	0.00483		
Total	0.88916666	11			

4.19 Some pertinent observations from the above analysis are as under;

- Age and Gender interaction affect is statistically significant on Blood Sugar Fasting, Blood Sugar Post – Prandial, Blood Sugar Random, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, Alanine Trans Amines and Globulin characteristics.
- Age and Stress interaction affect is not significant in case of any factor.
- Average Blood Sugar Fasting is differing significantly in different age groups with Gender.
- Average blood sugar fasting is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- The female group with between 55_70 differ significantly in Blood sugar fast from Female_40_55, Male_40_55 and Male_55_70 age groups.
- Average Blood Sugar Post - Prandial is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average blood sugar fasting is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- Average Blood Sugar Random is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average blood sugar Random is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions

- Average Urea is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average Urea is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- The average Creatine is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average Creatine is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- Average Sodium is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Average Sodium is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- Average Potassium is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Average Potassium is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- Average Lipid T - Cholesterol is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Average Lipid T - Cholesterol is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- Lipid Tri - Glyceride is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average Lipid Tri - Glyceride is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- Low Density Lipo Protein is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average Low Density Lipo Protein is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- Very Low Density Lipo Protein is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Average Very Low Density Lipo Protein is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- High Density Lipo Protein is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.

- Average High Density Lipo Protein is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- S Bilirubin Total is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average S Bilirubin Total is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- S Bilirubin Direct is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Average S Bilirubin Direct is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- S Bilirubin Indirect is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Average S Bilirubin Indirect is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- Aspartate Trans Amines is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Aspartate Trans Amines is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- Alanine Trans Amines is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender
- Alanine Trans Amines is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- Creatine Phosphate K is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- Creatine Phosphate K is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- CPK - Muscular is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
- CPK - Muscular is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
- T-Protein is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.

- T-Protein is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
 - Albumin is not differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
 - Albumin is not differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions.
 - Globulin is differing significantly in different age groups and Gender.
 - Globulin is differing significantly under no stress and stress conditions
- 4.20 Based on the following one-way and two-way analysis below it is observed that:

- Gender of a person has statistically significant impact on Blood Sugar Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol.
- Age level groups has no statistical significance on any one of these characteristics.
- Stress of a person has statistical significance on Potassium.
- The interaction effect of Gender and Stress is not statistically significant in case on any of these characteristics
- The interaction effect of Age and Gender is statistically significant on Blood Sugar Fasting, Blood Sugar Post - Prandial, Blood Sugar Random, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, Alanine Trans Amines and Globulin.
- The interaction effect of Age and Stress has no statistical significant on any of these characteristics.
- The main effect of 'Gender' and the interaction effect of 'Age and Gender' has influence on Blood Sugar Random. Similarly, The main effect of Gender and Stress influence on Potassium.

Discussions

4.21 Shepherd et al. (2015) noted that '...we are far from having a comprehensive and coherent story of this phenomenon. Instead, field has become increasingly fragmented and diverse' (p. 38). On one hand, we have a notion that entrepreneurs

should make choices using rationality, defined as a ‘...normative basis for deciding and acting’ (Miller, 2007). On the other hand, we have another notion that due to uncertainty (unknown nature of future) and ambiguity inherent in entrepreneurship, biases and heuristics represent a necessary ‘...systematic deviation from rationality or norms in choice and human centric choice making’ (Zhang and Cueto, 2017). In summary of related literature, Zhang and Cueto (2017) note that ‘...definitional disagreements, equivocal relationships, and overdue connections to advancements in other relevant research streams.’ Concerning rationality specifically, Miller (2007, p. 68) notes that empirical approaches are needed, because conceptual arguments alone cannot provide adequate answers.

4.22 Major finding is that business actor attempts to decide and evaluates prospective decision in Chaos and Resilience conditions using blood glucose medium. Thesis discusses findings to understand blood - glucose design and offers to answer issues in data - driven decision dynamics. Results demonstrate indications for extemporaneous counterfactual replication. Pertinent issue, in hand, is whether research can enlighten entrepreneurs as to how; optimally they can slant towards choice making? How can neurobehavioral research empirically scrutinise abstract frames for entrepreneurs’ choices? In this thesis, we have intended to challenge the stimulating theme entrepreneurial equanimity and reconnoiter circumstantial factors that influence human centric choice making. We have scrutinised the neuro - biological underpinnings considered ‘fair enough’ to make improved human centric choices (Busenitz and Barney, 1997; Manimala, 1992; Shepherd, Williams, and Patzelt, 2015). We have peered to strive for neurohematological insights a newfangled approaches of research in entrepreneurial neuromanagement that has facilitated an in depth consideration of questions centering entrepreneurial rationality to address questions regarding how entrepreneurs should make entrepreneurial choices. In spite of advances debate still embraces some concepts that merit attention. Are entrepreneurial choices rational? Why is it that in spite of an ocean of proved literature, still dichotomy between ‘rational versus irrational’ still haunts world of entrepreneurial choice mosaic? Of all issues haunting essence of ‘Rationality in Entrepreneurship Process: Is Being Rational Actually Rational’, what needs to be put on the surgical table? Scan needs to be undertaken as regards epistemic rationality (what to believe), practical rationality (what to do) and evaluative rationality (what to

value, what ends to pursue). What is the fine thread difference between responsibility (responsibility for entrepreneurial centric choices and actions) and rationality (expediency of choices and actions)? What are the choice making footsteps in entrepreneurial rational approach? Are these steps omitted anything? What view of entrepreneurial nature does this slant monitor? What influence does this tactic make to philosophies of entrepreneurial centric choice making?

4.23 In spectrum of rationality, one pertinent issue that crops up is whether more or large number of options (choice 'Noise') are better for entrepreneur? Entrepreneur operates on supposition that addition options do usually not offer detrimental situations and maneuvers on 'Profits at any (cognitive) cost diadem. Should entrepreneur aim at maximum utility concept or expected utility maximization? Should entrepreneur adopt the experimental or behavioural approaches? How should entrepreneur rationally select choice in a 'paradox of choice'? Do all entrepreneurs make same choices ('Choice Architecture') in face of same uncertain (unknown nature of future) / ambiguous / volatile and complex milieus? In wake of such issues, what is prescribed is thorough surgery between 'Finite' and 'Infinite' interpretation of entrepreneurial choice rationality.

4.24 Making proficient choices plays an imperatively vital role in business acumen and competency of entrepreneurs. Critical, as it sounds, cognition and assumptions that reinforce choice making is important when crafting and executing entrepreneurial strategies. Causativeness plays central role in entrepreneurial that typifies notion of causation in sciences of mind and brain. Contemporary lack of success and effort necessary for corroborating models are sketched to scrawny theoretical representation of entrepreneurial choice making in current 'mosaic. Are dissimilar notions a prerequisite for different experimental approaches? Are there variances in notions that are explicitly and implicitly presumed? What counts as causal evidence in entrepreneurial choice sciences? What role is played by information and physical mechanisms in identifying causal claims of entrepreneurial sciences of mind and brain? Thesis highlights potential cause - effect linkage between biology and management in explaining how entrepreneurs deal in choice dynamics.

4.25 Voyaging through ‘bustamination’ (‘business’ and ‘contamination’), entrepreneurial community is transversely at cater - cornered with cognitive science and entrepreneurship transmitting a perceptive organised linkage (‘Chess Board Matrix’). Each move in chess is a positional centric choice where players make and for which they tolerate magnitudes. This is perceived as ‘nonconforming approximation’ with business ‘replicas’ and ‘disruptors’. Positional defence is a choice situation where opening play by entrepreneur, or a series of moves taken protect his enterprise which is under threat. Check is a positional choice situation where move attacks opposing entrepreneur. Checkmate is positional centric choice situation where move by entrepreneur attacks opposing entrepreneur which opponent entrepreneur cannot get out of it.

4.26 Entrepreneurialcentric choice making is dominant to strategy of everything and strategy is about an inherent process. There is an imperative need to adopt shifting and embryonic unceasingly embracing neural mechanisms of perceptual practices fundamental to state of ‘Homo - cognitopsychoeconomicus which buttons ‘Homo Economicus’ by replicating how technology receptive entrepreneurs are influenced by psychological, genetic and cognitive conformations. Of interest is how ‘entrepreneurial’ brain captivates to acclimate to inform and improve ‘entrepreneurial’ choice mechanism in a state of complexity and seismicity of uncertain. With advent of crossbreed choice making prototypes, questions that merit consideration are; do entrepreneurs actually have a choice? How do they handpick an action in state of unbounded ‘scrolling’ and interminable ‘disorders’? What ‘cognitive signatures’ relate to receptive inferences? Will cognitive entrepreneurial dynamics supplant orthodox cognitive alignments associating cognitive - integrated mosaic to reconnoiter cognitive - corridors in ‘entrepreneurial’ choices? As a trade - off between accuracy and explain ability, experiments based on methods and approaches hematological arrangements data are offered.

4.27 The following deductions were obtained from the above cumulative analyses: -

- Hematological arrangements afford instrumental evidence during entrepreneurial choice.
- Hematological ‘tracking’ is recognised as appreciated method in entrepreneur - centered choice process.
- Apart from choice- task exactitudes and inference stretches, hematological arrangements can be logged to scrutinize entrepreneurial choice task key approaches and cognitive capability of entrepreneurs.
- Hematological arrangements help entrepreneurs represent vigorous entrepreneurial choice making in a communicative approach.
- Strong variations in hematological arrangements comportment represent choice certainty.
- Observing hematological variables helps identify transitory situations of ambiguity.
- Hematological arrangements serve as calculation technique that goes beyond customary scrutiny.

4.28 When confronted with improbability, entrepreneurs employ avant-garde reasoning intuition (reference is drawn to the concept of ‘Quasirationality’; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception) comportment is an essential part of business research. Proposing ‘practical wisdom’, this research advocates for Neuroscientific backed up experiment researches towards entrepreneurial rational centric choice modelling (via. Revealed Preference). There is a need to examine pirouetting concerning instinct and rationality with reference to information processing in entrepreneurial mind and haematological parameters.

Inferences

4.29 To provide central basis for understanding entrepreneurial choice making and rational centric choice poise, we analysed blood samples of willing and volunteer respondents. It is perceived that almost all ‘Hematological Monikers’ in respondents reflect disquieting trends. Based on clinical tests (Satpathy, J. et. al.; 2018), it is inferred that; rational centric choice making potential is bad when;

- Blood glucose fasting indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Blood glucose post - prandial indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.

- Blood glucose random indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Urea indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Creatine indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Sodium indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Potassium indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- S bilirubin direct indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- S bilirubin indirect indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Aspartate trans amines AST indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Alanine trans amines alt indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Lipid T - cholesterol indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Lipid tri - glyceride indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Low-density lipo protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Very low-density lipo protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- High density lipo protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- S bilirubin total indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Creatine Phosphate K indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- CPK - muscular / brain indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- GGT indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- T - Protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Albumin indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Globulin indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- A: G ratio indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.

4.30 Results exhibit signals for spontaneous counterfactual simulation in domain of high - level cognitive. Major finding is that entrepreneur endeavours to address choices using hematological arrangements ‘neuro - drivers’. Research communication discusses inferences and prospective ways to guide hematological neuroscience in choice curve. Research offers ‘First - Rate Anchorage’ of hematological arrangements ‘neuro - drivers’ and ‘entrepreneur centric choice corridor arrangements’ to appreciate how entrepreneurs make choices. Allowing for other methodologies to nature of insolent choice contours, this attempt can be pigeonholed as psycho - behavioural, in that it routines wide assortment of conceptions used in behavioural scholarships, in which anthropological behaviour is reconnoitered from capacious ways. The principal findings in this research are;

- Entrepreneurs tend to act rationally and in their own finest interests when deciding,
- Management researchers need to study neuromanagement in realm of entrepreneurial choice dynamics,
- Neuromanagement provides ways of measuring entrepreneurial well-being,
- Neuromanagement aid as a catalyst for entrepreneurial choice dynamics model development,
- Neuromanagement provides a way to test entrepreneurial centric choice models, and
- Neuromanagement improve capability to predict entrepreneurial choice dynamics behaviour.

4.31 Based on the analysis above it is observed that: -

- Gender has a statistically significant impact on Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid T - Cholesterol.
- Age level groups have no statistical significance on any one of these characteristics.
- Stress of a person has statistical significance on Potassium.
- The interaction effect of Gender and Stress is not statistically significant in case on any of these characteristics
- The interaction effect of Age and Gender is statistically significant on Blood Glucose Fasting, Blood Glucose Post - Prandial, Blood Glucose Random, Lipid Tri - Glyceride, Very Low Density Lipo Protein, Alanine Trans Amines and Globulin.
- Interaction effect of Age and Stress has no statistical significant on any of these characteristics.
- Main effect of 'Gender' and the interaction effect of 'Age and Gender' has influence on Blood Glucose Random. Similarly, The main effect of Gender and Stress influence on Potassium.

Experiment No. 2

Neuro - Ocular Experiment

4.32 As a prefatory, neuro - management parallels cognitive science and has bridged contrasting fields of management, psychology and neuro - entrepreneurial science with aim of providing a single notion of

entrepreneurial behaviour. Herein, consilience operates tools for modelling behaviour to understand processes that connect neuro - dynamisms in which entrepreneurs decide. Neuro - ocular findings pose challenge to standard management perspective by questioning as how entrepreneurs craft choices. Neuro - ocular choice making bridges this gap. Integration offers exciting potential for deciphering neuro - ocular choice transactions through mechanistic understandings of neuromanagement - oriented processes and computations. How to handle brains in age of dramatic change and growing 'deep' uncertainty? What are the coherent dynamics underlying prediction, control and choice-making? Problem statement is that, in eye simulations, choice is represented by spots of neural activity linked to stimulating prospects for rational processing that help acquisition, possessing and sketching entrepreneurial choice formation replicating computational choice formation.

4.33 Conformist approach in eye tracking experiment is to conjecture what eye patterns should be perceived if a given archetype of choice making is assumed to be perfect and advance to verify that. Purpose of this section of the thesis is to elucidate principles and dynamism in neuro - ocular interactions that contribute stimulus to management - oriented choice. Analyses of literature offers scant evidence on the subject. Methodology uses inputs from Kowler, Fang, Orquin and Hochman models that employ brain - eye movement. Results indicate characterising effect of brain - eye interactions to explain and describe 'choice making. This encourages cross - fertilization of perspectives to explore phenomena through neuro - ocular models of choice.

4.34 **Methodology and Design Parameters:** Eye tracking choice research, through neuro - ocular approaches, is, distinguished by occurrence of collaborating solicitations. Eye movements are integral part of interactions with ocular world. This is for inspecting contents of neuro - ocular scene, or navigating through environment. This brings eyes quickly and accurately to important positions. Eye movements accomplish this without external stimulation, spontaneous and self - generated activity. This manifests itself as oscillations in different frequency bands. Research explores effect of neuronal oscillations perceptual processes ('amplification' or 'filtering') that cannot be observed directly. Instead, they can be identified by modeling empirical 'inferential' data with models. These explain relationship between functional methodologies, experimental conditions and emotional 'inferential' data (advanced tests are underway at the Berlin

School of Mind and Brain; Germany). With different disciplines approaching through characteristically different techniques and substantial advances, question of how entrepreneurs design business choices has engaged scholars for decades (Satpathy; 2015).

4.35 Who has never been in web of hard circumstances to take paramount choice, weighing optimistic or unenthusiastic aspects to accept some risk for entrepreneurial choice making? How to account information about subjective value, risk, ambiguity and timing when making choice? How does this criterion differ in strategy? Research has documented rational and strategic considerations that explain choice behaviour that distinguishes dissimilar criteria? Are there direct correlations that exist between qualitative aspects of dissimilar criteria affect selection of choice-making criteria? How flexible are dissimilar models based upon current practices? Is there an identifiable relationship between external variables and choice criterion? What kinds of algorithms and computations underpin choice process? What areas of eyes are involved in entrepreneurial choice making and how are these processes implemented at neural level (Satpathy; 2015)? What are its neuro - ocular domain? Problem statement is that, in eye simulations, choice is represented by spots of neural activity linked to stimulating prospects for rational processing that help in gaining, possessing and tracing entrepreneurial choice formation replicating computational choice perspectives. Purpose of succeeding portion of this thesis is to explicate neuro - ocular interactions that contribute stimulus to entrepreneurial choice.

4.36 **Kowler Model** (Prof Eileen Kowler, USA) has directed research efforts via neuro - ocular approaches to understanding processes that control, plan and programme eye movements. Eye movements provide insights from sensorimotor integration to cognition. This is while entrepreneurs perform natural ocular and cognitive tasks. Model focuses on role of planning, attention, memory, sensory and perceptual cues to simulate demands of natural scanning and permit understanding dynamisms. In ocular search, principal questions are; how do entrepreneurs decide where to look when attempting to decide?

4.37 Instead of looking at locations where 'choice spots' are likely to appear, eye often visits unlikely locations because they were closer and take less time to access. Although such strategies seem unreasonable, they are useful in long run. This is because they reduce time required to plan saccades. Cohort of a saccade can be upshot of choice process. Functional models aligned to these are grounded on accretion of sensory

evidence. These are affected by choice oriented variables. In saccadic eye movements, model finds effort to attend to one place and saccade to another. Emphasis is on oculomotor behaviours: gaze control, smooth pursuit and saccades and their interactions with vision.

4.38 Fundamental and classical questions are; what dynamisms keep gaze stable with static or mobile targets? How does motion of image affect vision? Where do subjects look - and why - when executing a complex task? Fang Model (Prof Fang-Ying Yang, Taiwan) has directed research efforts towards development of scientific reasoning and conceptual development in comprehension. Model emphasizes on effects of neuro - ocular factors on issues oriented to entrepreneurs' choice concepts and reason when encountering uncertain information. Model, via neuro - ocular approaches, aims to combine eye tracking method and magnetoencephalography apparatus to explore behaviours. Some contributions are in digital environments based on eye tracking, cognitive processes during debugging in eye movement, eye-movement analysis about uncertain issue and methodology of eye tracking techniques (Fang; 2010, 2011 and 2016). Model concentrates on ocular cognition, perception and attention by using behavioural recorded 'shots' that are crucial in neuro - ocular domain. Within accepted optimal techniques, this model sets potential benchmarks for business choice making. The model leads to better understanding of how attention works with sensory signals (Kowler; 1989, 1990, 1991 and 1995). These are crucial contributions in its neuro - ocular domain with accepted optimal techniques that set potential benchmarks for entrepreneurial choice making? This thesis has incorporated and acknowledges essence of Kowler Model posits for advanced experimental researches in this domain.

4.39 Hochman Model (Prof Guy Hochman, Israel) models an integrated algorithm of cognitive processes underlie choice making. Neuro - ocular model incorporates dynamics of brain processes to mechanism of physiological measures viz. Pupil Diameter and Heart Rate. This is in context of connectivity to behavioural perspectives in entrepreneurial choice making. Computation of differences between descriptions and experience, proportional examination using eye - tracking, physiological measures, applications and improvements of eye movement form the foundation of the model,

Research Design

4.40 Objective was to learn about relevant eye tracking, design research questions, tasks and possible metrics, testing stimulus, create tests, analyse tracking 'inferential' data and generate result deliverables. Subjects were briefed about the experiments and

were provided with a 'material' on which they were to be tested as regards their comprehension of the provided information. Principal objective of experimentation was to contribute in its neuro - ocular domain with accepted optimal techniques. Aim was to have a 'cognitive - link' with 'heat maps' to connect neuro - ocular information schema. Heat maps were adopted to answer as to what fascinates participants' responsiveness? How does one characteristically look at a spot when undertaking a task? How do subjects allocate attention over an inducement? **These helped connect** important aspects of neuro - ocular information graphic behaviour. Gaze plots were observed as crucial contributions in neuro - ocular domain with accepted optimal techniques that set potential benchmarks for business choice making. All these experimental designs were aimed to understand and inquire if there exists a relationship between how subjects assimilated information and understanding of 'material' information.

4.41 In order to warrant that eye tracking experiment is properly inferred and simulated, experiment atmosphere, geometry of light settings, geometry of stimulus, font of 'material', system configuration, population traits, regulation corroboration method, timing, 'inferential' data route, AOIs and segregation criteria were defined. In order to ensure proper recording of significant eye activities, displays and phantasmagorias were fashioned to bring into line with inquiry purposes. After Area of Interests was demarcated, 'inferential' data was transferred to eye tracking software (Tobii) for each AOI. Eye movements were conducted to include fixations (when eye stops and focus) and saccades (when eye moves between fixation points). Tobii eye tracking cameras recorded fixation count, fixation duration, total fixation duration, percent fixated, time to first fixation and scan path in respect of each AOI.

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4.42 Design emphasis was to;

- Articulate queries and style primary observations,
- Articulate supposition and make likelihoods,
- Choose developmental methods and research strategy,
- Outline each measure,
- Select suitable recorded 'shots' technique,
- Practice recorded 'shots' technique,
- Collect facts and develop 'Heat Maps', and
- Analyse information to draw inferences.

4.43 Experiments were piloted at the Fang Yang Laboratory, Graduate Institute of Science Education, New Taiwan Normal University, Taipei, Taiwan, to resemble a typical choice- oriented setting. Subjects were tested on their comprehension of VUCA information. Tobii Eye Sensor was used for neuro - ocular purpose. Literature manual from Tobii Company illustrates that depending of system design, Tobii uses different NIR sensors and illuminators. Tobii Eye Sensors offer specific set of sensor and illuminators for each neuro - ocular design. Tobii uses imperceptible near-infrared light and tall classification cameras to assign light on entrepreneurial eye. It registers path they are revealed. Thereafter, sophisticated algorithms calibrate eyes and regulate foci on which where they are convexed. Tobii uses combination of custom-designed and standard components typically used in higher volume designs.

- **F1** - Displays live view to help place subject.
- **F2** - Perform simple one - point standardization update.
- **F3** - Launch full standardization.
- **F4** - Pointers becomes imperceptible.
- **F5** - Introduction of locations edge.
- **F6** - Hides hotspot at top.
- **F7** - Recesses eye tracking .
- **F8** - Clasp left click lock.
- **F9** - Quick access exit.

Research Strategy

4.44 As this piece of research (neuro - ocular) is a maiden attempt, within spectrum of neuro management, observed as crucial contributions in its neuro - ocular domain with accepted optimal techniques that set potential benchmarks for business choice making, it is prudent to place an extract from Tobii manual, presented as under;

‘Eye tracking analysis is based on important assumption that there is a relationship between fixations, gaze and thinking. Spatial and Temporal sampling ability of eye limits manner to extract ocular information from events. Because ocular acuity decreases rapidly when we move away from center of ocular field, we possess repertoire of eye movements that allow eyes at target locations of interest. Fixations are common feature of looking that eye tracking researchers analyze to make inferences about cognitive processes or states that they are interested in probing. Fixations are those times when

eyes essentially stop scanning about scene, holding central fovea vision in place so that the ocular system can take in detailed information about what is being looked at. But how do we get fixations? Fixations are constructions, outputs of a mathematical algorithm that translates sequence of raw gaze points into associated sequence of fixations’.

4.45 Thirty (30) healthy volunteers’ respondents were accorded space to undertake the tests. All experimental procedures were approved by New Taiwan Normal University, Taipei. At the start of each experiment session, a ‘material’ was provided to subject to be read aloud first and then a silent reading. Thereafter, the Lab entrepreneur in the experimenter station regulated the eye tracker for each participant to map ‘points’ on the monitor. After calibration, participant’s references were captured that reflected perception of cognitive load. ‘Inferential’ data were collected for each contributing subject independently. The stimuli, procedures, and analyses used in experiments were designed and deliberated at Fang Ying Ying Eye Tracking Lab, New Taiwan Normal University, Taipei. Some operational details were obtained directly from Prof Fang Ying Ying. Subjects differentiated upward from downward motion and random dot impetuses were located to left and / or right of fixation. Visual stimuli were created and considered. This was by using a Pentium - class computer operating within Windows XP environment. Visual stimuli were displayed using linearized 42" CRT monitor. It had an enliven rate of 60Hz. Screen was viewed by subjects from distance of 65cm. A chin rest was used. This was to steady observing situation. All experiments were performed in dimly-illuminated testing booth. Test results are presented in subsequent section(s) sub - titled ‘Results’, below.

Results and Discussion

4.46 **Research ‘Material’**: *Entrepreneur has to take choices with inadequate information. It is important to understand intricacy of entrepreneurial in exploring how eyes choose appropriate responses. In order to explain neural basis of choice making, ability to process alternatives and choose optimal course, research combines methods to build models for answering choice questions. The ‘material’ break - up is as under;*

V U C A : The Hidden Story

HYPOTHESIS

Complex business situation leads to wrong decisions

Global commercial crisis has led to a dramatic change in business world. Many organisations and managers are struggling to stay afloat and aligned in volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous nature of today's global and local business environment. Turbulence, rapid rate of change, is swirling around many of us, tipping us this way and that, as we attempt to navigate a safe passage through it all. Most businesses are suffering from uncertainty and complexity where business decision making is a probability. As a result, business leaders are suffering huge loss.

There is a **need to** overcome this state of VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity) and realign business prospects. Unpredictable events happening outside can be negative or positive. Each present greater VUCA. This which makes it more difficult for leaders to make decisions. The experiment revisions how business can manage change process in rapidly changing, chaotic and turbulent business environment. Leaders need to act as a change agent. They need to play important role in initiating, implementing and managing change in times of crisis under severe, uncertain and complex condition.

Furthermore, they do not understand how to respond or deal with VUCA. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity each component poses exceptional challenges. Therefore, business leaders should be able to identify each component with separate and unique response. They should start transition.

Choices are limited to: **One**, Move from hierarchy to self - organisation. Push decisions down to edge of organization, where information is freshest and salient. **Two**, Move from protecting information to democratization of information. To empower employees to make decisions, make communication frictionless. **Three**, Speed up interactions. Accelerate speed of interaction as much as possible. **Last**, use simple rules to make quick decisions, rather than perfect analyses.

Options are limited to **FIGHT** (Should Manager fight) forces of Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity, **FLIGHT** (Should Manager escape) from Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity situation or get a **FRIGHT** (Should Manager get frightened) and live along with Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity.

TIME TO FIXATE

Time to First Fixation

Fixation observation 4.JPG1Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG1 sum
Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG2N	Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG2Mean
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Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG4N	Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG4Mean
Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG4 sum	Time to First Fixation observation 5.JPG5N
Time to First Fixation observation 5.JPG5Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 5.JPG5 sum
Time to First Fixation observation 6.JPG6N	Time to First

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Fixated observation 6.JPG6 sum Percentage Fixated observation 6.JPG7N
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observation 7.JPG9N Percentage Fixated observation 7.JPG9MeanPercentage
Fixated observation 7.JPG9 sum

Rec 01	1	1.20	1.20	1	18.39	18.39	1	23.75	23.75	1	26.07	
	26.07	1	8.75	8.75	1	3.19	3.19	1	14.00	14.00	1	
	8.66	8.66	1	2.32	2.32	1	5.56	5.56	1	0.15	0.15	1
	0.11	0.11	1	0.44	0.44	1	0.07	0.07	1	0.17	0.17	1
	0.39	0.39	1	0.17	0.17	1	0.17	0.17	1	0.24	0.24	1
	0.16	0.16	7	0.19	1.32	12	0.19	2.27	1	0.44	0.44	7
	0.12	0.82	7	0.12	0.25	10	0.19	1.94	1	0.17	0.17	7
	0.15	1.06	1	0.16	0.47	4	0.15	0.58	1	1.32	1.32	1
	2.27	2.27	1	0.44	0.44	1	0.82	0.82	1	0.25	0.25	1
	1.94	1.94	1	0.17	0.17	1	1.06	1.06	1	0.47	0.47	1
	0.58	0.58	1	7.00	7.00	1	12.00	12.00	1	1.00	1.00	1
	7.00	7.00	1	2.00	2.00	1	10.00	10.00	1	1.00	1.00	1
	7.00	7.00	1	3.00	3.00	1	4.00	4.00	1	1.72	1.72	1
	2.78	2.78	1	0.44	0.44	1	1.23	1.23	1	0.25	0.25	1
	2.28	2.28	1	0.17	0.17	1	1.73	1.73	1	0.94	0.94	1
	0.85	0.85	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	100%	1
Rec 02	1	3.97	3.97	1	29.23	29.23	1	35.48	35.48	1	39.96	
	39.96	1	14.63	14.63	1	12.08	12.08	1	45.81	45.81	1	
	22.38	22.38	1	3.13	3.13	1	17.22	17.22	1	0.14		1
	0.14	1	0.29	0.29	1	0.21	0.21	1	0.97	0.97	1	

0.20	0.201	0.25	0.25	1	0.41	0.41	1	0.27	0.27	1
0.21	0.211	0.34	0.34	7	0.22	1.54	16	0.22	3.45	8
0.22	1.777	0.35	2.44	13	0.24	3.07	15	0.28	4.22	9
0.23	2.0415	0.19	2.91	8	0.24	1.95	10	0.20	2.01	1
1.54	1.541	3.45	3.45	1	1.77	1.77	1	2.44	2.44	1
3.07	3.071	4.22	4.22	1	2.04	2.04	1	2.91	2.91	1
1.95	1.951	2.01	2.01	1	7.00	7.00	1	16.00	16.00	1
8.00	8.001	7.00	7.00	1	13.00	13.00	1	15.00	15.00	1
9.00	9.001	15.00	15.00	1	8.00	8.00	1	10.00	10.00	1
1.64	1.641	3.77	3.77	1	1.89	1.89	1	2.55	2.55	1
3.34	3.341	4.56	4.56	1	2.70	2.70	1	3.77	3.77	1
2.15	2.151	2.32	2.32	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	
100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
100%	100%									

Rec 03	1	3.183.18	1	31.36	31.36	1	49.27	49.27	1	53.08
53.08	1	18.93	18.93	1	8.97	8.97	1	42.40	42.40	1
20.88	20.88	1	3.93	3.93	1	14.64	14.64	1	0.26	
0.26	1	0.28	0.28	1	0.26	0.26	1	0.77	0.77	1
0.35	0.351	0.25	0.25	1	0.31	0.31	1	0.33	0.33	1
0.33	0.331	0.13	0.13	9	0.27	2.40	20	0.30	6.05	4
0.42	1.689	0.27	2.39	12	0.27	3.20	15	0.28	4.15	13
0.30	3.928	0.29	2.28	11	0.24	2.65	6	0.24	1.42	1
2.40	2.401	6.05	6.05	1	1.68	1.68	1	2.39	2.39	1
3.20	3.201	4.15	4.15	1	3.92	3.92	1	2.28	2.28	1
2.65	2.651	1.42	1.42	1	9.00	9.00	1	20.00	20.00	1
4.00	4.001	9.00	9.00	1	12.00	12.00	1	15.00	15.00	1
13.00	13.00	1	8.00	8.00	1	11.00	11.00	1	6.00	
6.00	1	2.58	2.58	1	6.71	6.71	1	1.73	1.73	1
2.73	2.731	3.68	3.68	1	4.70	4.70	1	4.15	4.15	1
2.47	2.471	3.06	3.06	1	1.57	1.57	1	100%	100%	1
100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	

100% 1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	
100%	100%	1	100%	100%						
All Recordings	3	2.78	8.35	3	26.33	78.98	3	36.17	108.50	3
39.70	119.10	3	14.10	42.31	3	8.08	24.24	3	34.07	
102.21	3	17.31	51.93	3	3.13	9.38	3	12.48	37.43	3
0.18	0.55	3	0.23	0.68	3	0.30	0.91	3	0.60	1.80
0.24	0.72	3	0.30	0.89	3	0.30	0.89	3	0.26	0.77
0.26	0.78	3	0.21	0.63	23	0.23	5.27	48	0.25	11.77
0.30	3.88	23	0.25	5.66	27	0.24	6.52	40	0.26	10.32
0.27	6.14	30	0.21	6.25	22	0.23	5.07	20	0.20	4.02
1.76	5.27	3	3.92	11.77	3	1.29	3.88	3	1.89	5.66
2.17	6.52	3	3.44	10.32	3	2.05	6.14	3	2.08	6.25
1.69	5.07	3	1.34	4.02	3	7.67	23.00	3	16.00	48.00
4.33	13.00	3	7.67	23.00	3	9.00	27.00	3	13.33	
40.00	3	7.67	23.00	3	10.00	30.00	3	7.33	22.00	3
6.67	20.00	3	1.98	5.94	3	4.42	13.27	3	1.36	
4.07	3	2.17	6.52	3	2.42	7.27	3	3.84	11.53	3
2.34	7.02	3	2.66	7.97	3	2.05	6.15	3	1.58	4.74
100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	
300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3
100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%			
Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG1Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG2Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG3Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG4Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 5.JPG5Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 6.JPG6Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 6.JPG7Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 7.JPG10Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 7.JPG8Mean	Time to First Fixation observation 7.JPG9Mean	
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	7.00	2.00	10.00	1.00	7.00	3.00	4.00	1.72	2.78	0.44	1.23
	0.25	2.28	0.17	1.73	0.94	0.85	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
	100%	100%		100%	100%	100%					
Rec 02	3.97	29.23	35.48	39.96	14.63	12.08	45.81	22.38	3.13	17.22	
	0.14	0.29	0.21	0.97	0.20	0.25	0.41	0.27	0.21	0.34	0.22
	0.22	0.22	0.35	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.19	0.24	0.20	1.54	3.45
	1.77	2.44	3.07	4.22	2.04	2.91	1.95	2.01	7.00	16.00	8.00
	7.00	13.00		15.00	9.00	15.00	8.00	10.00	1.64	3.77	1.89
	2.55	3.34	4.56	2.70	3.77	2.15	2.32	100%	100%	100%	100%
	100%	100%		100%	100%	100%					
Rec 03	3.18	31.36	49.27	53.08	18.93	8.97	42.40	20.88	3.93	14.64	
	0.26	0.28	0.26	0.77	0.35	0.25	0.31	0.33	0.33	0.13	0.27
	0.30	0.42	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.30	0.29	0.24	0.24	2.40	6.05
	1.68	2.39	3.20	4.15	3.92	2.28	2.65	1.42	9.00	20.00	4.00
	9.00	12.00		15.00	13.00	8.00	11.00	6.00	2.58	6.71	1.73
	2.73	3.68	4.70	4.15	2.47	3.06	1.57	100%	100%	100%	100%
	100%	100%		100%	100%	100%					
All Recordings	2.78	26.33	36.17	39.70	14.10	8.08	34.07	17.31	3.13		
	12.48	0.18	0.23	0.30	0.60	0.24	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.26	0.21
	0.23	0.25	0.30	0.25	0.24	0.26	0.27	0.21	0.23	0.20	1.76
	3.92	1.29	1.89	2.17	3.44	2.05	2.08	1.69	1.34	7.67	16.00
	4.33	7.67	9.00	13.33	7.67	10.00	7.33	6.67	1.98	4.42	1.36
	2.17	2.42	3.84	2.34	2.66	2.05	1.58	100%	100%	100%	100%
	100%	100%		100%	100%	100%					

Discussion

4.47 ‘Inferential’ data from each subject were analysed independently. Error rates were quite low. Even with MSS (memory set size) of 100 objects, Observations were correct (85%) of the time. There was a main effect of both presence of target item and MSS on response accuracy: target presence, $F(1, 12) = 31.18, p < 0.001$, generalised eta squared ($g-\eta^2$), a measure of effect size) = 0.25; MSS, $F(1.44, 18.85) = 88.80, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.51$, and the two factors interacted significantly, $F(1.47, 19.30) = 23.77, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.04$. Real time ‘inferential’ data on correct references follow same pattern of large main effects for both factors: target

presence, $F(1, 12) = 28.71, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.24$; MSS, $F(1.37, 17.88) = 83.81, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.51$, and substantial interaction between the two, $F(2.46, 31.94) = 24.26, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.04$. Slope was significantly influenced by target presence, $F(1, 12) = 37.25, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.27$. In addition, there was significant effect of MSS on search slope, $F(1.33, 17.47) = 45.43, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.45$. In sum, behavioural results are in strong agreement with previous work. There was a significant effect of target presence (all F values $> 7, p < 0.04$) on all measures except dwell time on fixated distractors, $F(1, 12) = 2.00, p = 0.17, g-\eta^2 = 0.01$. In all cases, two factors interacted such that the effect of target presence became larger as MSS increased (all F s > 5 , all p s < 0.004). percentage of distractors fixated on absent references increases significantly from an average of 22% per O per reference to 72% as MSS increases from one to 100 items, $F(1.74, 22.87) = 56.9, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.55$. Dwell time on each distractor increased from 52 to 290 ms, $F(1.24, 16.23) = 27.97, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = 0.36$. This result replicates if we restrict analysis to only distractors that were fixated, $F(1.27, 16.57) = 13.55, p < 0.004, g-\eta^2 = 0.23$. Total fixations per item on absent references rose from 0.26 with one item in memory to 1.27 with 100 items in memory, $F(1.26, 16.32) = 29.23, p < 0.001, g-\eta^2 = .36$. Fixations could be interpreted in different ways depending on context and objective of the study. During processing of neuro - ocular scene, individuals moved eyes to relevant features in that scene. Some features were primarily detected by peripheral area. Based on this, it can be inferred that, 'entrepreneurial choice making is unswervingly inter - oriented to instantaneous accessibility, and effortlessness of analysis of pertinent 'material' evidence'. Neurophysiological experiments reveal that neurons in prefrontal cortex display saccade - oriented activity. Saccade - oriented activity in prefrontal cortex shows steering discernment and setting dependence. Inherent characteristics are parallel between pre- and post - saccadic activities. Above results indicate participation of prefrontal cortex participates in saccadic eye movements. Prefrontal cortex and eyes might contribute to saccadic eye movements. This does play role in cognitive functions or monitoring entrepreneurial behaviour.

4. 48 Results above study lend credence to aim of experiments undertaken in that, eye tracking methodology does help in investigating and corroborating dynamics of entrepreneurial choice making. Results exhibit substantial connection between

'subjective', 'physiological' and 'fixations' from real-world point of view. When entrepreneurs make choices, there's heavy disparity in comportment. 'Vacillating' entrepreneurs employ additional evidence when attempting a choice compared to 'definite' entrepreneurs. There were differences in the manner entrepreneurs scanned available information. While 'definite' entrepreneurs' spot on to a choice based on a particular trait, 'vacillating' entrepreneurs take in all of the 'material'. 'Definite' entrepreneurs perhaps opine that all options have 'good' and 'bad' characteristics. But they prefer a feature that is presumably important. 'Vacillating' entrepreneurs observed and opined that all 'material's had some quota of 'good' and 'bad' points. Secondly, 'vacillating' individuals distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during their course of experimental observation. The 'definite' participants 'focused' on fewer attributes in order to make their choice. Interestingly, 'vacillating' entrepreneurs spent more time overall looking at nothing. The subjects looked at 'blank cells' in the 'grid' while (apparently) attempting to make a choice. This series of experiments theorises that undertaking entrepreneurs to 'cogitate' or 'reframe' selections before arriving at 'a choice'.

4.49 Prefrontal neurons display saccade - oriented action. Appreciating how entrepreneurial brain works is significant in footings of meaningful impact on cognitive functions. Pre-saccadic activity encrypts guidelines of eye movements. Brain filters out unwanted information when entrepreneurs shift vision from one target to another focal target. Complexity of (entrepreneurial) 'intended' choice problems increases with options and features of each available option. Neuro -'intended' choice from eye tracking processes (images and responses) to complex results, makes assumptions about how (entrepreneurs) make intended choices, defines link between (entrepreneurial) choices and (entrepreneurial) preferences. This postulates that entrepreneurs have full understanding of 'intended' choice problem and adopt optimising behaviour to create 'intended' choices. Neuro - ocular action, towards entrepreneurial- oriented behaviour, capable of explaining entrepreneurial choice making, on cognitive models of choice, recommends the following;

- Escape from clichés and arrangements,
- Challenge conventions,
- Generate options and alternatives,

- Strategize new designs and observe what happens, and
- Find new access opinions from which to change forward.

Inference

4.50 Neuro - ocular analysis is based on an assumption that there is relationship amongst fixations, gaze and what entrepreneurs are considerate in matters of choice. Insistently, prefrontal cortex of entrepreneurial brain is responsible for visual stability. Eye tracking techniques reveal ability to aid in entrepreneurial choice dynamics. Settings, lengths and records in prechosen 'areas of interest' with transitions indicate 'degree of attention allocation' to prechosen areas. These exhibit how choice making can be explored with eye tracking techniques. It reflects methodological concerns when interpreting 'inferential' data. Research needs renewed thinking and undertaking things to address them. Primarily, sometimes fixations do not necessarily translate into conscious cognitive process. For example, during a search task one can easily fixate briefly on search object and miss its presence, especially if object has unexpected shape or size. This happens as expectations of which object should look like modulates ocular attention further interferes with object detection. As inference, above study attempts to explore phenomena through neuro - ocular action, management - oriented choice and reasoning processes on cognitive models of choice. This provides framework for understanding and conducting research at intersection of brain and eye - based models capable of predicting management - oriented behaviour capable of explaining entrepreneurial choice making.

4.51 Eye tracking measures provide non-invasive indices of brain dynamics. Apparently, gaze examination divulges attentional and cognitive approaches. Ocular measures deliver perceptions concerning cognitive expanses. As a concluding note to this Chapter, this thesis advocates auxiliary inquiries to scan physiognomies of saccade - related dynamics in prefrontal cortex and the conceivable influences to eye movement mechanism and related - prefrontal functions. Eye tracking offers novel peep into choice management.

Fig - 1

CHOICE FLOW PATH

Courtesy: Wikipedia

SKETCH DEPICTING EYE MOVEMENTS

Fig - 2

SKETCH DEPICTING EYE ACTIONS

Fig – 3

Fig – 4

TOBII TRACKER

TOBII TRACKER CONFIGURATION

Fig – 5

KOWLER MODEL

Courtesy: Prof Kowler (Rutgers University, USA)

TIME TO FIXATE

Time to Second Fixation

Fixation observation 4.JPG1Mean Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG1Sum
 Time to First Fixation observation 4.JPG2N Time to First Fixation
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 Percentage Fixated observation 7.JPG10Mean Percentage Fixated observation
 7.JPG10Sum Percentage Fixated observation 7.JPG8N Percentage Fixated observation
 7.JPG8Mean Percentage Fixated observation 7.JPG8Sum Percentage Fixated
 observation 7.JPG9N Percentage Fixated observation 7.JPG9Mean Percentage
 Fixated observation 7.JPG9Sum

Rec 01	1	1.20	1.20	1	18.39	18.39	1	23.75	23.75	1		
	26.07	26.07	1	8.75	8.75	1	3.19	3.19	1	14.00		
	14.00	1	8.66	8.66	1	2.32	2.32	1	5.56	5.56	1	
	0.15	0.15	1	0.11	0.11	1	0.44	0.44	1	0.07	0.07	1
	0.17	0.17	1	0.39	0.39	1	0.17	0.17	1	0.17	0.17	1
	0.24	0.24	1	0.16	0.16	7	0.19	1.32	12	0.19	2.27	1
	0.44	0.44	7	0.12	0.82	2	0.12	0.25	10	0.19	1.94	1
	0.17	0.17	7	0.15	1.06	3	0.16	0.47	4	0.15	0.58	1
	1.32	1.32	1	2.27	2.27	1	0.44	0.44	1	0.82	0.82	1
	0.25	0.25	1	1.94	1.94	1	0.17	0.17	1	1.06	1.06	1
	0.47	0.47	1	0.58	0.58	1	7.00	7.00	1	12.00	12.00	1
	1.00	1.00	1	7.00	7.00	1	2.00	2.00	1	10.00	10.00	1
	1.00	1.00	1	7.00	7.00	1	3.00	3.00	1	4.00	4.00	1
	1.72	1.72	1	2.78	2.78	1	0.44	0.44	1	1.23	1.23	1
	0.25	0.25	1	2.28	2.28	1	0.17	0.17	1	1.73	1.73	1
	0.94	0.94	1	0.85	0.85	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	
	100%	100%										
Rec 02	1	3.97	3.97	1	29.23	29.23	1	35.48	35.48	1		
	39.96	39.96	1	14.63	14.63	1	12.08	12.08	1	45.81		
	45.81	1	22.38	22.38	1	3.13	3.13	1	17.22	17.22	1	
	0.14	0.14	1	0.29	0.29	1	0.21	0.21	1	0.97	0.97	1
	0.20	0.20	1	0.25	0.25	1	0.41	0.41	1	0.27	0.27	1
	0.21	0.21	7	0.34	0.34	7	0.22	1.54	16	0.22	3.45	8
	0.22	1.77	13	0.35	2.44	13	0.24	3.07	15	0.28	4.22	9
	0.23	2.04	15	0.19	2.91	8	0.24	1.95	10	0.20	2.01	1
	1.54	1.54	1	3.45	3.45	1	1.77	1.77	1	2.44	2.44	1
	3.07	3.07	1	4.22	4.22	1	2.04	2.04	1	2.91	2.91	1
	1.95	1.95	1	2.01	2.01	1	7.00	7.00	1	16.00	16.00	1
	8.00	8.00	1	7.00	7.00	1	13.00	13.00	1	15.00	15.00	1
	9.00	9.00	1	15.00	15.00	1	8.00	8.00	1	10.00	10.00	1
	1.64	1.64	1	3.77	3.77	1	1.89	1.89	1	2.55	2.55	1

3.34	3.34	1	4.56	4.56	1	2.70	2.70	1	3.77	3.77	1
2.15	2.15	1	2.32	2.32	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	1
100%	100%										
Rec 03	1	3.18	3.18	1	31.36	31.36	1	49.27	49.27	1	
53.08	53.08	1	18.93	18.93	1	8.97	8.97	1	42.40		
42.40	1	20.88	20.88	1	3.93	3.93	1	14.64	14.64	1	
0.26	0.26	1	0.28	0.28	1	0.26	0.26	1	0.77	0.77	1
0.35	0.35	1	0.25	0.25	1	0.31	0.31	1	0.33	0.33	1
0.33	0.33	1	0.13	0.13	9	0.27	2.40	20	0.30	6.05	4
0.42	1.68	9	0.27	2.39	12	0.27	3.20	15	0.28	4.15	13
0.30	3.92	11	0.29	2.28	11	0.24	2.65	6	0.24	1.42	1
2.40	2.40	1	6.05	6.05	1	1.68	1.68	1	2.39	2.39	1
3.20	3.20	1	4.15	4.15	1	3.92	3.92	1	2.28	2.28	1
2.65	2.65	1	1.42	1.42	1	9.00	9.00	1	20.00	20.00	1
4.00	4.00	1	9.00	9.00	1	12.00	12.00	1	15.00	15.00	1
13.00	13.00	1	8.00	8.00	1	11.00	11.00	1	6.00		
6.00	1	2.58	2.58	1	6.71	6.71	1	1.73	1.73	1	
2.73	2.73	1	3.68	3.68	1	4.70	4.70	1	4.15	4.15	1
2.47	2.47	1	3.06	3.06	1	1.57	1.57	1	100%	100%	1
100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	
100%	100%	1	100%	100%							
All Recordings	3	2.78	8.35	3	26.33	78.98	3	36.17	108.50	3	
39.70	119.10	3	14.10	42.31	3	8.08	24.24	3	34.07		
102.21	3	17.31	51.93	3	3.13	9.38	3	12.48	37.43	3	
0.18	0.55	3	0.23	0.68	3	0.30	0.91	3	0.60	1.80	3
0.24	0.72	3	0.30	0.89	3	0.30	0.89	3	0.26	0.77	3
0.26	0.78	23	0.21	0.63	23	0.23	5.27	48	0.25	11.77	13
0.30	3.88	23	0.25	5.66	27	0.24	6.52	40	0.26	10.32	23
0.27	6.14	30	0.21	6.25	22	0.23	5.07	20	0.20	4.02	3
1.76	5.27	3	3.92	11.77	3	1.29	3.88	3	1.89	5.66	3

2.17	6.52	3	3.44	10.32	3	2.05	6.14	3	2.08	6.25	3
1.69	5.07	3	1.34	4.02	3	7.67	23.00	3	16.00	48.00	3
4.33	13.00	3	7.67	23.00	3	9.00	27.00	3	13.33		
40.00	3	7.67	23.00	3	10.00	30.00	3	7.33	22.00	3	
6.67	20.00	3	1.98	5.94	3	4.42	13.27	3	1.36		
4.07	3	2.17	6.52	3	2.42	7.27	3	3.84	11.53	3	
2.34	7.02	3	2.66	7.97	3	2.05	6.15	3	1.58	4.74	3
100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%		
300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	
100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%				

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	0.30	0.42	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.30	0.29	0.24	0.24	2.40
	1.68	2.39	3.20	4.15	3.92	2.28	2.65	1.42	9.00	20.00
	9.00	12.00		15.00	13.00	8.00	11.00	6.00	2.58	6.71
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26.33	36.17	39.70	14.10	8.08	34.07	17.31	3.13	12.48	0.18	
	0.23	0.30	0.60	0.24	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.26	0.21	0.23
	0.30	0.25	0.24	0.26	0.27	0.21	0.23	0.20	1.76	3.92
	1.89	2.17	3.44	2.05	2.08	1.69	1.34	7.67	16.00	4.33
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First Reference Run

GazePlot
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Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:19.987
Participant filter: All Participants
Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

Choice are limited to: **One**, Move from hierarchy self -
organisation. **Two**, Move from top to edge of organization, where
information is freest and simplest. **Two**, Move from protecting
information to democratization of information. To empower
employees to make decisions, make communication frictionless.
Three, Speed up interactions. Accelerate speed of interaction as
much as possible. **Last**, Simple rules to make quick decisions,
rather than perfect analyses.

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片5.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:11.612
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

Furthermore, they do not know how to respond or deal with VUCA. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity each component poses exceptional challenges. Therefore, business leaders should be able to identify each component with separate and unique response. They should start transition.

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片4.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:30.387
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

There is a need to overcome the state of VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity) and reorganize business aspects. Unpredictable events happening outside can be negative or positive. Each researcher agrees VUCA. This which makes it more difficult for leaders to make decisions. The experiment revisions how business can manage change process in rapidly changing, chaotic and turbulent business environment. Leaders need to act as a change agent. They need to play important role in initiating, implementing and managing change in times of crisis under severe, uncertain and complex condition.

GazePlot
 Media: 投票片3.PPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:01:37.453
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投票片3.PPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:05.583
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
Media: 投影片1.JPG
Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:04.302
Participant filter: All Participants
Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

HeatMap
Draw: 8975 μ s
FIS: 111
0 213
counts

Options limited to FLIGHT (Should Manager fight) forces of Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity, FRIGHT (Should Manager escape) from Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity situation or get a FRIGHT (Should Manager get frightened) and live along with Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity.

choices are limited to: **One**, Move from hierarchy to self-organisation. Push decisions down to edge of organization, where information is freshest and salient. **Two**, Move from protecting information to democratization of information. To empower employees to make decisions, make communication frictionless. **Three**, Speed up interactions. Accelerate speed of interaction as much as possible. **Last**, Use simple rules to make quick decisions, rather than perfect analyses.

Furthermore, they do not understand how to respond or deal with VUCA. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity each component poses exceptional challenges. Therefore, business leaders should be able to identify each component with separate and unique response. They should start transition.

There is a **need to** overcome this state of VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity) and re-align business prospects. Unpredictable events happening outside can be negative or positive. Each present greater VUCA. This which makes it more difficult for leaders to make decisions. The experiment revisions how business can manage change process in rapidly changing, chaotic and turbulent business environment. Leaders need to act as a change agent. The need to play important role in initiating, implementing and managing change in times of crisis under severe, uncertain and complex condition.

Global commercial crisis has led to a dramatic change in business world. Many organisations and managers are struggling to stay afloat and aligned in volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous nature of today's global and local business environment. Turbulence, rapid rate of change, is swirling around many of us, tipping us this way and that, as we attempt to navigate a safe passage through it all. Most businesses are suffering from uncertainty and complexity where business decision making is a probability. As a result, business leaders are suffering huge loss.

HYPOTHESIS

Complex business situation leads to wrong decisions

VUCA The Hidden Story

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片7.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:11.676
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

Second Reference Run

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片7.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:31.484
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片6.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:01:02.482
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片5.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:27.798
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影屏4.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:49.429
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影屏3.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:30.864
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片2.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:09.767
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片1.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:04.103
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

Options are limited to **FIGHT** (Should Manager fight) focus of Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity, **FI** **T** (Should Manager escape) from Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity situation or get a **FRIGHT** (Should Manager get frightened) and live along with Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity.

Options are limited to: **One**, Move from hierarchy to self-organization. Push decisions down to edge of organization, where information is freshest and salient. **Two**, Move from putting information to decentralization of information. To empower employees to make decisions, make communication frictionless. **Three**, Speed up interactions. Accelerate speed of interaction as much as possible. **Last**, use simple rules to make quick decisions, rather than perfect analyses.

Furthermore, they do not understand how to respond or deal with VUCA. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity each component poses exceptional challenges. Therefore, business leaders should handle each component with sensitive and unique response. They should start transition.

There is **need** to overcome this state of VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity) and align business prospects. Unpredictable events happening outside can be negative or positive. Each present enter VUCA. This which makes it more difficult for leaders to make decisions. The experiment reveals how business can manage change process in rapidly changing, chaotic and turbulent business environment. This is need to act as a change agent. They need to play important role in initiating, implementing and managing change in times of crisis under severe, uncertain and complex condition.

Global commercial crisis has led to a dramatic change in business world. Many organisations and managers are struggling to stay afloat and aligned in volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous nature of today's global and local business environment. Turbulence, rapid rate of change, is swirling around many of us, tipping us this way and that, as we attempt to navigate a safe passage through it all. Most businesses are suffering from uncertainty and complexity where business decision making is a probability. As a result, business leaders are suffering huge loss.

HYPOTHESIS

Complex business situation leads to wrong decisions

VUCA : The Hidden Story

Third Reference Run

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片4.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:01:04.597
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片3.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:52.962
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

GazePlot
 Media: 投影片2.JPG
 Time: 00:00:00.000 - 00:00:07.362
 Participant filter: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

gazePlot
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 Participant Error: All Participants
 Number of participants included: 1/3 (33%)

Heatmap
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 FPS: 91
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Options are limited to: One, Stay in hierarchy to self-organization. Push decisions down to edge of organization, where information is freshest and salient. Two, Move from producing information to democratization of information. To empower employees to make decisions, make communication frictionless. Three, Speed up interactions. Accelerate speed of interaction as much as possible. Last, use simple rules to make quick decisions, rather than perfect analyses.

Heatmap
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 FPS: 58
 0 479
 counts

Options are limited to: One, Stay in hierarchy to self-organization. Push decisions down to edge of organization, where information is freshest and salient. Two, Move from producing information to democratization of information. To empower employees to make decisions, make communication frictionless. Three, Speed up interactions. Accelerate speed of interaction as much as possible. Last, use simple rules to make quick decisions, rather than perfect analyses.

Furthermore, they do not understand how to respond or deal with VUCA. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity each component poses exceptional challenges. Therefore, business leaders should be able to identify each component with separate and unique response. They should start transition.

There is a need to overcome this state of VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity) and re-align business prospects. Unpredictable events happening outside can be negative or positive. Each present greater VUCA. This which makes it more difficult for leaders to make decisions. The environment of business is a manage change process in rapidly changing, chaotic and turbulent business environment. Leaders need to act as a change agent. They need to play important role in initiating, implementing and managing change in times of crisis under severe, uncertain and complex condition.

Global commercial crisis has led to a dramatic change in business world. Many organizations and managers are struggling to stay afloat and aligned in volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous nature of today's global and local business environment. Turbulence, rapid rate of change, swirling around many of us, approaching us way and that, we attempt to navigate a safe passage through it all. Most businesses are suffering from uncertainty and complexity where business decision making is a probability. As a result, business leaders are suffering huge loss.

HYPERTEXT
 Complex business situation leads to long decisions

U A Study

Conclusion

4.52 Making cogent psychosomatic decisions, in a state of Chaos and Resilience, is a management action. Cerebral Science (Cerebral Management) has made advances bringing unprecedented insights into human brain and decision making. Inquiry is witnessing multilevel research in organizational studies that integrates delineated research domains and offers novel lens for understanding business practice. Human organizations are at crossroads with cerebral and business laying a conduit that seems an abnormal approximation with infinite ‘Scrolling’, Chaos, Complexity and ‘Interpolations’. Impression that decisions are taken through rational or logical thought process have been exposed to questioning by experiments that analyses estimation during decision making. Reference is drawn to bio - processes that impact decisions, activate to differentiate based on multiple signals of origin, conditions that support or negate findings that aid understanding of how neuro - configurations influence decision making. Documentation of molecular and genetic markers precisely forecast rational physiognomies for understanding neural mechanisms of ‘Chaos’ and ‘Resilience’ in entrepreneurial decision making.

4.53 Are ‘business actors’ being threatened by ‘decision alarm’? ‘Business actors’ assume that decisions they take are rational, optimal and based on best accessible data. They postulate that they are in total appreciation of decisional behaviours. Such

propositions are now scanned under lens of cellular and chromosomal prisms. Issues like how decisional processes transgress in brain pathways, how brain considers sources of data and what intrinsic processes embody conflicting 'Chaos' and 'Resilience' values have been explored to design 'rational' decisions. Objective has been to monitor philosophy of neurobiological drivers in behavioural models towards understanding neurobiological drivers that underlie behaviour and decision making by means of fundamental tools from economics, psychology, neuroscience, mathematics and statistics. Major finding is that business actor attempts to decide and evaluates prospective decision in Chaos and Resilience conditions using blood glucose medium and eye tracking.

4.54 Entrepreneurs ('Actors') contract high uncertainty, ambiguity, time pressure and emotional stress. Neural mechanisms of behavioural strategy - based sustainable decision making require integration of evidence over time until a response threshold is reached. Cognito - management investigates behavioural strategy - based sustainable decision making by using 'Cognito - Tactical Monikers' (CTM) to investigate how brain behaves in circuit of higher cognitive functions. This has transitioned from mapping confined effects to evolving extrapolative models that assimilate data scattered across brain structures. In a progressively complex management milieu, entrepreneurs struggle between tactical arrangements and precise methods to gauge degree of accomplishment of predetermined goals. Behavioural strategy - based sustainable decision - oriented planning assists as 'catalyst' in terms of cognitive behaviours. There is need to understand behavioural - biological 'drivers' for investigating underlying behavioural - mechanisms of sustainable decision processes. Scope is to understand how entrepreneurial traits mapping divulge behavioural insight. The factual lateral lies on analysis of available verifiable, reliable and significant information, filtering and sieving of available information and accessing expressive information. This is supplemented by actions of behavioral compartments to further process interactive - oriented actions.

CHAPTER – V

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Overview

5.1 Behaviourism is the mirror that reflects penchants, philosophies, and other psychological states. Choice making is a rudimentary human action. Choices craft anthropological (and business) lives. The arena of (global) business is time and again acquiring a multifaceted, multifarious, complicated and a knotty architecture with wide - ranging and vigorous, originality and novelty that has developed as a catalyst for performance and concert for business and business management albeit the problematic settings. In such a mosaic of conditions, it becomes vivacious to fruitage powerful, astute businesses that generate enthusiastic doppelgänger of entrepreneurship.

5.2 The world of management is in acceptance to the fact that the classical boundaries, frontiers borderlines and front lines between undercurrents of economics, psychology, commerce, markets and business has amalgamated into a unified scholarship notably; Neuromanagement. Neuro - management challenges customary management postulates. This 'New World' has covertly and overtly embraced the world of neuroscience, neurobiology and multidisciplinary science (undercurrents of heredity, genetics, molecular biology and cellular sciences) that syndicates neurophysiology; all five sense organs included. This cumulative dynamics (science of 'choice behaviour' concept of 'thought') has embraced allied physiological mechanics like gut feeling, emotions, eye tracking, eye tracing, eye gazing, heartbeat, blood chemistry skin conductance and along with the dynamics of choice making has given birth to an 'Era of Neuromanagement'; that symbolises a spate of bio (economic) - revolution. This has in fact generated waves that obligated choice behaviour and accretion of choices. Not to forget is the association of considerations of Darwin's Survival of the Fittest (best 'fitted,' or best 'adapted,' to its atmosphere is most likely to occur).

5.3 Humans take choices by conforming to laws of rationality incorporating the paradoxes. For any economist, analysing choice centers on the world of prediction. Based on strong axiomatic pedestals, arguments profess 'should' or 'could' directives primarily based on a strict regimen of algorithms. These generated normative theories. Psychologists appreciate

psychological constructs that escort choice making. They predict behaviour and capture 'mental events' that go beforehand choice. Neuromanagement appreciates neural architecture alleyways and designs to reach at choice making comportment. Irrespective of the scholarship angle, aim is to select as a course of action and arrive to a solution that ends uncertainty (or imperfect knowledge) or dispute in course of choice making. This act is primarily centered on 'expected utility' dynamics. It is perceived that some amount of (cognitive) bias does seep in the process. This is for the reason that some element of bias, gut feeling, tastes, preferences and belief / faith coupled up with intuition (reference is drawn to concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception) does make way into choice processes. It is here that brain; sense organs, heart, skin, blood and eye have a role to play in gathering real time information and aiding real - time choice making. Issue is, is there an extraordinary function for neuromanagement or neuroeconomics, and, if so, what are its suitable exploratory philosophies?

5.4 This thesis outmaneuvers basic safekeeping that neuroscience, neuroeconomics and neuromanagement cannot sway business modeling. This norm or code is on '*Behavioural Sufficiency*' (causative circuit elucidations of behavioral external stimuli dimensional challenge) and '*Emergent Phenomenon*' (soupçon corresponding to connections that harvest qualitatively innovative topographies not initiated in its integral fragments physiognomies of necessity and independence) guiles. Each experience perceived by brain, blood and eye(s) are in sync with transferences of neuronal activity achieved by each event being perceived as evidence from neuro - mechanisms. This provides conceptual geometry for conducting neuro - entrepreneurial translational research science. It rears few fundamental issues and offers solution through measurement of brain, blood activity at management levels of analysis (Satpathy and Gankar; 2016).

5.5 Entrepreneurial prototypes are fundamentally instantaneous with operational originality. Voyaging through 'bustamination' ('business' and 'contamination'), entrepreneur is diagonally at cater - cornered with neuroscience, neuroeconomics and neuromanagement. Entrepreneur thereby covertly and overtly communicates a perceptive organised linkage ('Chess Board Matrix') perceived as 'nonconforming approximation' with business replicas' and 'disruptors'. This is chaotic 'noise' that calls for 'Entrepreneurial Choices'. There is domineering need to embrace variegated and propagation perpetually embracing neural mechanisms of perceptual practices fundamental

to state of 'Homo - Neuropsychoeconomicus. This buttons 'Homo Economicus' by replicating how technology receptive entrepreneurs are influenced by psychological, molecular, genomic and (neuro) cognitive conformations (involved in representation and selection of choice opportunities).

5.6Of interest is how entrepreneur brain captivates to acclimate to inform and improve entrepreneurial choice mechanism in a state of complexity and uncertainty (or imperfect knowledge). With crossbreed choice making prototypes, questions are; Do entrepreneurs actually, grounded on facts, figures, data, information and statistics have a choice? How do they skim off on an action in a state of unbounded 'scrolling' and perpetual 'disorders'? What 'neuro pointers' and 'neuro - monikers' relate to amenable conclusions? Will neuro entrepreneurial dynamics usurp orthodox cognitive arrangements associating neuro - integrated course to reconnaissance neuro - milieus in 'entrepreneurial' choices? As a trade-off between accurateness and explicate ability, experiments based on methods and approaches from Eye Tracking and Blood Monikers physio-diagnostic data have been offered that encompasses porches of biological basis of preferences traveling significant role of 'neurronics' in crafting entrepreneurial neuro - based preference flight path. This translational research communication attempts at addressing how neuro apparatuses explore entrepreneurial preference making.

Motivation

5.8Motivations for this thesis was on account of the fact that human brain is a bioelectric organ that has gradually allowed social and neural sciences to effect a marriage and share a common concentration. Choice making is critical for any entrepreneur when crafting and executing strategies. Interconnection plays central role. What typifies notion of causation in sciences of mind and brain? Are dissimilar notions a prerequisite for different experimental approaches? Are there variances in notions that are explicitly and implicitly presumed? What counts as causal evidence in entrepreneurial choice sciences? What role is played by information and physical mechanisms in identifying causal claims of entrepreneurial sciences of mind and brain? Documentation of molecular and genetic markers precisely forecast rational physiognomies for appreciation cognitive and neural mechanisms of individual choice making. An emerging new paradigm, through brain's wiring diagram, thesis adopts to examine potential cause - consequence linkage between

biology (neurobiology of choice making) and management in explaining how entrepreneurs deal in choice dynamics.

5.9 Human beings seldom make decisions on a random note. Central motivation is to go up in price nature of a hybrid scholarship that serves as central or entrepreneurial assumptions rather than theories. Considering the above, based on neural underpinnings, raise the following questions: Is a theoretical charter missing in entrepreneurial neuroscience? Moreover, if not, to what magnitude does it have a theory? In what ways does theory or conceptual architectural framework it has compare to those of more established sciences? What consequences might these differences have for a reasoning of neuroscience? The bottom contour is: Can there be reasoning of neuroscience without a broad or successful theory? All these prompted to explore the links between entrepreneurial choice making and neuroscience. Perceptions into mechanisms help develop an important question; what is then the role and connection of neuromanagement? What do brain, blood and eye(s) tell about management? How is the big picture for neuromanagement going forward? choice making involves forming a perceptual representation of choice base.

5.10 There are four major motivations for this work of translational research: -

- First, few management investigators are passionate to study character of neuromanagement in entrepreneurial choice making dynamics. Herein exists an opportunity to undertake an examination into the subject.
- Second, neuromanagement translational research arrange for new way of computing entrepreneurial choice. This provides stimulus to undertake an inquiry.
- Third, neuromanagement serve as 'catalyst' for model development.
- Fourth, 'inferential' information and neuroscientific representations stimulate to start a fresh inquiry into the subject.
- Fifth, neuromanagement provides ways to test choice observables and computational (neural) mechanisms?

Neuro - Continuum

5.11 Some decisions by human brains are influenced by atoms of irrationality, molecules of impulsiveness and particles of emotions. Neuro - Continuum has encompassed business atmosphere and human organisations with neuroscience and business spreading a linking

that seemed an uncharacteristic guesstimate. There is a 'heterodoxian noise' for a disruptive strategy to make choice making a reality via unconventional strategy. Hybrid intuition - based (reference is drawn to the concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception) 'disruptive mental' approximations' models are emerging as alternative to model complex systems under improbability. Do entrepreneurs have all data they need? Are entrepreneurs still using precise models? Is there new analysis or heterodoxian insight that could make entrepreneurs operative? Crucially, do entrepreneurs choose what stroke to take? What heterodoxian physiognomies of substitutions aid intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations'? How to help entrepreneurs cultivate choice and intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations' skills? Will heterodoxian neuromanagement replace conventional management? This thesis intends to explore an elucidation linked to 'busitagion' scenario via cause and effect linkage.

5.12 Behavioural management has shown that entrepreneurs do not always work in ways that management theories envisage. Entrepreneurs, as humans, are subject to of thoughts, attention, logic, *mirror image* and speculation. Brain has been a subject of the evolutionary processes. All these subscribe to a series of emotions? *In such milieu, how are brain, blood and eye(s) systems responsible for choice making process?* Is it correct and precise to think of brain, blood and eye(s) as calculating device? Does scholarship profess and acknowledge as to what should neuroscience or neuromanagement inherit from computationalism (neural mechanisms)? *How to craft laboratory and field based, as deemed appropriate, experiments to study choice making in choice - demanding situations?* In specific, how does biology, neuroscience and neuromanagement provision and oblige choice making. These questions include tenets from psychology, behavioural management, cognitive, neuroscience and allied subjects. This is the new signature paradigm in entrepreneurial choice dynamics with logic advanced from dissimilar approaches using divergent methodologies. What neuromanagement prepares, one would be prudent enough to just endure to coat it as a black box? All above trends towards inference that neuromanagement is a perfect podium to exhibit that neuro - entrepreneurial sciences, can provide answer to issues in entrepreneurial choice dynamics. It is significant to arrive at a deduction that neuroscience, and neuromanagement, follow '*Biological Plausibility*' (contributory linking flanked by acknowledged derivation and conclusion that is unwavering with ubiquitous biotic appreciation).

5.13 The dawn of substantial progresses has fashioned capability to scrutinize anthropological brain at an insightful glassy, yet scholastic and applied significance of prevailing confirmation centered on neuroscience procedures and approaches contained by pitch of entrepreneurship rests unmapped. Some issues from the discussions are as under;

- How to version confirmation about value, probability, risk, ambiguity and timing?
- How do above parametric indices perform?
- What distinguishes when criteria adopted are disparate?
- Are there any straight connexions that exist between the above tactics?
- How perceptible variables impact assortment of choice making criteria?
- Is there any link between peripheral variables and choice norm used?
- What kinds of set of rules and calculations underpin choice process?
- Which zones of brain, blood and eye(s) are implemented at neural level?
- How is management business choice made in intricate environs?
- How management sciences harness neuro - digital 'inferential' data for rational inquiry?
- What are the crucial 'neuro - ordered' domains and allied protocols?
- What mutual links occur between cognitive and effective processes?
- What are the neuro - behavioural management underpinnings?
- How does valence of evidence have emotional impact on choice?
- How do responsive and affective agents' / design parameters influence?
- How changes can be expounded by neuro - behavioural management?

5.14 As regards **discrete differences**, some entrepreneurial predicaments are;

- How do unconnected changes influence choice-making?
- How do stimulus and goal - orientation impact?
- What neuro - systems provision dissimilar motivational states?
- What neuro - behavioural processes differentiate 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents' of choice?

5.15 As regards **circumstantial stimuluses**, some entrepreneurial quandaries are;

- How do circumstantial connections encourage, provision or dent choice?

- How entrepreneurial standing influence choice?
- What are the effects of norms, pressures and stigma?
- What adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents influence process and quality of choice?
- How precisely are paradigms supposed to be encoded in neuro - physiological structures?
- How can discernments from neuromanagement be implanted?
- What has neuromanagement sponsored on 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents' not being rational?

5.16 **Investigational concerns** that aid in exploring the above issues are: -

- How does entrepreneur decide in a state of Vacillation, Risk and Probability?
- How does entrepreneur decide in state of Uncertainty, Vulnerability, Complexity and Ambiguity?
- What neuro - biological monikers aid in deciding?

Objective of Study

5.17 The principal attempt launched in this research thesis was to cast eye on tumultuous issues engulfing world of business and primarily that of choice processing. Care has been allotted for 'disruptive mental' approximations'. This is from a principle - based outlook to report research problem based on empirical study. Principal aim is to model entrepreneurs' choice making by using tools from neuro - management. This translational thesis presents neuro-entrepreneurial science of management modeling approach. This is to create evidences for multiple systems involved in entrepreneur s' choice-making. Besides principal objective, following objectives are taken into consideration for present translational research work;

- Criteria (physiognomies that each alternative own) adopted for choice making,
- Methodology of assessing cases for choice making,
- Variables that emphasizes choice making,
- Choice perspectives as regards (UVCA), and

- Conduct neuro - based interpretation on entrepreneurs' choice making.

Scope of Study

5.18 The backbone of this thesis that embodies translational research depicting link between management and entrepreneurial neuromanagement is to explicate how choice makers inter-disciplinary field translational research makes choice by integrating management science, economics, neuroscience and psychology. Attempt encompasses irregularities that are gainsay with traditional entrepreneurial hypotheses, appraise choice making by combining methods such as behavioural, neurophysiological, experimental economics and develop choice models based on neural and psychological mechanism.

5.19 Scope underlines previous and present translational research progress regarding each perception and relates it to scope of this thesis. This thesis addresses perceptions, theories and models from cognitive science, psychology and biology standpoint. The scope ranges from entrepreneurs of small, medium and large units

Hypotheses

5.20 The hypotheses, adopted and tested are;

- Choices are made based on measurable and idiosyncratic results,
- Neuro undercurrents are obligatory to dynamics of entrepreneurs' choice,
- Entrepreneurs' harbour gradation of analytic thinking than pragmatic thinking style,
- Entrepreneurs' are susceptible to cognitive biases during choices and,
- Entrepreneurs' face intuitive perceptible during choices.

Research Methodology

5.21 Neuroscience is the new order in 21st Century neuro-entrepreneurial decision dynamics. Meandering along among finite or infinite alternatives, research was conducted with use of theoretical and experimental approaches according to a procedure consisting of selecting a research question, searching relevant and pertinent literature from management

science databases, choice making process and experiments of neurophysiological techniques like blood moniker analysis and eye tracking (adopted as a Test Case - cum - Pilot Study) as effective tool for experimental research.

5.22 Based on an inter - connected and hybrid pathway, methodology adopted has been to develop theoretical foundations, models and systems to provision choice making in highly complex, dynamic systems, operating in uncertain, resource-constrained situation. Although, based on neuro - operations translational research procedures, this translational research attempt includes multi - disciplinary emphasis to accommodate complex, multi-dimensional choice architectural frameworks.

5.23 For this purpose, methodology adopted is outlined below.

Conceptual translational research has been directed with use of literature inter - disciplinary review method consisting of following stages: -

- Choosing theoretical translational research queries,
- Literature probe in neuro - controlled 'inferential' catalogues,
- Congregation of selecting relevant literature, and
- Summarising and synthesising.

Empirical journeys, methodology comprises of inter - disciplinary tests on: -

- Character of 'Blood Signatures' and 'Eye Movements' in entrepreneurial choice mechanism,
- Empirical treatment of 'Blood Signatures' and 'Eye Movements' in entrepreneurial choice mechanism, and
- Introduce association between entrepreneurial choice 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents' / design parameters'.

Sample Population and Size

5.24 On focal radar were issues like, how to read minds (brain mapping), how to read facial expressions (anthropometrics), choice making ability (eye tracking and blood synthesis) and adopt style of management in future. Moot question is what insights can behavioural science give us about entrepreneurs and reactions / interplay with those entrepreneur's lead? A sample of 150 representative entrepreneurs) in Bhubaneswar have been chosen. Basic assumption is that samples so selected out of population are best representative of population under study.

5.25 This research incorporates stratified sampling methodology. The research architecture has been stratified into gender and age groups. Each echelon has been experimented as a self-governing sub-population, of which specific rudiments have been designated casually. This has facilitated to arrive at conclusions and interpretations about unambiguous subcategories that would have been lost in case of indiscriminate illustration. Such exercise facilitated a package of statistical estimates. By means of stratified sampling, approach was deemed to be appropriate than accumulating data transversely towards groups. Since each stratum was viewed and subsequently treated as self-determining populace, dissimilar sampling tactics has been adopted to dissimilar strata, theoretically empowering use of methodology best suitable for each acknowledged subcategory within populace.

Data Collection

5.26 **Primary data and knowledge** has been collected through process of pre-tested questionnaire, personal interviews and focus group interviews, personal observation, projective techniques, pilot survey to improve questionnaire, structured questionnaire, statistical choice sampling and naturalistic observation. Some part of the data was obtained from experiments conducted in Taiwan and a few papers were published of these. For empirical part, data has been collected through blood chemical analysis and eye training apparatuses. Blood analyzer equipment has been for blood parametric analysis and for eye movement analysis, Tobii equipment has been used.

5.27 **Secondary Data and Knowledge** has been chosen from web sources, business journals, dairy and desk sources etc. Engine Searches, where wide knowledge about

different areas was easily available, was relied upon. Data were also corroborated from archival records and diary translational research sources

Tools and Techniques

5.28 **Questionnaire:** It was proposed to implement open-ended questionnaire. Paper - and - Pencil Questionnaire administration, Computerized Questionnaire administration and Adaptive Computerized Questionnaire administration were contemplated for purpose of gathering information from respondents. Due to pandemic situation, questionnaires were floated through personal mails and some were floated through personal contacts.

5.29 **Statistical Techniques:** Once data / facts / information were obtained from primary and secondary sources, these were clinically tested through Blood Analyzer and Eye Movement Monitoring methodologies to establish a co - relation between variables aimed at typically summing up discrepancy between observed values and values expected under the model in question. The results have been corroborated about entrepreneurs choice making: dependency on characteristics, choice making biases and deliberate / intuitive reasoning approaches. Data obtained has been treated through;

- **Test** : Determine differences between means related in definite structures,
- **ANOVA** : Analyze differences among group mean and difference of variability,
- **Blood Analysis** : Check on physical and chemical properties of blood sample, and
- **Eye Movement** : Investigate dynamics of eye movements.

5.30 **Assumptions:** Assumptions engaged for this study are;

- Choice is clear and explicit ('Problem Transparency').
- Entrepreneur identifies relevant alternatives('Known Possibilities').
- All substitutions and extents are known,
- Predilections are perfect, persistent and unchanging,
- There is no time or cost constrictions,
- Final choice maximises gainful payoffs,
- Changes are ranked and assigned weights ('Clear Preferences'),
- Weightiness assigned are unchanging over time ('Constant Preferences'),

- Full information is available ('No Time or Cost Constraints'),
- Penchant unconventional yield highest perceived value ('Maximum Payoff'),
- Explanatory schemes can be advanced at neuroscientific and management levels of analysis, and
- There are judicious mappings among above levels of elucidation.

5.31 Limitations: Current lack of attainment and determination indispensable for corroborating models are outlined to weak theoretic representation of choice making in contemporary 'assortment. Contemporary models of choice-making are restricted in their capacity to deliver an all - inclusive appreciative of the arena. Limitations envelop two crucial issues. These are primarily methodological and limit neuro - behavioural management conceptual translational research that entrepreneurial science has difficulty accepting in. The issues are (i) low influence in existing neuroscientific studies lead to questions over generalisability of results, and (ii) fundamental inability to localise phenomena in brain, blood and eye (s). This thesis gauges the predictions for emerging field of neuromanagement to cast light on customary affirmative and normative queries. It contends that possibility for evocative influences, nevertheless frequently misinterpreted and recurrently exaggerated, is however contemporaneous. Limitations encountered during this study were;

- Anthropological aspects posed some manageable limits,
- Literature had to be scanned to study brain, eyes and blood dynamics in entrepreneurial choice making.

5.32 Application of eye tracking methodologies is currently a fresh attempt, world - wide, in brain, eyes and blood dynamics in entrepreneurial choice making. This thesis appreciates that study - involving use of brain, eyes and blood dynamics in entrepreneurial is time - consuming than studies encompassing only behavioural responses. Key limitation is that neuro - behavioural management approaches identify those regions of brain, blood and eye(s) that are stimulated when entrepreneurs are in constrained situations. These techniques in some way provide full explanation as to why entrepreneurs react in a certain fashion. A synergy between neuro entrepreneurial techniques and brain, eyes and blood experiments provide vision into appreciative entrepreneurial choice making. Alternatives

recommended for advancing studies are EEG, Skin Conductance, etc. for better appreciation the dynamics (outside the scope of this thesis).

5.33 **Contributions to Society / Existing Knowledge**

- Entrepreneurial neuro - management offers insights into nature of planned rationality.
- Entrepreneurial neuro - management provisions data in totting to those accessible from conjectural, experimental and investigational research on human comporment.
- Entrepreneurial neuro - management offers brain, eyes and blood dynamics - based solution to choice making.
- Outcome of study is beneficial to various stakeholders directly or indirectly associate with entrepreneurial decision actions.
- Study provides conceptual architectural framework for appreciation intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science and entrepreneurial choice.
- Study sheds light on reasons of entrepreneurial behaviour (and incongruities) that help build theories capable of amplification and forecasting business choice. This has been the principal bed - rock of the theoretical practicalities in this thesis.
- Dynamics of brain, blood and eye(s) activity affords information about underlying mechanisms brain, blood and eye(s) during business choice processes.
- Combining above disciplines gives interdisciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - entrepreneurial choice making that has eluded translational researchers. This has been a primary pedestal of experimental realities in this thesis.
- The research findings are important as foundation for future translational research and society at a large would get benefit from this study.

Chapterisation Schema

5.34 This work is compiled in the following Chapters.

Chapter - 1:Introduction

Within uncertainty, stress and strain environment, prospect to anticipate about neural mechanisms underlying entrepreneurial choice making, this Chapter introduces the thesis

under title of 'Introduction'. The Chapter revolves around 'human beings' and entrepreneurs as principal agents who attempt to 'push' towards constancy in choice dynamics. This Chapter presents 'biology - inspired entrepreneurial science' revolutions that originate from management (science of 'choice behaviour') and psychology (discipline of 'thought') with reference to brain, blood and eye(s). Attempt has been made to reveal as to how rational events are concomitant to neurophysiological chronicles. There are efforts to reveal brain, blood and eye(s) interrelations to appreciate how and why entrepreneurs make choices. Orientations have been made to compendium of subjects that challenge research. Entrepreneurial issues have been underlined that rear few central issues and offer solution through 'rationalism' scrutiny. Inspiration for undertaking this investigation has been accessible with *potential to propose central change in how entrepreneurs think, perceive and model choice*. Role of neuromanagement, brain and eye (s), opinions and sentiments, neurons, psychology, behavioural controlling, cognitive and sentimental neuroscience, entrepreneurial sciences, that possibly deliver answer to issues in entrepreneurial choice dynamics has been anticipated with orientation to '*Biological ('mental effort') Plausibility*'. *Entrepreneurial neuro - linkages have been initiated that develop around hematological, brain imaging and ocular (eye movements) considerations. Some empirical processes have been recommended that address core problem in conceptual choice exploration and advance fresh questions? Challenging observations, including some unexplained difficulties and objectives of proposed inquiry have been acknowledged. Hypothesis and research methodology have been offered that form pedestal of this analysis. A set of 'assumptions' and 'limitations' engaged for this inquiry is enumerated. Likely contributions to area of scholarship from this inquiry have been stimulated. Chapter I culminates with Chapterisation Schema' of this thesis.*

Chapter - 2 : Literature Survey

This Chapter rationales to present inter - disciplinary review of some neuro - based theories and methods used in entrepreneurial choice making. Challenge is to promote knowledge that apply outside lab and address complex challenges. This thesis relates assimilated economic -psychological viewpoint. To conduct a comprehensive review of literature pertaining to a dynamic and interdisciplinary subject of scholarship viz. neuro-preference architecture, review defied its scope with published journal thesis and books plus research literatures linked to bases, philosophies, methods and principles of neuro-

preference architecture. Some key words punched for purpose of reviews were neuro - preference, neuro - architecture, types, methods, classification of neuro-preference-architecture, neuro - preference reinforcement, neuro - facilitation, neuro-preference reduction, neuro - preference deficiencies, neuro-preference optimization, neuro-preference assessment and neuro-preference evaluation. Secondary sources were primarily from those extracted from published literatures by academic bodies and web search engines. Chapter describes rudimentary strengths and weaknesses of each characteristic with key references. Reviews include theories, investigational facts, figures, statistics, deductions, axioms, corollaries, inferences, conjectures and results of earlier studies well established in chosen area of inquiry; blood monikers, brain and eye(s). Focal point revolves around; neural processes underlying how entrepreneurs design preferences, understand methodologies of preference architecture using neuroimaging methodologies and integrating transdisciplinary research to preference management. These include pointers at functions of 'neuro - biologism'. Review attempts to assimilate transdisciplinary research by integrating theoretical issues in choice, involvement of neuro - behavioural management, 'opportunities' and 'limitations', that allow fresh perceptions into in what way models can be corroborated or equated.

5.35 Reviews indicate research gaps. This encompasses: -

- Neural level which proposes neural networks in preference,
- Biological attributes in evolutionary and cerebral relevance in preference,
- 'Anthropological' components that describe conscious among species,
- 'Psychological' aspects that provide definition to exact cognitions and emotions,
- 'Philosophical' dimensions that regards rational dimension of causes and effects, and
- 'Socio - entrepreneurial' dimensions that describe past and present experiences.

5.36 Principal gap observed is that there is no rock solid evidence as regards any study centering on role of blood monikers /signatures in entrepreneurial choice making, barring a negligible few. This research is perhaps a new step forward research in this area by using tools from neuro - management. This attempt could and does generate indications for manifold arrangements involved in entrepreneurs' choice making. Some inherent issues in entrepreneurial preference architecture are;

- Entrepreneurial preference under risk and ambiguity,
- Preference under conflict: hedonic vs. utilitarian approaches,

- Preference under conflict: time pressure, preference under conflict,
- Multi attribute entrepreneurial management preference,
- Inter-temporal preference,
- Construal model, loss aversion and reference-dependence,
- Probability assessments,
- Calibration, optimism and overconfidence,
- Causal reasoning and perception of randomness,
- Framing effects interpretation and consequences,
- Do feelings precede preference and role of emotions,
- Moral preferences and sacred values, trust and mutuality,
- Fairness, procedural approaches, imprecision and noise,
- Biases: implications, joint vs. Distinct modes of evaluation, and
- Innovative directions, topical perspectives and conceivable future developments.

5.37 In this, inter - disciplinary review, research gaps identified for investigations are;

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does entrepreneur decide? • How does entrepreneur decide in state of Risk and Probability? • How entrepreneur decides in Uncertainty and Ambiguity? • What is role of ‘bio - ‘agents’ in entrepreneurial preference architecture? • What is role of ‘eye - movements’ and blood monikers in entrepreneurial preference architecture? |
|--|

Chapter - 3 : Methodology and Research Design

Aim of this research segment is to comprehend subjects’ relevance judgment based on blood monikers eye tracking method. Fundamental inquiry has two components; First, how subjects’ blood monikers and eye tracking ‘inferential’ data are concomitant with fortitude of bearing of portions of content displayed. Next, connections crop up between blood monikers and eye tracking ‘inferential’ data with cognitive loads (‘mental effort’) during exploration tasks? Besides analysing questionnaire responses, principal methodologies adopted for this inquiry are Hematological tests and Eye Movement tests. Why do entrepreneurial choice researchers undertake experiments? Is it to test a notion or outcome

implications with experimental observations? Is it to explore causes of notion's failure? Is it to establish empirical regularities as basis for new notion(s)? Is it for comparing choice settings? Dynamics of eye movement, with connect to Prefrontal Cortex and Somatic (genetic) - markers, are 'catalysts' of neuro entrepreneurial choice. When entrepreneurs sort choices, they commit deviations in their signature behaviour. In neural computational simulations, each entrepreneurial choice task is signified by protuberance of neural activity. choice related neural activity has constituents of spiraling of activity and choice initiation to overcome choice to be completed.

5.38 Aim was to observe whether entrepreneurs were receptive and welcoming new ideas, fresh approaches and innovative thought processes. It was conjectured that any business entrepreneur who was 'high' on 'Openness to Experience' would be a go - getter / risk - taker on path of business - adventurism. The above analysis can be oriented to brain dynamics in that openness to experience is allied with distinction in brain assembly. They are comprehensive in thinking, spread - out in how they process information and those with higher percentage on any of the above factors tend to reason and act resourcefully. They view the world of business creatively different. Their brains and mind harbour important ocular and cognitive responses. There is an observed superior 'extensiveness, penetration and penetrability of business and choice awareness' and inclination to 'cognitively reconnoiter' intellectual information (ideas and arguments) plus sensory 'inferential' data. All these lend an important part in shaping business choice making inventiveness. The role of 'genetic - influence' is factored in at this stage of analysis. This is envisioned as critical in direction of client connections and inclusive *business* progress. They are allotting space towards turning all possibilities and probabilities into near - perfect outcomes and results. The respondents are perhaps attentive towards mind - set, relationships, perception, influence and thinking. They are tactical agents, trendsetters and transformation agents. They are dedicated to distinction, pellucidity and veracity.

5.39 This Chapter purports to craft an edifice of entrepreneurial neuro - choice making architecture via hybrid modeling attempts. Chapter depicts growing interest over last decade and half in exploiting and exploring probable links between human biology, management and organisation studies. This purports to cast greater attention to psychological processes in explaining entrepreneurial behaviour and choice effectiveness.

Chapter endeavours to create connection, through 'choice matrix' between neuromanagement and entrepreneurial choice with reference to neural actualities in development of models. Neuro - choice operant have been examined using between brain, blood and eye(s) activity measurement processes. For eye movement examination, inputs from Kowler Model, Fang Model, Orquin Model and Hochman Model has been adopted and incorporated in experimental portions of this thesis. For blood signatures examination, inputs from primary analyzer analysis have been dovetailed for understanding intersection of neuroscience, management and psychology. This is to offer neuro - based activity at time of entrepreneurial choice making, describe standard archetypes capable of envisaging observed entrepreneurial behaviour.

5.40 Some inquiries investigated during interviews were;

- How much 'time' do you give in choice making?
- How confident are you in correct choice making?
- What pointers indicate that choice making confidence has increased?
- What habits influence choice making?
- What are the 'risks' associated in choice making?
- Do you sometimes postpone choice making?
- Do values and principles play a role in choice making?
- Does choice making align with priorities and guestimated consequences?
- What complexities are intricate in choice making?

Chapter - 4 : Experiments: Analysis and Discussion

5.41 Human centric choices and choices define human beings. How to introduce a 'human centric choice'? In fact, what is a human centric choice? Is it a beginning or end to a specific contemplation? Do they have biological basis? Do these have bio - philosophical computational connotation? Are they regulated by some genetic 'drivers' like sense organs? Human centric choice archetype is concerned with perception underpinning driver centric choices. If yes, then who serves as 'driver'? Do these represent sweeping renaissance of primary concerns in understanding biology of human centric choice apparatus? This Chapter presents gist of experiments, results obtained, inferences drawn and general discussion on 'cause' and 'effect' relationship in gamut of entrepreneurial

choice making. Chapter emphasizes principally on abstract concerns involved in selecting inquiry method and estimating results by means of diverse practices. Principal aim was to conduct experiments by likening its message / outcome implications with experimental observations, explore causes, establish empirical regularities as basis for new theory, comparing environments by protuberance of neural activity. Methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary review approach. Principal methodologies tested are; hematological tests, eye movement tests by using Tobii apparatus and drawing deductions with reference to (entrepreneurial) choice making. Questionnaire analysis with psychological, neuro - behavioural and choice making' linkages have been presented. Interview responses add to analysis from qualitative perspective. The first analysis (Haematological 'Situation Reaction' Test) presents results of blood monikers from 150 respondents. Second, analysis (Neuro - Ocular 'Choice' Test) presents results of eye movements from 30 respondents. Methodology adopts inputs from Kowler, Hochman and Fang models. Objective is to learn about relevant eye tracking, designresearchquestions, tasksandpossiblemetrics, testingstimulus, createtests,analyse tracking 'inferential' data and generate result deliverables. Neuro - ocular analysis has been recommended as a framework for understanding and conducting research at intersection of brain and eye - based models capable of predicting and explaining entrepreneurial choice making.

5.42 Scope encompasses how neuro apparatuses explore entrepreneurial centric choice crafting. Attempt comprises corridor of neuroroot of preferences scrutinizing considerable role of 'neurotics' in prototyping entrepreneurial centric choice corridor. Cursors are dynamic 'drivers' and 'elements'. Objective was to exhibit theoretic and empirical mosaics in 'neuro - corridors' of centric choice corridor. Methodology includes observations with results displaying pointers for adlibbed counterfactual imitation in dominion of high - level cognitive. Major finding is that technopreneur endeavours to address neuro - mosaic using 'neuro - drivers'. Research communication discusses findings and future directions to guide neuro science in choice corridors.

5.43 The following deductions were obtained:-

- Hematological provisions instrumental evidence in entrepreneurial choice.
- Hematological 'tracking' is appreciated in technopreneur choice process.
- Hematological arrangements scrutinize choice - task approaches and cognitive capability

- Strong variations in hematological arrangements compartment represent choice certainty
- Observing hematological variables helps identify transitory situations of ambiguity.
- Hematological arrangements serve as calculation technique beyond customary scrutiny.

5.44 Psycho - cognitive progressions are prime catalysts to calculate different alternatives and weightages before inching towards a choice.

- Robust link among choice, choice and emotive courses appears to relate to approving heuristics; quick and instinctive,
- VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous) reshapes entrepreneurial world,
- Entrepreneurs in VUCA world cannot have a cinch,
- Entrepreneurs response and perception are part of choice making behaviours,
- Entrepreneurs use perception and skill to sense what should be done,
- Entrepreneurs use intuition courage of convictions to act conclusively,
- ‘Inferential’ data from each subject were analysed independently and observed that error rates were quite low.
- Observations were correct (85%) of the time.
- There was effect of presence of target item and memory set size on response accuracy.
- Real time ‘inferential’ data on correct references follow same pattern of large main effects for both factors: target presence and substantial interaction.
- Slope was significantly influenced by target presence.
- Behavioural results are in strong agreement with dwell time on references.
- Fixations could be interpreted in different ways depending on context and objective.
- During processing of neuro - ocular scene, individuals moved eyes to relevant features in that scene.
- Some features were primarily detected by peripheral area to infer that, ‘entrepreneurial choice making is unswervingly inter - oriented to instantaneous accessibility, and effortlessness of analysis of pertinent ‘material’ evidence’.
- Experiments reveal that neurons display saccade - oriented activity,
- Saccade - oriented activity show steering discernment and setting dependence.
- Results exhibit substantial connection between ‘subjective’, ‘physiological’ and ‘fixations’ from real-world point of view.
- ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs employ additional evidence when attempting a choice.

- ‘Definite’ entrepreneurs spot on to a choice based on a particular trait.
- ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs take in all of the ‘material’.
- ‘Definite’ entrepreneurs, perhaps, opine that all options have ‘good’ and ‘bad’ characteristics. ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs observe and opine that all ‘material’s had some quota of ‘good’ and ‘bad’ points.
- ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during experimental observation.
- ‘Definite’ participants ‘focused’ on fewer attributes in order to make their choice.
- ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs spent more time overall looking at nothing.
- Complexity of ‘intended’ choice problems increases with options and features of each available option.
- Entrepreneurs have full understanding of ‘intended’ choice problem and adopt optimising behaviour to create ‘intended’ choices.

Chapter – 5 : Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.45 Question of how entrepreneurs make choices and judgments continues to pose important challenges for scientific research. This Chapter summarizes all Chapters contained in this thesis. Chapter contains salient aspects as depicted in Chapters titled Introduction, Literature Survey, Entrepreneurial Neuro - Architecture and Experiments with Discussion. Chapter pools extrapolations drawn at various segments of thesis with analytical discourses. Chapter *suggests fundamental change in biological* (‘mental effort’) *Plausibility ‘of how entrepreneurs need to think, observe and model business choice in all its contexts.* With package of issues for further research, Chapter attempts to advocate intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science, management and psychology) towards providing conceptual framework for understanding and conducting entrepreneurial choice research for choice making.

Concluding Remarks

5.46 Business of choice making is central to entrepreneurs. A complex choice progression takes many stages. Despite inspiring accomplishments, neuro - behavioural management is at best a couple of decade old and is yet to embody critical role in neuro - behavioural management. Researchers are still rhetoric whether neuroscientific ‘inferential’

information will expansively provide for entrepreneurial choice. Focus is on obligatory frameworks for interdisciplinary alliance. Being a maiden inquiry, thesis attempts to underwrite towards existing scholarship in following mode;

- Provides frame for appreciating theoretical entrepreneurial choice research,
- Offers elucidation through dynamics of brain, blood and eye(s) during choices,
- Describes standard brain, blood and eye(s) based archetype for choice.

- Any entrepreneurs who was 'high' on 'Openness to Experience' would be a go - getter / risk - taker on path of business - adventurism.
- Entrepreneurs, at an appreciably young age, seems to establish powerful cognitive reflections.
- Entrepreneurs at appreciably middle age too seems to establish powerful cognitive reflections.
- Entrepreneurs at appreciably elder age seems to establish comparatively less cognitive reflections with some degree of lop - sidedness.
- It is inferred that young entrepreneurs belong to 'creative - flock' and are carriers of unambiguous cognitive aptitude, intellectual, ocular and emotion - laden engagement. There is a drive to engage in philosophies, cogent - oriented and a sense of openness. All these open doors and opportunities for creativity. In such a situation, component of decentralised choice making atmosphere is envisioned.
- The phenomenon is linked to 'brain dynamics' where 'openness' to experience is allied with distinction in brain assembly. Role of 'genetic - influence' is factored in at this stage of analysis.
- Training is observed to be a catalyst towards cultivating subjective efficiency in choice making. Corollary deduced is that positive mental attitude in business is an indispensable proposition for choice making dynamics. With patterns of brain activity changing consequent to training and adoption of a control strategy allows space for possibilities and probabilities in near - perfect thinking for choice arrival. Training captures emotional reactions that help initiate unconscious choices. Training leads to swing in sensory motor information through prefrontal cortex. Good training leads to a fine sense of choice making.

- Entrepreneurial life, as characterised by factors of production is spiral to profit intensification. Neuropsychology holds that there exists strong link between *profit maximisation* and survival in unpredictable business. When profit maximisation is reliable with high rates of persistence, respondents adjust conclusively towards an optimal state. When survival and profit maximisation are counter - balancing, respondents improve effort to persistence rates. All these influence choice design.
- Entrepreneurs are intuitively poised based on business information. They continuously attempt to act in a phase - wise manner of eternal economic and business surveillance. Strategic intelligence that enables to control things that thwart business prospects. It is observed that as regards corporate social responsibility and service to society are concerned; opinion is somehow a state of near - balance. With such falling percentages, choice to join business appears to be strong by majority of respondents. Correct information leads towards balanced choice design.
- There appears to be a mind - set that corporate social responsibility reduces profit margin as such projects do not lend towards a rising profit curve. Entrepreneurs opine that such projects would mean a 'stealing of rightful assets'. They need to focus on bottom line towards survivability. In view of profit maximisation psychology harboured by entrepreneurs, there exists no repudiating potency of this dispute. Irrefutably, corporate social responsibility has been accorded low priority. Concentration is more on business profit maximisation rather than corporate social responsibility agenda.
- Opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work finds favour with entrepreneurs. It is a booster aimed at human resources management and development that ultimately leads to organisation development. These act as top 'motivating agents'. 'Mind set' to perform are high on joining a business organisation. It is indicative that respondents are ready to move out of their 'comfort zones' and jump across the periphery.
- Preference for option of 'reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard', in current scenario, seems to be a depressing proposition. There seems to be an air of pessimism. Micro - neuroscience based treatment may offer that respondents can ward off with pessimistic tone if they develop an air of aficionado. This is offered from point of view of role of emotion in choice making. Robust optimism is the alley forward towards progress and choice making. 'Transcendence' (based on a 'gut feeling') scan be introduced as a 'potent' as effective and efficient entrepreneurs. Inference is that entrepreneurs put faith on intuition.

- In a world of unlimited choices, there is a spring of ridiculously high expectations. ‘Expectation to grow with career path clearly mapped’ finds favour where at least a blue print is available. With a set of well - defined purpose, vision, goal, skill, knowledge, attitude, competence, networking, mentorship etc. where career path is well - projected, respondents feel that such resources are premeditated to help recognise skills and aptitudes to advancement within business domain. Such an expectation takes birth from environmental and societal realisms which aid choice making. This is because the blue print appears to decide as to what is required to subsist in a business world.

Recommended Issues For Future Research

5.47 Building a bridge between entrepreneurial choice making with neuromanagement and neuroscience, this inquiry leads to the pronouncement that neuromanagement, neuroeconomics, neuro - choice and neuro entrepreneurial choice is the ‘Order’ of 21st Century business dynamics. The flow from biological perspectives of choice making to entrepreneurial choice dynamics is gaining momentum.

5.48 This inquiry has attempted to explore whether neuroscience contribute to business choice management or has it already influenced management with its characteristic positioning? If this is so, what principles about neural apparatuses could have triggered this ‘swing’ or a shift of conception? In such a scenario, how do entrepreneurs decide in a state of VUCA where vacillation is the pivotal phenomenon? Juxtaposed is the issue of role of prefrontal cortex, somatic markers and eye movements in (entrepreneurial) choice making. With an eye to gain an optimal choice, how do entrepreneurs bargain ‘hot buttons’ in business choices?

5.49 As regards neural actualities, on a bio - choice plane, this inquiry attempts to penetrate into brain - choice reproductions? How can management sciences harness digital ‘inferential’ data for logical inquiry? What are the crucial geometric domains? Are there direct correlations that exist between external variables and choice criterion approaches? What kinds of algorithms and computations are involved that underpin choice process? What is the character of innovative information (contextual or individual) in disproving or approving choice theories? Reference is drawn to brain expanse in a definite choice task that endures ‘reference’? Tagged along is the role of emotion regulation and emotional intelligence. What consequences might these differences have for a reasoning of

neuroscience? Can these be improved by incorporating number of insights from evolutionary theory and complex systems theory?

5.50 Scholarship shall stand enriched if future research attempts could cover the following to lend strength to the research inquiry initiated in this work.

- What are the underlying cognitive mechanisms of entrepreneurial choices and effectiveness?
- What is role of entrepreneurial cognitive influence in entrepreneurial choice making?
- What are the biological bases to bond optimal data, neural activity and choice making?
- What are the causal cognitive mechanisms of entrepreneurial choices?
- What is the bearing of context and environment on entrepreneurial choice making?
- How neuroscientific measures in choice ‘drivers’ trigger choice behavioural?
- How to sketch ‘geometry of alternatives’ that govern entrepreneurial choice?
- What are the methodological aspects in entrepreneurial behavioural during VUCA?
- What are the complexities in entrepreneurial behavioural during VUCA?
- What appropriate data abstractions in eye tracking help choice representations?
- How to link blood moniker datasets with neuro entrepreneurial choice mechanism?
- How to link eye tracking and gaze datasets with neuro entrepreneurial choice mechanism?
- How to link sweat conductance datasets with neuro entrepreneurial choice mechanism?
- How to link olfactory aspects datasets with neuro entrepreneurial choice mechanism?

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Department of Psychology

School of Social Sciences and Humanities

NEURO - EXPERIMENT IN ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING

QUESTIONNAIRE

- Choice of answering is purely voluntary.
- Please answer 'Yes' (Y) or 'No' (N) against your option, as applicable.
- Please put tick [✓] mark against your option, as applicable.
- Please Rank factors [1, 2, 3 ...] as per your value judgment, as applicable.
- Please indicate SCALE to which you 'Agree' or 'Disagree' with a proposition, as applicable.

1	=	Strongly Disagree
2	=	Disagree
3	=	Neither Disagree nor Agree
4	=	Agree
5	=	Strongly Agree

PART – I

BIOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION

Name (Optional):

Gender

(Please put a √)

- Male []
- Female []

Age in Years

(Please put a √)

- 25 - 40 years []
- 41 - 55 years []
- 56 to 70 years []
- 70 years and above []

Education Qualifications

(Please put a √)

- Class 10 []
- Junior College []
- Degree and above []
- Post - Graduate and above []

Have you earned a Certificate in business education? **(Please put a √)**

- Yes
- No

Family Composition

(Please put a

√)

- Single []
- Married []
- 1 Child []
- 2 or 3 Children []
- 4 and above []

Size of Business Firm

(Please put a ✓)

- Large []
- Medium []
- Small []
- Start – up []

What is **primary business function?**
(mark)

(Please put a ✓)

- Human Resources Management []
- Finance Management []
- Information Management []
- Marketing Management []
- Production Management []
- Information Management []

What is the **level of business responsibility?**
(Please put a ✓ mark)

- Bottom - Level Management []
- Middle - Level Management []
- Top - Level Management []
- Strategic - Level Management []

What is the nature of business responsibility?
(Please put a ✓ mark)

- Planning []
- Organising []
- Directing []
- Controlling []

Length of Experience(in business)

(Please put a

√)

- Less than 10 years []
- Between 11 to 20 years []
- Between 21 - 30 years []
- Between 30 - 40 years []
- Above 40 Years []

PART - II

PSYCHOLOGICAL LINKAGE

Openness to Experience

Please subscribeto the following adjectives that describe you:

- Multifaceted []
- Resourceful []
- Deep []
- Reflective []
- Knowledgeable []
- Rational []
- Unproductive []
- Unchallenging []

What was the most **important factor** in your choice to join business?

(Please indicate *Scale*, 'Agree' or 'Disagree', as applicable)

- Training for business skills []
- Long run profit maximisation []
- Corporate Social Responsibility []
- Service to Society / Philanthropy []

- Maximisation of sales []
- Maximisation of shareholder value []
- Opportunities to develop by doing challenging and interesting work. []
- I have a reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard. []
- I expect to grow and my career path is clearly mapped out. []
- I come to work purely to get the business done. []
- My loyalty is defined and I feel part of a team in business. []
- I feel business reciprocates the effort put by me. []
- I am motivated to contribute 100% to business for future benefits. []
- I will work for business indefinitely. []
- I work to achieve goals of business. []
- Being able to change things, I do not like about my business. []
- Having a say about the way I do things in my business. []
- Chance to learn new things in my work. []
- Chance to use my abilities within my business. []
- Chance of achieving something worthwhile. []
- I work for profit and expect to be paid for overtime. []
- Business is a high - concert occupation. []

- Choice to remain involved (so) influential? []
- Business harnesses your potential. []
- ‘Carrot and stick’ approach of motivating works in business. []
- Managers in business evaluate different practices of management. []
- Above factors, reflect desired values and virtues in business. []
- Above factors contribute towards better environment. []

Please rank your proficiency about choice making

(Please indicate *Scale*, ‘Agree’ or ‘Disagree’, as applicable)

- No Proficiency []
- Little Proficiency []
- Average Proficiency []
- Good Proficiency []
- Very Good Proficiency []
- Rich Proficiency []

PART - III

Behavioural Aspects

Person - Business Fit

(Please indicate *Scale*, 'Agree' or 'Disagree', as applicable)

- Personal values are a good fit with business.
[]
- Business has same values as I do with regard to concern for others.
[]
- Business has same values as I do with regard to honesty and ethics.
[]
- Business has same values as I do with regard to fairness and justice.
[]

Work - Personal Interface (Please indicate *Scale*, 'Agree' or 'Disagree', as applicable)

- Business philosophy defines how to operate business. []
- Amount of work responsibility and norms of performance are centered on business. []
- Ties with present business are difficult to break and are central to existence.
[]
- Business shows concern and cares about opinions and well - being.
[]
- Business strongly considers goals and values.
[]
- Help is available when I have a problem.
[]

PART – IV

Economic Aspects

(Please indicate *Scale*, 'Agree' or 'Disagree', as applicable)

Profit and Wages

- Reward procedures in business are fair.
[]
- If I work hard and am productive, I am compensated by profits.
[]
- I have plenty of opportunities for growth / reward.
[]
- Those who deserve rewards receive them with fairness.
[]
- Business will notice if productivity or work quality declines.
[]
- Are you satisfied with amount of profit you generate? [YES
/ NO]

How satisfied were you with overall business benefit package?

(Please put a $\surd$ mark)

- Very Satisfied
[]
- Satisfied
[]
- Neutral
[]
- Dissatisfied
[]
- Very Dissatisfied
[]

PART - V

'CHOICE MAKING' ORIENTATION

How frequently each of the following, in the table presented below, relates to you? Please (Please rank factors: 1, 2, 3 ...)

Do you weigh 'plusses' and 'minuses' before deciding?

- Recurrently []

- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you take 'intelligence' over choices selected?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you decide on your own?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you deliberate when time is at a premium?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you plan in adequate time - frame?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you factor in 'ancillary' choice choices?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

When deciding, do you provision for 'first - look option'?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you favour to 'avoid' making choices?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you talk about choice making to others? (Please answer 'Yes' or 'No')

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you often change your mind?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []

- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you make choices without seeing implications?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Is your choice administered by principles?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you identify 'control of things'?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you remain calm during 'sudden' choices?

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Do you rely on 'gut feelings' when making choices? (Please answer 'Yes' or 'No')

- Recurrently []
- Intermittently []
- Occasionally []
- Hardly ever []
- Certainly not []

Why sometimes choices are not executed? (Please rank factors: 1, 2, 3 ...)

- Inadequate answer from management []
- Absence of significance []
- Poor mechanism of supervision []

To what range better 'industrial relations' aid towards choices? (Please rank factors: 1, 2, 3 ...)

- Very Operative []
- Greatly Operative []
- Somewhat Operative []
- Little Operative []
- Not Operative []

Choice Dynamics

(Please rank

factors: 1, 2, 3 ...)

- Remain confident to make choices []
- Know steps in choice-making []
- Have feel of commitment to crafting a right choices []
- Influence choices with 'certainty' factor []
- Make choices under 'time' density []
- Control level of concentration []

- Think openly and keep pertinent factors []
- Narrow down list of options
[]
- Determine assortment of alternative
[]
- Handle quantitative data to classify preferences, difficulties and explanations
[]
- Obtain information
[]
- Weigh consequences of each option
[]
- Evaluate business choice problem situation
[]
- Choose best alternative []
- Secure resources []
- Make choice and persevere with engagements []
- Refrain from postponing choice making []

Do you experience any of these while deciding?

(Please Tick)

Never Sometimes Repeatedly

Headaches /Migraine
Aches And Pains
High Blood Pressure
Poor Sleep Patterns
Skin Rashes
Indigestion
Stomach Ulcers
Asthma
Anxiety
Depression

Heart Disease
Changes In Appetite
Exhaustion
Increased Tobacco Use
Increased Alcohol Use.
Inability to concentrate
Erratic moods
Low self-esteem/confidence

While deciding do you feel any of the following: **(Please Circle)**

	Repeatedly	Never	Sometimes	
Irritated		1	2	3
Angry		1	2	3
Frustrated		1	2	3
Helpless		1	2	3
Anxious		1	2	3
Depressed		1	2	3
Unable to concentrate		1	2	3
Over tired		1	2	3

INTERVIEW SECTION

- How much 'time' do you give in choice making?
- How confident are you in correct choice making?
- What pointers indicate that choice making confidence has increased?
- What habits influence choice making?
- What are the 'risks' associated in choice making?
- Do you sometimes postpone choice making?
- Do values and principles play a role in choice making?
- Do choice making align with your priorities?

- Do you guesstimate consequences of choice making?
- Do you change your mind after creating choice making?
- What complexities are intricate in choice making?
- How do you deal with engagements in choice making?
- What steps you anticipate as regards risks in choice making?

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